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**Research Paper on:
INTERNATIONAL TRADE IN INDIA SINCE 1991
(An assignment for International Trade)**

Guided By:- Dr. Anjali Dash

**Submitted By:-Bibhuti Ranjan Das
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ABSTRACT

Foreign trade plays a vital role in Indian economy. As the country need to import diverse product so the foreign trade is extremely important to a country. India export vast number of product and also import equal amount of other product. Although India has steadily opened up its economy, its tariffs continue to be high when the compared to the other countries and its investment norms are still restrictive. This leads some to see India is a 'rapid Globalizer' while others still it is a 'highly protectionist' economy. Nonetheless , in recent year Government's stand on trade and investment policy has displayed a marked shift from protecting 'producer' to benefiting 'consumers'. India is now aggressively pushing for more liberal global trade regime, especially in services. This paper is an attempt to analyses the major change in volume, composition and direction of Indian foreign trade.

Introduction:-

Foreign Trade has been one of most significant determinants of economic development in a country. International trade related to the exchange of goods, services and factor among the different countries. International trade is the trade among the resident of different countries. Ordinarily, sale and purchase of goods is called trade. In the other word, The Foreign Trade of a country consists of inward and outward movement of goods and services, which result in to out flow and inflow of foreign exchange from one country to another country. During present time, international trade is a vital part of development strategy and it can be an effective instrument of economic growth, employment generation and poverty alleviation in an economy. Trade to be classified (a) Internal trade.

(b) International trade.

(a)Inter-regional/Internal/domestic trade:-

Internal refers to the trade refers to the trade carried out in different places and regions of the same country. It is also called national trade, inter-regional trade or domestic trade. In the other word Inter-regional trade is among people belonging to the same country even though they may differ on the basis of castes, creeds, religions, tastes or customs. They have a sense of belonging to one nation and their loyalty to the region is secondary. Trade between Punjab and Himachal Pradesh or Haryana and Gujarat, Odisha and Andhra Pradesh is an example of internal trade /domestic trade.

(b) International trade:-

International trade is trade between two or more than two countries. In the other word International Trade refers to the trading or exchange of goods and or services across international borders. Trade between India and USA is called international trade / foreign trade. The good and services consigned India to USA will be known as India's exports. On the other hand goods and services coming from USA to India will be called India's imports.

In 1991, the government introduced some changes in its Policy on trade, foreign Investment, Tariffs and Taxes under the name of "New Economic Reforms". The main focus of these reforms has been on Liberalization, openness and export promotion activity. India's foreign Trade has export significantly changed in the Post- reforms period. In absolute terms, Trade Volume rose and the composition of

exports has undergone several significant changes. In Post-reform Period, the major contributor to exports growth has been the manufacturing sector. This is really a welcome development and the trend needs to be strengthened further for the increased income through exports. The effect of liberalization on India's foreign trade the economy has greatly influenced. In this paper an attempt has been made to examine the growth and structure of exports in India during the period 1990-91 to 2020-21.

➤ Indian position in International trade:-

India's real gross domestic product (GDP) at current prices stood at Rs. 195.86 lakh crore (US\$ 2.71 trillion) in FY21 as per the second advance estimates (SAE) for 2020-21. Simultaneously, the per capita income at current prices was estimated at Rs. Rs. 127,768 (US\$ 1,765.43) in FY21. India's trade and external sector had a significant impact on the GDP growth as well as expansion in per capita income.

Total exports from India (Merchandise and Services) stood at US\$ 439.64 billion between April 2020 and February 2021, while imports totalled US\$ 447.44 billion, according to data from the Ministry of Commerce and Industry. Merchandise exports stood at US\$ 256.18 billion in 2020-21, while imports touched US\$ 340.80 billion. The estimated value of services export and import for 2020-21 stood at US\$ 183.46 billion and US\$ 106.64 billion, respectively.

According to Mr. Piyush Goyal, Minister for Commerce and Industry & Railways, the Government of India is keen to grow export and provide more jobs for young, talented, and well-educated people as well as for semi-skilled and unskilled workforce in India.

Literature review:-

Eminent researchers and academicians have started exploring this vague area of studies during the prevailing post reform situation. Few studies available have been reviewed related to the pandemic. Although, to gain greater insight into the area, literature available related with similar crisis faced by the world have been reviewed. Following are some of the prominent research studies conducted previously been referred in the study.

As a result of long term poor economic performance under protectionist policies, many developing countries including India started removing their barriers to international trade in late 1980s with an aim to improve economic development of the country. During the time of independence, the foreign trade of India was typical of that of a colonial and agricultural economy and the trade relations were mainly confined to Britain and other commonwealth countries. During the period 1950 - 1990, foreign trade of India suffered from strict bureaucratic and discretionary controls. Although the Indian foreign liberalisation era started in 1970's but only in A. Pushpalata Singh International Journal of Humanities Social Sciences and Education (IJHSSE) Page 12 the late 1980's and early 1990's, drastic changes have started taking place as far as Indian foreign trade is concerned. In 1991, the Government of India introduced series of economic reforms to liberalize and globalize Indian economy. Since the initiation of economic reforms, India's outward

orientation has started increasing. The Indian trade policy experienced various changes time to time after its initiation and the major changes included simplification of procedures, removal of quantitative restrictions and substantial reduction in the tariff rates. The policy regime in India with regard to liberalization of the external sector has brought tremendous changes in Indians foreign trade. Thus, it is in this connection that the present study aims to analyse the trend and composition of the foreign trade since 1991. but in 2020 the Indian foreign trade effect badly due to the /covid-19 pandemic .

According to P. Sahu, (2014) has analyzed the trends in India's exports from the period 1990-91 to 2019-20 in order to examine the impact of economic reforms on India's exports behavior. The study shows that India's exports performance improved significantly during the post -reform periods and there has been a remarkable change in the value, composition and direction of India's exports but India's share in the world exports is not satisfied.

According Gupta, S. (2019) in his paper studied the trend in foreign trade of India with the help of three parameters i.e. changes in value, direction and composition of foreign trade. The study found that in 1990-1991, export as percentage of GDP were only 5.8% which rose to 19.2% of total GDP in 2016-17. Regarding the composition of commodities, the researcher found that, apart from traditional goods, the percentage change in non-traditional good like chemical and engineering goods were also showing a higher rate of export. The major market for India's export was region developing countries and OECD countries.

According Virmani, A. and Bhasin, K. (2020) attempted to study the growth implication on Indian economy due to the outbreak of Covid-19. The study divided the economy into three major sectors- essential commodities, contact services and rest of the economy. The study highlighted that due to the lockdown measures taken by government, there was a decline in both demand and supply of goods and services except for food, beverage and pharmaceutical items. The study further revealed that Air transport, Hotels & Restaurants and Malls & shops (retailers) are considered as the most vulnerable sector due to Covid-19. However, the researcher mentioned in the study that Indian economy will start to recover from second half of 2020-2021.

Principle main finding shows the evidence of a significant change in the export and import in the India before and after the new economic reforms in the periods (1991-2020). After the new economic policy 1991 in India the Government of India introduced series of economic reforms to liberalize and globalize Indian economy. Since the initiation of economic reforms, India's outward orientation has started increasing. The Indian trade policy experienced various changes time to time after its initiation and the major changes included simplification of procedures, removal of quantitative restrictions and substantial reduction in the tariff rates. The policy regime in India with regard to liberalization of the external sector has brought tremendous changes in Indians foreign trade. Thus, it is in this connection that the present study aims to analyses the trend, composition and detraction of the foreign trade in India since 1991.

Objectives:-

The main objective of the study is to analysis of India's export and import performance in India during the period 1991 to 2021.

- To examine and compare the growth trends of India's exports during pre and post reform periods.
- To analyses and compare the changing trends of India's imports during pre and post reform periods .
- To study the magnitude of changes in share of exports and imports to gross domestic product (GDP) of India.
- To examine the trade balance of India during pre and post reform periods.
- To observe the trend of foreign trade of India before and during the pandemic

Data & Methodology:-

The study is based on data collected from secondary sources like internet website, Hand book of Statistics on Indian Economy published by the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), Ministry of Commerce and Industry and Directorate General of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics. To examine the trend and composition of foreign trade exports and imports in India after New Economic reform of 1991. Simple statistical tools like growth rate, percentage share calculations and simple diagrams have been used. The growth rates of exports ($\Delta X / X$), Import ($\Delta I / I$) and GDP ($\Delta Y / Y$) are obtained by using the following formula:

$$Gr_t = \frac{Y_t - Y_{t-1}}{Y_{t-1}} \times 100$$

Where, Gr_t is the growth rate of variable Y for t^{th} time period compared to its previous year and it is represented as percentages.

To examine the role of foreign trade in economic growth of India, linear regression model has been used where Gross Domestic Product (GDP) at factor cost at constant price is taken as a measure of economic growth; and volume of export, import and economic openness in monetary terms are taken as variables of the study. Before applying Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method, the stationary of the concerned variables are tested using Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Test.

The following model is applied here examine the impact of trade on economic growth

$$Y_t = \alpha + \beta_1 X_t + \beta_2 M_t + \beta_3 O_t + u_t , \quad t = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

Where, α and β are the co-efficient

u_t is the error term which follows normal distribution with mean zero and variance σ^2 .

Y_t is the Gross Domestic Product in period t, X_t is the export in time t. Krueger (1997) finds a strong association between export and economic growth. M_t is the import in time t. Ahmed et.al (2013) finds a negative impact of imports on GDP. Li et. al (2003) from their study suggest that imports of services have a significant positive impact on economic growth in developed countries and a negative impact in developing countries. O_t is the economic openness in time t. The openness variable is measured as exports plus imports divided by GDP [$O = (X + M)/GDP$]. It is expected to have a positive effect on growth as drawn from various works that have been reviewed (Grossman and Helpman, 1992, Chen and Gupta, 2006).

Data analysis:-

In the analysis is based on data collected from secondary sources wick collected form internet website, Hand book of Statistics on Indian Economy published by the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) , Ministry of Commerce and Industry and Directorate General of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics. We take the data in 1991 to 2020 .we take the 1st table export, import and trade balance in the period 1991 to 2020.

Table 1 below given the current trends of India export , import, balance of trade movement of exchange rates. It can be observed that import and export increased steadily and reveals that import improved more rapidly than export.

Below the table present the information on the value of foreign trade in India over the period of post reform (1991-2021) in term of US million dollars. As is clear from this table the value of India's export and import increased considerably over the period of post reform. From \$18145.2 million in 1991 export rose to \$313138.5 million in2019-20. Import during this period rose from \$24072.5million in 1991 to \$473995.2 million in 2019-20. It can be noted that the country (India) has faced substantial trade deficit during the period of post reforms period. in the study of foreign trade data show that the trade balance was deficit (negative) after the new economic reforms . it is the fact that the trade deficit has increased significantly over the period(1991-2020).

The year 1990-91 show the trade deficit was \$-5927.3 millions import rose by 13.5% against a raise of 9.2% registered export. However, strict import restrictions was imposed in 1991-92 which lead to -19.4% reduction in the value of import and Trade deficit declaimed to \$-1545.1 million so export was \$17865.4 million and import was\$19410.5 million. In the year 1992-93 the trade deficit was \$-3344.4 million, export and import rose by 3.8% and 12.7%. The next 2 years (1994-1996)

INDIA'S FOREIGN TRADE - US DOLLAR(\$)											
											(US \$ million)
Year	Exports			Imports			Trade Balance			Rate of changes	
	Oil	Non-Oil	Total	Oil	Non-Oil	Total	Oil	Non-Oil	Total	Export	Import
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1990-91	522.7	17622.5	18145.2	6028.1	18044.4	24072.5	-5505.4	-421.9	-5927.3	9.2	13.5
1991-92	414.7	17450.7	17865.4	5324.8	14085.7	19410.5	-4910.1	3365.0	-1545.1	-1.5	-19.4
1992-93	476.2	18061.0	18537.2	6100.0	15781.6	21881.6	-5623.8	2279.4	-3344.4	3.8	12.7
1993-94	397.8	21840.5	22238.3	5753.5	17552.7	23306.2	-5355.7	4287.8	-1067.9	20.0	6.5
1994-95	416.9	25913.6	26330.5	5927.8	22726.5	28654.4	-5510.9	3187.1	-2323.8	18.4	22.9
1995-96	453.7	31341.2	31794.9	7525.8	29149.5	36675.3	-7072.0	2191.7	-4880.4	20.8	28
1996-97	481.8	32987.9	33469.7	10036.2	29096.2	39132.4	-9554.4	3891.7	-5662.7	5.3	6.7
1997-98	352.8	34653.7	35006.4	8164.0	33320.5	41484.5	-7811.2	1333.1	-6478.1	4.6	6.0
1998-99	89.4	33129.3	33218.7	6398.6	35990.1	42388.7	-6309.2	-2860.8	-9170.0	-5.1	2.2
1999-2000	38.9	36783.5	36822.4	12611.4	37059.3	49670.7	-12572.5	-275.8	-12848.3	10.5	17.3
2000-01	1869.7	42690.6	44560.3	15650.1	34886.4	50536.5	-13780.4	7804.2	-5976.2	20	0.5
2001-02	2119.1	41707.6	43826.7	14000.3	37413.0	51413.3	-11881.2	4294.6	-7586.6	-0.6	2.9
2002-03	2576.5	50142.9	52719.4	17639.5	43772.6	61412.1	-15063.0	6370.3	-8692.7	20.3	19.4
2003-04	3568.4	60274.1	63842.6	20569.5	57579.6	78149.1	-17001.1	2694.5	-14306.5	21.1	27.3
2004-05	6989.3	76546.6	83535.9	29844.1	81673.3	111517.4	-22854.8	-5126.7	-27981.5	30.8	42.7
2005-06	11639.6	91450.9	103090.5	43963.1	105202.6	149165.7	-32323.5	-13751.7	-46075.2	23.4	33.8
2006-07	18634.6	107779.5	126414.1	56945.3	128790.0	185735.2	-38310.7	-21010.5	-59321.2	22.6	24.5
2007-08	28363.1	134541.1	162904.2	79644.5	171794.7	251439.2	-51281.4	-37253.6	-88535.0	29	35.5
2008-09	27547.0	157748.0	185295.0	93671.7	210024.6	303696.3	-66124.8	-52276.6	-118401.3	13.6	20.7
2009-10	28192.0	150559.5	178751.4	87135.9	201237.0	288372.9	-58943.9	-50677.5	-109621.4	-3.5	-5
2010-11	41480.0	209656.2	251136.2	105964.4	263804.7	369769.1	-64484.4	-54148.5	-118632.9	40.5	28.2
2011-12	56038.5	249925.3	305963.9	154967.6	334352.0	489319.5	-98929.0	-84426.6	-183355.7	21.8	32.3
2012-13	60865.1	239535.5	300400.6	164040.6	326696.1	490736.6	-103175.4	-87160.6	-190336.1	-1.8	0.3
2013-14	63179.4	251236.4	314415.7	164770.3	285443.3	450213.6	-101591.0	-34206.9	-135797.9	4.7	-8.3
2014-15	56794.1	253557.9	310352.0	138325.5	309707.9	448033.4	-81531.4	-56150.0	-137681.4	-1.3	-0.5
2015-16	30582.6	231708.4	262291.1	82944.5	298063.3	381007.8	-52361.8	-66354.8	-118716.7	-15.5	-15
2016-17	31545.3	244307.2	275852.4	86963.8	297393.2	384357.0	-55418.6	-53086.0	-108504.6	5.2	0.9
2017-18	37465.1	266061.1	303526.2	108658.7	356922.3	465581.0	-71193.6	-90861.2	-162054.8	10	21.1
2018-19	46553.6	283524.5	330078.1	140920.6	373157.8	514078.4	-94367.1	-89633.3	-184000.3	8.7	10.4
2019-20	41163.8	271974.7	313138.5	130531.9	343463.3	473995.2	-89368.2	-71488.5	-160856.7	-5.1	-7.7
2020-21(Apr-Nov)(P)	--	--	174116	--	--	218874	--	--	-44758	-17.5	-32.6

Source: - Directorate General of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics & Ministry of Commerce and Industry.

The trade deficit increased , in the year 1995-96 the trade deficit was \$-4880.4 million, total export was \$31794.9 million and total import was\$36675.3 million, the rate of exchange export was18.4% and import was 22.9% . In the year 2000-01 increased the deficit of trade balance was \$-5976.2 million the total export was\$44560.3 million and import was \$50536.5 million the rate of exchange export and import was 20% and 0.5%. in the year of 2004-05 the rate of growth of export was consistently above 20% per annum with the rate of growth touching 30.8% in the year 2004-05 , total export and

import was \$83535.9 million and \$111517.4 million trade balance deficit increased \$-27981.5 million . In 2005-06, the rate of growth export was 23.4% and import was 33.8% and the trade balance deficit was \$-46075.2 million. In the year 2006-07 the growth rate of export was 22.6% the value of export more than double in the year 2002-03. In 2002-03 it was \$52719 million in 2006-07 it was \$126414.1 million. Both external and domestic factor contributed to this satisfactory performance. In 2007-8 the trade deficit was \$-88535 million the growth of export and import was 29% and 35.5% total export and import was \$162904.2 million and \$251439.2 million. in 2008-09 the deficit of trade balance was \$-118401.3 million the rate of exchange export and import was 13.6% and 20.7%, total export and import was \$185295 million & \$33696.3 million . In 2009-10 the trade balance was declined \$-109621.4 million, the growth of trade was declined -3.5% in export and -5% in import, the total export and import was \$178751.4 million and \$288372.9 million. the export was increased \$251136.2 million in 2010-11 to \$305963 .9 million in 2011-12 and import was \$369769.1 million in 2010-11 to \$48319.5 million in 2011-12, the growth of import increased from 28.2% in 2010-11 to 32.3% in 2011-12 & the growth of export reduced from 40.5% in 2010-11 to 21.8% in 2011-12 the trade balance deficit was \$-118632.9 million in 2010-11 & \$183355.7 million in 2011-12. in 2012-13 total export and total import was \$300400.6 million & \$490736.6 million , deficit trade balance was \$-190336.1 million , the growth of export & import was -1.8% & 0.3% . In 2013.14 the trade deficit declined to \$-135797.9 million. This was basically due to a modest recovery of export & a sharp fall in import, total export and Import in the year was \$ 314415.7 million and \$450213.6 million. In 2014-15 the trade deficit was marginally high \$-137681.4 million the trade deficit to be continued due to the lower level of import total export and total import was \$310352 million & \$448033.4 million. Trade deficit in 2015-16 was \$-118716.7 million, the growth of export and import was -15.5% & -15%, total export & import was \$262291.1 million & \$381007.8 million. After the two years of negative growth , export recorded as a positive growth of 5.2% in 2016-17 , this was due to substantial pick-up export in the second half of 2016-17, in this year total export & import was \$275852.4 million & \$385347 million , trade balance was \$-118716.7 million. Massive increases in import expenditure by as much as 21% in 2017-18 as against as increases on export earnings of 10%, trade deficit rose to high \$-162054.8 million. This rose further to \$-184000.3 million in 2018-19. Total export & import in 2017-18 was \$303526.2 million & \$465581 million, the growth of export & import was 10% & 21.1%. In 2018-19 total export was \$330078.1 million & import was \$514078.4 million, the growth of export & import was 8.8% & 10.4% in 2018-19. In 2019-20 total export was \$313138.5 million & import was \$473995.2 million, whereas the rate of change in export import was -5.1% & -7.7%, total trade balance deficit was \$-160856.7 million . in 2020-2(Apr-Nov) total export was \$174116 million & import was \$218874 million, whereas rate of changes export & import was -17.5% & -32.6% , total trade balance deficit was \$-44758 million.

It based on the following fig.:-

In the above fig. show that the foreign trade in India since 1991- 2020, in the fig show that the increases the export and import over the period but trade balance was deficit in the period 1991-2020.

By the composition of foreign trade of any country, we imply the composition of export & import .composition of foreign trade is an important indicator to know the country are developed or under-developed country, i.e. if we find a country import the food grains and raw materials but export finished goods, machinery, capital equipment, we can safely conclude that it has reached high level of economic development. On the other hand , if it export primary commodity like jute ,tee ,raw cotton ,sugar , etc., but import the capital equipment & machinery , finished goods , etc., we can conclude that the country are under-developed country . The speed with which such a country changes its pattern of trade (leading to

Percentage decline in import of manufacturing product & parentage increased exports of such product) is sometimes taken by some economists as an indication of the pace of development in the country .Table -2 represents the composition of export in India

Before the advent of planning in India, main exports were primary goods like jute, tea, cotton, hides & skins, manganese ore, mica, etc., while manufactured product constituted the bulk imports. During the planning period process of the industrialization and economic development has induced a number of changes in the composition of the foreign trade, as would be clear from the discussion below

Composition of Exports

The following tables depict the export of major commodities from India since 1991 to 2013 in terms of US \$ However, post 2013; the principal commodities exported were classified by the names of 30 specific goods. These included major commodities such as tea, coffee, rice, fruits and vegetables, meat and dairy products, ceramic products, gems and jewellery, petroleum products etc. The data for this is given below from the year 2013-14 to 2019-20 .

Composition of export presented in the above table. A clear trend over the years has been decline in the importance of primary product (agricultural & allied product) & substantial increases the importance of manufactured product for instance the share of primary products was &4324 million in 1990-91, it was decline \$3873.5 million in 1992-93, in 1993-94 it started to increased due to less industrialization more than 70% people were depend on agriculture, in 1999-2000 it was \$6524.2 million it increased \$13553.3 million in 2004-05 , in 2005-06 it was \$16377.4 million it was increased \$25335.4 million in2008-09,in 2012-13 it was \$46200 million . The primary product derived in two part (a) agriculture & allied product (b) Ores & minerals

Agriculture & allied product export in 1990-91 was \$3354.4 million ,it was decline \$3135.8 million in 1992-93 again it increases rapidly, in 1993-94 it was \$4027.5 million, in 1999-2000 it was \$5608 million , again it increase \$5901.2 million in 2001-02, in 2004-05 it was \$8474.7 million. In 2006-07 it was \$12683.5 million ,it was increased \$37473.3 million in 2011-12 & \$40641.5 million in 2012-13

Composition of Exports- US \$								
								(US \$ million)
Commodity/Year	1990-91	1991-92	1992-93	1993-94	1999-00	2000-01	2001-02	2004-05
I. Primary products	4324	4132.2	3873.5	4915.7	6524.2	7126.2	7163.6	13553.3
A. Agriculture and allied products	3354.4	3202.5	3135.8	4027.5	5608	5973.2	5901.2	8474.7
1. Tea	596.4	491.5	337.2	337.7	411.9	391.5	360.5	409.6
2. Coffee	140.6	134.7	129.9	173.9	331.1	259.4	229.6	237.9
3. Rice	257.2	306.5	336.8	410.2	721.4	641.8	665.6	1506.5
4. Wheat	17.3	51.5	3.5	0.1	0	90.9	278.9	324.9
5. Cotton raw including waste	471.4	123.7	62.8	208.4	17.8	48.4	9	94
6. Tobacco	146.8	152.9	163.7	147	232.8	189.8	169.4	279.2
7. cashew nut	249.1	274	258.5	334.2	567.9	449.5	376.2	554
8. Spices	130.4	151	135.8	181.4	407.9	354.1	313.9	419.1
9. Oil meals	339.1	373.8	533.5	740.9	378	447.6	474.5	707.2
10. Fruits and vegetables	118.9	141.6	107.9	132.1	148.4	184.6	221.1	398.7
11. Processed fruits, juices items	118.5	77.3	78.8	90.6	196.9	288.4	259.3	284.3
12. Marine products	535	585.2	601.9	813.6	1182.6	1393.8	1236.8	1439.8
13. Sugar and molasses	20.9	63.8	122.1	56.8	9.3	110.6	373.6	34.5
14. Meat and meat preparations	77.9	93.6	88.8	109.8	189.1	321.7	250.2	424
15. Others	134.7	181.4	174.6	290.8	813.1	801.2	682.8	1360.9
B. Ores and minerals	969.6	929.7	737.8	888.2	916.1	1153	1262.4	5078.6
1. Iron ore	584.7	582.3	381.2	438	271.2	357.6	426.4	3277.3
2. Mica	19.4	14.3	8.3	8.8	9.8	9.1	11.7	14.1
3. Others	365.5	333.2	348.3	441.4	635.1	786.3	824.3	1787.1
II. Manufactured goods	12996.4	13148.4	14038.8	16656.7	29714.4	34335.2	33369.7	60730.7
A. Leather and manufactures	1449.2	1268.8	1277.5	1299.5	1590.2	1944.4	1910.1	2421.6
B. Chemicals and related products	1728	1868.8	1786.1	2377.2	4706.5	5885.9	6051.8	12443.7
1. Basic chemicals& cosmetics	1235.1	1400.7	1148	1373.1	3088.2	3664	3697	7139.1
2. Plastic and linoleum products	111.2	112.1	149.4	335.9	603.8	915.2	987.4	3032.8
3. Rubber, glass, paints, enamels and products	310	277.4	408.1	563.8	693.7	936.5	984.5	1759.5
4. Residual chemicals and allied products	71.7	78.6	80.7	104.4	320.9	370.1	382.9	512.3
C. Engineering goods	2250.4	2253.1	2480.8	3038.1	5152.1	6818.6	6957.8	17348.3
1. Iron & steel	161.1	153.5	306.1	568.4	833	1028.3	898.1	3921
2. Manufacture of metals	456.3	484.2	560.2	663.2	1225.6	1577.7	1604	3401.5
3. Machinery and instruments	696.2	581.4	541.6	638.9	1183.2	1580.1	1734.1	3719.4
4. Transport equipment	400.6	496.4	533.7	591.9	810.2	991.9	1020.9	2829.7
5. Electronic goods	232.4	265.2	212.3	303.6	681	1051.5	1171.3	1831.8
6. Others	303.8	272.3	326.9	272.2	419.1	589.1	529.4	1644.9
D. Textile and textile products	4342.6	4693.1	5007.4	5472.3	9822.1	11285	10206.5	13555.3
1. Cotton yarn, fabrics, madeups, etc.	1170.3	1299.3	1350.5	1537.1	3089.6	3460.7	3072.9	3450.1
2. Natural silk yarn, fabrics, madeups, etc., incl. silk waste	131	142	138.6	127.2	245.4	316.6	285.9	405
3. Man made yarn, fabrics, madeups, etc.	226.7	333.2	372.6	425.7	811.4	1058.5	1065	1962.7
4. Manmade staple fibre	.	.	21.5	12.2	43.7	36.6	23.5	88
5. Woolen yarn, fabrics, madeups, etc.	11.8	30	39.2	50.2	50	62.4	52.2	69.8
6. Readymade garments	2236.1	2199.2	2393	2586.2	4765.1	5568.9	5006.6	6561.4
7. Jute & jute manufactures	166.3	158.5	122.6	124	125.7	151.2	128.3	276.3
8. Coir & coir manufactures	26.8	28.5	31.2	41.4	46.1	48.3	61.8	105.6
9. Carpets	373.7	502.4	538.2	568.2	645.1	581.7	510.2	636.4
(a) Carpet handmade	289.3	407.4	434.8	453.7	498.6	446.9	374.8	608.1
(b) Carpet millmade	84.4	95	85.5	100.3	112.9	110.5	99.3	0
(c) Silk carpets	.	0	17.9	14.2	33.6	24.3	36.1	28.4
E. Gems and jewellery	2924.1	2738.2	3071.7	3995.8	7502.3	7384	7306.3	13761.8
F. Handicrafts (excluding handmade carpets)	223.9	241.5	275.9	318.5	668.6	661.5	549	377.4
G. Other manufactured goods	78.2	84.9	139.3	155.3	272.6	355.8	388.3	822.6
III. Petroleum products	522.7	414.7	476.2	397.8	38.9	1869.7	2119.1	6989.3
IV. Others	302.2	170.1	148.6	268	544.9	1229.2	1174.3	2262.6
Total exports	18145.2	17865.4	18537.2	22238.3	36822.4	44560.3	43826.7	83535.9

Composition of Exports - US \$								
								(US \$ million)
Commodity/Year	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13
I. Primary products	16377.4	19686	27523.4	25335.4	26396.5	32844.2	45923.6	46200
A. Agriculture and allied products	10213.8	12683.5	18403.6	17534.9	17734.1	24207.6	37473.3	40641.5
1. Tea	390.9	435.3	505.3	584.6	620.4	736.2	851.1	859.6
2. Coffee	358.8	435.1	465	490.5	428.3	660.6	946.2	866.1
3. Rice	1405.2	1554.9	2918.7	2427.4	2372.3	2542.9	5030.7	6213.6
4. Wheat	125.9	7.8	0.1	0.3	0	0.2	213.5	1927.7
5. Cotton raw including waste	656	1349.8	2202	623.1	2010.2	2888.4	4512.3	3641.4
6. Tobacco	300.6	372.4	479.8	752.5	915.7	874.7	836	925.6
7. cashew nut	585.8	553.9	555.1	637.2	596.3	626.2	928.6	753
8. Spices	477.9	697.9	1044.3	1378.1	1297.8	1765.4	2758.6	2815.5
9. Oil meals	1101.1	1216.4	2022	2232.8	1650.8	2429.5	2461.6	2907.9
10. Fruits and vegetables	481.9	681.1	761.6	982.6	1128.9	1076.5	1200.4	1238.1
11. Processed fruits, juices items	359	405.8	530.5	690.7	686	805.4	1145.3	1273.5
12. Marine products	1589.2	1768.2	1720.5	1536.4	2086.7	2615.6	3460.7	3461.3
13. Sugar and mollasses	135	720.6	1406.5	985.2	27.4	1236.4	1872	1617.7
14. Meat and meat preparations	621.2	732.4	931.3	1167.9	1325	1966.5	2944.5	3290.3
15. Others	1625.3	1751.6	2861	3045.7	2588.2	3983.1	8311.8	8850.4
B. Ores and minerals	6163.6	7002.5	9119.8	7800.5	8662.5	8636.6	8450.3	5558.5
1. Iron ore	3801.1	3902	5812	4723.6	5978.9	4700.3	4629.1	1600.3
2. Mica	17.4	16.8	21.8	29.6	27.8	41.5	49.6	50.6
3. Others	2345.1	3083.7	3286	3047.3	2655.7	3894.8	3771.6	3907.7
II. Manufactured goods	72562.8	84920.6	102944	123149	115181	157994	185423	183719
A. Leather and manufactures	2697.7	3016.7	3502.5	3556	3361.1	3910.6	4793.6	4870.2
B. Chemicals and related products	14769.5	17335.5	21176.7	22708.1	22908.8	28871	37104.6	39929.7
1. Basic chemicals& cosmetics	9127.1	10958.9	13935.3	15628.4	15767.5	19305	24528.5	27043.4
2. Plastic and linoleum products	2819.3	3252.6	3418.6	3004.2	3354.1	4674.2	6241.5	6311.1
3. Rubber, glass, paints, enamels and products	2105.2	2372.8	2886.3	2992.2	2752.5	3595.9	4727.9	5075
4. Residual chemicals and allied products	717.9	751.2	936.5	1083.4	1034.7	1296	1606.7	1500.2
C. Engineering goods	21718.8	29567.2	37352.8	47285.6	38271.3	58137.9	67832.2	65288.6
1. Iron & steel	3548.3	5238.6	5446.5	5822.7	3622.2	5113.3	6587.9	6225.9
2. Manufacture of metals	4233.2	5081.2	7051.3	7548.2	5523	8456	9581.9	10034.3
3. Machinery and instruments	5077.5	6722.8	9128	10945.5	9539	11839	14310.8	15215.6
4. Transport equipment	4323	4949.9	7024.3	11153.3	9824.3	16048.5	21140.5	18409.3
5. Electronic goods	2173.1	2854	3349.3	6805.6	5458.2	8203.7	8851.5	8065.2
6. Others	2363.7	4720.6	5353.4	5010.2	4304.5	8477.4	7359.7	7338.3
D. Textile and textile products	16402.1	17373.2	19420.1	20016.4	19853	24225	28026.6	27343
1. Cotton yarn, fabrics, madeups, etc.	3944.8	4218.7	4649.8	4115.7	3684.2	5785.6	6805.1	7516.6
2. Natural silk yarn, fabrics, madeups, etc., incl. silk waste	432.6	441.9	385.8	363.1	302.7	374.2	208.5	167.7
3. Man made yarn, fabrics, madeups, etc.	1957.8	2204.4	2896.9	3026.3	3602.7	4277.7	5069.5	4535.2
4. Manmade staple fibre	81.8	196.4	278.6	254.8	356.4	421.4	574.4	507.2
5. Woolen yarn, fabrics, madeups, etc.	85.3	85.2	92.8	99.3	89.6	110	151.3	121.1
6. Readymade garments	8617.7	8892.3	9687.1	10935	10705.6	11601.8	13691.2	12925.6
7. Jute & jute manufactures	296.3	260.4	326.1	299.1	217.8	459.2	464.5	387.2
8. Coir & coir manufactures	133.3	145.9	160.2	148	160.1	159.5	212.5	197
9. Carpets	852.6	928	942.7	775.1	734	1035.6	849.6	985.4
(a) Carpet handmade	829.2	898.7	924.8	762.4	725.4	1033	845.4	981.6
(b) Carpet millmade	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
(c) Silk carpets	23.3	29.3	17.9	12.8	8.6	2.6	4.2	3.8
E. Gems and jewellery	15529.1	15977	19678.7	27955.2	28996.3	40476.1	44840.5	43457.4
F. Handicrafts (excluding handmade carpets)	462	438	508.2	301	224.8	256.9	277.9	200.2
G. Other manufactured goods	983.7	1213	1304.5	1326.7	1565.5	2116.9	2547.2	2629.7
III. Petroleum products	11639.6	18678.7	28363.1	27547	28192	41480	56038.5	60290.7
IV. Others	2510.7	3128.8	4302.1	9263.7	8982.2	18817.7	18579.1	10361
Total exports	103091	126414	163132	185295	178751	251136	305964	300571

Composition of Exports - US \$

(US \$ Million)

Commodity / Year	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20
1. Tea	798.8	681.8	720.0	731.3	837.4	830.9	826.5
2. Coffee	798.8	814.0	783.9	842.8	968.6	822.3	738.9
3. Rice	7790.1	7853.1	5846.6	5733.8	7806.2	7750.6	6396.6
4. Other cereals	1204.2	869.1	261.2	212.3	248.6	349.0	204.4
5. Tobacco	1011.4	958.6	982.0	958.7	934.3	981.3	905.0
6. Spices	2497.3	2430.3	2541.5	2851.9	3115.4	3322.4	3622.6
7. Cashew nut	842.3	909.3	768.6	786.9	922.4	654.4	566.8
8. Oil Meals	2796.4	1324.2	553.0	805.4	1093.2	1508.6	827.5
9. Oil seeds	1291.7	1735.4	1246.9	1355.2	1174.3	1156.8	1318.1
10. Fruits & Vegetables	2255.3	2153.5	2268.8	2454.7	2513.3	2540.9	2373.6
11. Cereal preparations & miscellaneous processed items	1149.5	1257.7	1319.8	1270.8	1416.6	1555.4	1536.4
12. Marine Products	5016.6	5510.5	4767.5	5903.1	7389.2	6802.6	6722.0
13. Meat, dairy & poultry products	5292.9	5385.0	4575.5	4368.8	4610.1	4363.7	3714.1
14. Iron Ore	1552.4	515.3	191.5	1533.5	1471.1	1317.3	2625.0
15. Mica, Coal & Other Ores, Minerals including processed minerals	4022.5	3903.5	3656.0	3578.2	3776.9	4254.7	3941.8
16. Leather & leather products	5572.8	6030.5	5407.8	5165.6	5289.1	5140.8	4645.3
17. Ceramic products & glassware	1292.2	1644.4	1712.1	1856.6	2131.8	2649.2	2869.9
18. Gems & Jewellery	41388.3	41266.1	39284.3	43412.8	41544.4	40251.0	35891.7
19. Drugs & Pharmaceuticals	14949.5	15431.5	16909.5	16785.0	17282.8	19146.6	20702.7
20. Organic & Inorganic Chemicals	12286.0	12473.6	11731.3	12336.1	15949.5	19222.7	18723.6
21. Engineering Goods	63902.7	73074.8	61949.5	67216.1	78695.7	83621.6	78688.4
22. Electronic Goods	7843.0	6260.8	5959.5	5962.9	6393.1	8829.4	11700.9
23. Cotton Yarn/Fabs./made-ups, Handloom Products etc.	11015.9	10774.6	10119.4	9862.2	10260.4	11215.1	10026.0
24. Man-made Yarn/Fabs./made-ups etc.	5183.7	5275.0	4621.7	4557.1	4826.3	4980.5	4821.0
25. RMG of all Textiles	14990.5	16833.3	16964.4	17368.2	16706.9	16138.3	15487.7
26. Jute Mfg. including Floor Covering	351.6	297.0	295.4	309.9	335.1	324.9	342.6
27. Carpet	1178.3	1360.8	1440.1	1490.2	1429.8	1481.9	1373.3
28. Handicrafts excl. hand made carpet	1499.3	1378.0	1648.0	1926.7	1823.3	1838.1	1786.5
29. Petroleum Products	63179.4	56794.1	30582.6	31545.3	37465.1	46553.6	41163.8
30. Plastic & Linoleum	6147.0	5746.0	5764.2	5796.5	6851.1	8607.5	7551.1
31. Other Commodities	25315.3	19410.2	17418.8	16873.7	18264.2	21865.7	21044.9
Total Exports	314415.7	310352.0	262291.1	275852.4	303526.2	330078.1	313138.5

Sources: - Directorate General of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics & Ministry of Commerce and Industry.

The composition of export Tea in 1990-91 was \$596.4 million, it was decline \$337.7 million in 1993-94, in 1999-2000 it was \$411.9 million. in 2004-05 it was \$409.6 million, in 2007-08 it was \$505.3 million , in 2010-11 it was \$736.2 million , in 2012-13 it was \$851.1 million , in 2013-14 it was \$798.8 million , it was rapidly increases in 2018-19 it was \$830.9 million ,in 2019-20 it was \$826.5 million.

In the composition of Coffee in 1990-91 was \$140.6 million , it was increased \$331.1 million in 1999-2000 , in 2004-05 it was \$237.9 million again it increases \$490.5 million in 2008-09, in 2010-11 it was \$660.6 million, in 2011-12 it was \$946.2 million , in 2014-15 it was \$814.0 million, in 2017-18 it was \$968.6 million , in 2018-19 it was \$822.3 million , in 2019-20 it was 738.9 million.

The composition of export Rice in 1990-91 was \$257.2 million it increases \$721.4 million 1999-2000 , in 2004-05 it was \$1506.5 million , in 2005-06 it was \$1405.2 million it increases \$2918.7 million in 2007-08, in 2011-12 it was \$5030.7 million , in 2012-13 it was \$6213.6 million. In 2013-14 it was \$7790.1 million, in 2016-17 it decreases \$ 5733.8 million again it increases \$7806.2 million in 2017-18 , in 2018-19 it was \$7750.6 million , in 2019-20 \$6396.6 million.

The composition on export wheat in 1990-91 was \$17.3 million, in 2001-02 it was \$278.9 million, in 2012-13 it was \$1927.7 million.

The composition on export Tobacco in the year 1990-91 was \$146.8 million it increases \$232.8 million in 1999-2000, in 2004-05 it was \$279.2 million , in 2008-09 it was \$752.5 million , in 2012-13 it was \$925.6 million , in 2018-19 it was \$981.3 million , in 2019-20 it was \$905.0 million.

Composition on export Cashew nut in the year 1990-91 was \$249.1 million it increases over the period of time \$567.9 million in 1999-2000,in 2004-05 it was \$554 million , in 2008-09 it was \$637.2 million, in 2012-13 it was \$753 million, in 2018-19 it was \$654.4 million & in 2019-20 it was \$566.8 million.

Composition on export Spices in the year 1990-91 was \$130.4 million, it increases over the period of time \$407.9 million in 1999-2000,in 2004-05 it was \$419.1 million , in 2008-09 it was \$ 1378.1 million, in 2012-13 it was \$ 2815.5 million, in 2018-19 it was \$ 3322.4 million & in 2019-20 it was \$3622.6 million.

Composition on export Marine product in the year 1990-91 was \$535 million it increases over the period of time \$1182.6 million in 1999-2000,in 2004-05 it was \$1439.8 million , in 2008-09 it was \$1536.4 million, in 2012-13 it was \$ 3461.3 million, in 2017-18 it was \$7389.2 million & in 2019-20 it was \$6722.0 million.

Composition on export Ores and Minerals in the year 1990-91 was \$969.6 million it increases over the period of time \$1153 million in 2000-01 ,in 2004-05 it was \$ 5078.6 million , in 2008-09 it was \$7800.5 million, in 2012-13 it was \$5558.5 million, in 2018-19 it was \$5572.0 million & in 2019-20 it was \$ 6566.8million.

Composition on export Iron ore in the year 1990-91 was \$584.7 million it increases over the period of time \$438million in 1993-94 ,in 2004-05 it was \$3277.3 million , in 2008-09 it was \$4723.6 million, in 2012-13 it was decreases \$ 1600.3million, in 2018-19 it was \$1317.3 million & in 2019-20 it was \$2625.0 million.

Composition on export Mica in the year 1990-91 was \$19.4 million it decreases over the period of time \$808 million in 1993-94 ,in 2004-05 it was \$14.1 million , in 2008-09 it was \$29.6 million, in 2012-13 it was \$50.6 million, in 2018-19 it was \$4254.7 million & in 2019-20 it was \$3941.8 million.

Composition on export Leather product in the year 1990-91 was \$1449.2 million it increases over the period of time \$1590.2 million in 1999-2000,in 2004-05 it was \$2421.6 million , in 2008-09 it was \$3556 million, in 2012-13 it was \$4870.2 million, in 2018-19 it was \$5140.8 million & in 2019-20 it was \$4645.3 million.

Composition on export Chemical and related product in the year 1990-91 was \$1728 million it increases over the period of time \$4706.5 million in 1999-2000,in 2004-05 it was \$12443.7 million , in 2008-09 it was \$22708.1 million, in 2012-13 it was \$39929.7 million, in 2018-19 it was \$41018.5 million & in 2019-20 it was \$42296.2 million.

Composition on export Engineering good in the year 1990-91 was \$2250.4 million it increases over the period of time \$5152.1 million in 1999-2000,in 2004-05 it was \$17348.3 million , in 2008-09 it was \$47285.6 million, in 2012-13 it was \$65288.6 million, in 2018-19 it was \$83621.6 million & in 2019-20 it was \$78688.4 million.

Composition on export Electronic goods in the year 1990-91 was \$232.4 million it increases over the period of time \$681 million in 1999-2000,in 2004-05 it was \$1831.8 million , in 2008-09 it was \$6805.6 million, in 2012-13 it was \$8065.2 million, in 2018-19 it was \$8829.4 million & in 2019-20 it was \$11700.9 million.

Composition on export Cotton Yarn/Fabs./made-ups produce in the year 1990-91 was \$1170.3 million, it increases over the period of time \$3089.6 million in 1999-2000,in 2004-05 it was \$3450.1 million , in 2008-09 it was \$4115.7 million, in 2012-13 it was \$7516.6 million, in 2018-19 it was \$11215.1 million & in 2019-20 it was \$10026.0 million.

Composition on export Readymade garments in the year 1990-91 was \$2236.1 million it increases over the period of time \$4765.1 million in 1999-2000, in 2004-05 it was \$6561.4 million, in 2008-09 it was \$10935.0 million, in 2012-13 it was \$12925.6 million, in 2018-19 it was \$16138.3 million & in 2019-20 it was \$15487.7 million.

Composition on export Jute & jute manufacture in the year 1990-91 was \$166.3 million, it increases over the period of time \$125.7 million in 1999-2000, in 2004-05 it was \$276.3 million, in 2007-08 it was \$326.1 million, in 2012-13 it was \$387.2 million, in 2018-19 it was \$324.9 million & in 2019-20 it was \$342.6 million.

Composition on export Gems & jeweler in the year 1990-91 was \$2924.1 million it increases over the period of time \$7502.3 million in 1999-2000, in 2004-05 it was \$13761.8 million, in 2008-09 it was \$27955.2 million, in 2012-13 it was \$43457.4 million, in 2018-19 it was \$40251.0 million & in 2019-20 it was \$35891.7 million

Composition on export Carpet in the year 1990-91 was \$373.7 million it increases over the period of time \$645.1 million in 1999-2000, in 2004-05 it was \$636.4 million, in 2007-08 it was \$942.7 million, it increases \$1035.6 million in 2010-11, in 2012-13 it was \$985.4 million, in 2018-19 it was \$1481.9 million & in 2019-20 it was \$1373.3 million.

Composition on export Handicrafts (excluding handmade carpets) in the year 1990-91 was \$223.9 million it decreases over the period of time \$668.6 million in 1999-2000, in 2004-05 it was \$377.4 million, in 2008-09 it was \$301.0 million, in 2012-13 it was \$200.2 million, in 2018-19 it was \$1838.1 million & in 2019-20 it was \$1786.5 million.

Composition on export Petroleum products in the year 1990-91 was \$522.7 million it increases over the period of time \$1869.7 million in 2000-01, in 2004-05 it was \$6989.3 million, in 2008-09 it was \$27547.0 million, in 2012-13 it was \$60290.7 million, the value was decreases in 2018-19 it was \$46553.6 million & in 2019-20 it was \$41163.8 million.

Composition on export on the other commodity in the year 1990-91 was \$302.2 million it increases over the period of time \$544.9 million in 1999-2000, in 2004-05 it was \$2262.6 million, in 2008-09 it was \$9263.7 million, in 2012-13 it was \$10361.0 million, in 2018-19 it was \$21865.7 million & in 2019-20 it was \$21044.9 million. So, the total export in 1990-91 was \$1845.2 million, in 1999-2000 it was \$36822.4 million, in 2004-05 it was \$83535.9 million, in 2008-09 it was \$185295 million, in 2012-13 it was \$300571 million, in 2015-16 it was \$262291.1 million, in 2018-19 it was \$33008.1 million & in 2019-20 it was \$313138.5 million, so after the post economic reform India increases the export.

It based on following fig:-

In this fig. show that Composition of export presented in the above. A clear trend over the years has been increases in the importance of primary product (agricultural & allied product) & substantial increases the importance of manufactured product & petroleum product.

The above chart shows the trend and distribution of the 30 major commodities and other commodities taken as a whole from the year 2013-14 to 2019-20 in terms of US Dollars.

Composition of Imports:-

In 1947-48, the main items of imports in India (in order of importance were: machinery of all kinds; oils (vegetable , mineral & animal); grains, pluses, and flour; cotton, raw & waste; vehicles , cutlery, hardware, implements & instrument; chemicals, drugs & medicines; dyes & colures; other yarns & textile fabrics; paper, paper board & stationery; & metals other than iron & steel & manufactured. These imports together constitute more than 70% of all imports.

The intention of planning process in the country in 1951-52 , & more specifically beginning the 2nd five year In 1956-57 brought about the considerable change in the composition of imports. The 2nd plan based on the Mahalanobis model introduced a program of industrialization with heavy emphasis on the development of capital goods & basic industries. As a result it necessary to import capital equipment in large quantities . After some years, spare parts, materials & machinery had to be imported in substantial quantities to keep the equipment in working order. Thus, ‘maintenance imports’ entered in to

the import structure of the country in a big way. The composition of imports since 1990-91 is given table. The following tables depict the export of major commodities from India since 1991 to 2013 in terms of US \$ However, post 2013; the principal commodities exported were classified by the names of 30 specific goods. These included major commodities such as tea, coffee, rice, fruits and vegetables, meat and dairy products, ceramic products, gems and jewellery, petroleum products etc. The data for this is given below from the year 2013-14 to 2019-20 .

For the convenience, import of the country has been divided in to (i) Bulk import (ii) Non-bulk import. Under the bulk import it divided (a) petroleum & crude oil (b) Bulk consumption good & (c) other item (paper, Non-ferrous metals, sulphur , etc..) . Under the Non-bulk item it divided in to (a) capital good (b) Mainly export related item (textile, organic chemical, semi-precious stones, etc.) & (c) other item.

The composition of the bulk import in the year 1990-91 was \$10848 million, it increases \$19646.1 million in 1999-2000, in the year 2004-05 it was \$42400.7 million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$112745 million, in 2012-13 it was \$229573 million, in the year 2018-19 it was \$246579.3 million, in 2019-20 it was \$236761.3 million.

The composition of the import of petroleum & crude product increases significantly over the year, in the year 1990-91 was \$6028.1 million, it increases \$12611.4 million in 1999-2000, in the year 2004-05 it was \$29844.1 million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$79644.5 million, in 2012-13 it was \$169319 million, in the year 2018-19 it was \$140920.6 million, in 2019-20 it was \$130531.9 million.

The composition of the import fertilizers (crude, Sulphur, manufactured product, etc.) in the year 1990-91 was \$984.3 million, it increases \$1399.1 million in 1999-2000, in the year 2004-05 it was \$1377.1 million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$5406 million, in 2012-13 it was \$9085.3 million, in the year 2018-19 it was \$7467.4 million, in 2019-20 it was \$7468.1 million.

Composition of Import's principle commodity

(US \$ million)

Commodity / Year	1990-91	1991-92	1992-93	1993-94	1999-00	2000-01	2001-02	2004-05
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
I. Bulk imports	10848	8562.8	9829.8	9112.2	19646.1	20815.7	20263.1	42400.7
A. Petroleum, crude and products	6028.1	5324.8	6100	5753.5	12611.4	15650.1	14000.3	29844.1
B. Bulk consumption goods	556.5	274.7	506.7	326.7	2416.9	1443.2	2043.2	3104.6
1. Cereals and cereal preparations	101.6	70.3	333.5	92.6	221.9	19.1	18.2	26.4
2. Edible oils	181.6	100.5	57.6	53.1	1856.8	1308.2	1355.6	2465.3
3. Pulses	268.2	103.5	115.5	180.7	81.9	109.1	662.6	395.6
4. Sugar	5.2	0.3	0	0.2	256.3	6.8	6.8	217.3
C. Other bulk items	4263.3	2963.2	3223.1	3032	4617.8	3722.4	4219.6	9452
1. Fertilisers	984.3	954.2	977.7	825.9	1399.1	751.8	679	1377.1
a) Crude	193.2	184.5	158.4	122	204.2	222.3	166.8	289.5
b) Sulphur and unroasted iron pyrite	155.1	124.4	120.9	72.2	116	89	57.4	128.1
c) Manufactured	636	645.3	698.4	631.7	1079	440.5	454.8	959.5
2. Non-ferrous metals	614.1	340.6	394.8	479.2	546.9	533.8	647.3	1310.3
3. Paper, paper boards, manufactures including news prints	254.2	197.9	177.2	221.9	447.2	451.1	446.9	727.7
4. Crude rubber, including synthetic and reclaimed	126.1	73.8	90	109	143.3	151.9	174.3	409.2
5. Pulp and waste paper	255.2	121.2	141.2	158.6	255.2	281.7	294.7	489.5
6. Metalliferrous ores, metal scrap, etc.	851.7	476.5	663.6	442.4	874.5	774.2	1143.7	2468.5
7. Iron and steel	1177.6	798.9	778.6	795	951.7	777.8	833.7	2669.7
II. Non-bulk imports	13224.6	10847.8	12051.8	14194	30024.6	29720.8	31150.2	69116.7
A. Capital goods	5835.6	4232.6	4531.6	6242.8	8965.5	8941.1	9882.2	25135
1. Manufactures of metals	168.5	130.4	145.8	178.3	405	390.3	407	918.7
2. Machine tools	263.2	172.8	166.1	154.6	261.5	219.1	193	620.4
3. Machinery except electrical and electronic	2100	1457.5	1652.6	1881.9	2745	2708.8	2970.8	6817.8
4. Electrical machinery except electronic	948.7	629.8	826.9	204.1	437.8	481	594.4	1195
Commodity/Year	1990-91	1991-92	1992-93	1993-94	1999-00	2000-01	2001-02	2004-05
5. Electronic goods	.	.	.	912.4	2796.6	3508.5	3782	9993.2
6. Computer goods	.	.	.	18	197	186	216.5	666.3
7. Transport equipment	930.5	371.2	461.8	1270.4	1136.6	700.3	1149.4	4327.4
8. Project goods	1424.7	1471	1278.5	1623.1	986	747.2	569	596.2
B. Mainly export related items	3680	3581	4148.2	4387.5	9117.3	8058.6	8260	17095.5
1. Pearls, precious and semi-precious stones	2083.1	1957.1	2442.1	2634.5	5436	4807.7	4622.6	9422.7
2. Organic and inorganic chemicals	1275.6	1378.7	1427.5	1370.7	2866.3	2443.9	2799.6	5699.9
3. Textile yarn, fabrics, made-ups, etc.	246.7	137.1	148.7	228.4	538.4	596.8	747.5	1571.2
4. Cashew nuts	74.7	108.2	129.9	153.9	276.5	210.3	90.4	401.7
C. Others	3709	3034.2	3372	3563.7	11941.8	12721.1	13008	26886.2
1. Gold and silver	.	.	.	.	4706.1	4638	4582.3	11150
a) Gold	.	.	.	.	4151.8	4121.6	4170.4	10537.7
b) Silver	.	.	.	.	554.3	516.5	411.9	612.3
2. Artificial resins and plastic materials, etc.	610	568.7	420.5	434.5	719.5	554.9	674.1	1456.9
3. Professional, scientific controlling instruments, photographic optical goods	590.6	407.2	501.4	422.3	844.5	878.8	1041.1	1530.4
4. Coal, coke and briquettes, etc.	440	420.4	477.6	466.5	1008.1	1103.1	1143.3	3198.4
5. Medicinal and pharmaceutical products	261.1	226.6	280.8	257.9	373	374.7	424.9	705.4
6. Chemical materials and products	159.4	137.2	169.5	167	360.8	334.5	444.4	819.4
7. Non-metallic mineral manufactures	113.1	88.8	89.1	86.8	163.9	173.7	219.9	471.9
8. Others	1534.9	1185.2	1433	1728.8	3765.9	4663.4	4478	7553.9
Total Imports	24072.5	19410.5	21881.6	23306.2	49670.7	50536.5	51413.3	111517

Composition of Import's principle commodity

(US \$ million)

Commodity / Year	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13
1	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
I. Bulk imports	61086.1	84434.2	112745	138791	125315	151167	214933	229573
A. Petroleum, crude and products	43963.1	57143.6	79644.5	93671.7	87135.9	105964	154968	169319
B. Bulk consumption goods	2766.6	4294.2	4600.3	4975.3	9012.7	8854.8	11654.7	14219.7
1. Cereals and cereal preparations	36.1	32.1	705.2	47	104.7	119.7	73.6	83.2
2. Edible oils	2024	2108.3	2558.6	3443.4	5582.1	6553.7	9652	11230.8
3. Pulses	559.3	860.1	1335	1358.1	2068.4	1569.2	1863.7	2341.2
4. Sugar	147.2	0.8	1.5	126.8	1257.5	612.3	65.5	564.6
C. Other bulk items	14356.5	22996.5	28499.9	40144	29166.5	36347.9	48310.7	46033.5
1. Fertilisers	2127	3144.1	5406	13626.5	6836.9	7162	11601.3	9085.3
a) Crude	317.8	361.1	467.3	1062.6	701.1	715.7	1749	1348.1
b) Sulphur and unroasted iron pyrite	136	109.3	362	651.2	143.7	241.3	476.9	319.6
c) Manufactured	1673.3	2673.6	4576.6	11912.7	5992.1	6205.1	9375.3	7417.6
2. Non-ferrous metals	1844.4	2604.9	3505.2	5699.3	3006.5	4080.2	4888.7	5123.8
3. Paper, paper boards, manufactures including news prints	944.1	1206.8	1424.8	1770.3	1504.1	2110	2567.7	2379.1
4. Crude rubber, including synthetic and reclaimed	414.1	630.8	785.7	860.8	1014.6	1772.1	2501.9	2234.3
5. Pulp and waste paper	572.9	639.3	778	805.6	880.7	1143.1	1361.5	1284.3
6. Metalliferous ores, metal scrap, etc.	3881.8	8345.8	7911.7	7906.3	7682.8	9704.6	13380.5	14982.2
7. Iron and steel	4572.2	6424.7	8688.6	9475.3	8240.9	10375.9	12009.3	10944.6
II. Non-bulk imports	88079.6	101315	138694	164905	163058	218602	274387	261915
A. Capital goods	37666.2	47069.2	70110.5	71833.1	65865	78546.1	99223.3	91449.7
1. Manufactures of metals	1211.1	1603.6	2662.7	3254.9	2402.1	3328.9	4261.6	4288.4
2. Machine tools	1076.2	1481.3	2208	2259.8	1655.7	2255.3	2986.2	2761.5
3. Machinery except electrical and electronic	10009.8	13850.4	19860.4	21601	19683.1	23846.8	30110.8	27642.8
4. Electrical machinery except electronic	1504.3	1959.8	2870.5	3685.5	3113.4	3843	4778.2	4454.2
5. Electronic goods	13241.7	15972.6	20209.9	23333.8	20955.2	26560.6	32657.4	31457.4
6. Computer goods	901.9	967	893.8	1274.6	1680.5	1129.7	1539.2	574.6
7. Transport equipment	8838.5	9438.6	20111.6	13230.3	11692.3	11437.5	14079.6	13713.3
8. Project goods	882.7	1795.9	1293.6	3193.1	4682.8	6144.4	8810.2	6557.6
B. Mainly export related items	18641	17871.7	20768.3	31930.8	31270	53608.3	51895.2	46844.9
1. Pearls, precious and semi-precious stones	9134.4	7487.5	7971.6	16581.3	16162.1	34588.9	28017.2	22619.2
2. Organic and inorganic chemicals	6984.1	7830.7	9896.6	12203	11903.2	15220.8	18841.8	19256.7
3. Textile yarn, fabrics, made-ups, etc.	2050.5	2151.2	2474.1	2565.4	2562.4	3217.1	3922.2	3989.2
4. Cashew nuts	471.9	402.4	425.9	581.1	642.4	581.5	1114	979.8
C. Others	31772.4	36374.2	47815.7	61141.4	65922.8	86447.7	123268	123620
1. Gold and silver	11317.7	14646	17867	22783	29601.7	42482.7	61401.8	55674.1
a) Gold	10830.5	14461.9	16723.6	20725.6	28640	40546.9	56319.8	53694.1
b) Silver	487.2	184.1	1143.3	2057.4	961.7	1935.8	5082	1980
2. Artificial resins and plastic materials, etc.	2267.7	2584.8	3685.2	3939.1	4990.1	6870.5	7540	8623.9
3. Professional, scientific controlling instruments, photographic optical goods	1972.7	2341	3899.6	4420.3	3616.3	4214	5247.2	5367.7
4. Coal, coke and briquettes, etc.	3868.7	4576.8	6423.7	9990.2	8960.4	9804.1	17443.9	15438.1
5. Medicinal and pharmaceutical products	1027.9	1296.5	1671.7	1886.1	2099.1	2439.3	2981.4	3118
6. Chemical materials and products	1052.5	1321.6	1625.3	2092.8	2292.1	2914.3	3462.9	3631
7. Non-metallic mineral manufactures	621.9	780	1046.6	1171.4	1080.8	1523.2	2064.5	2068.3
8. Others	9643.2	8827.5	11596.7	14858.5	13282.2	16199.8	23126.4	29698.9
Total Imports	149166	185749	251439	303696	288373	369769	489320	491487

However, the classification of imported commodities changed post 2013. It is now classified follows:

Composition of Import's principle commodity

(US \$ Million)

Commodity / Year	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20
1	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
1. Cotton Raw & Waste	392.7	508.8	394.1	946.9	979.3	633.1	1328.4
2. Vegetable Oil	9395.4	10621.5	10492.1	10892.7	11637.5	9890.3	9672.9
3. Pulses	2114.4	2786.1	3902.2	4244.1	2908.3	1140.8	1440.1
4. Fruits & vegetables	1378.9	1665.7	1853.3	1783.4	2092.6	2143.9	2221.3
5. Pulp and Waste paper	768.2	944.0	955.7	975.1	1154.6	1311.7	1143.0
6. Textile yarn Fabric, made-up articles	1505.0	1691.5	1715.1	1502.5	1837.3	1900.0	1923.2
7. Fertilisers, Crude & manufactured	6306.8	7398.7	8071.5	5024.0	5376.3	7467.4	7468.1
8. Sulphur & Unroasted Iron Pyrites	182.6	286.4	217.1	131.2	165.9	217.1	117.7
9. Metaliferrous ores & other minerals	8395.2	9299.4	7298.6	6194.2	9096.9	7583.3	5088.9
10. Coal, Coke & Briquettes, etc.	16384.8	17802.6	13667.6	15759.9	22901.2	26177.8	22455.1
11. Petroleum, Crude & products	164770.3	138325.5	82944.5	86963.8	108658.7	140920.6	130531.9
12. Wood & Wood products	5120.7	5471.0	5048.1	4891.8	6027.3	6126.5	5612.2
13. Leather & leather products	823.7	1005.1	968.1	935.3	1009.2	1057.7	1014.0
14. Organic & Inorganic Chemicals	17464.5	18593.0	16586.4	16598.4	20631.5	23827.7	20617.2
15. Dyeing/tanning/colouring mtrls.	2419.0	2447.8	2247.5	2282.7	2887.5	3221.9	2906.3
16. Artificial resins, plastic materials, etc.	10456.0	12070.3	11794.6	11964.0	14487.7	15682.0	14633.5
17. Chemical material & products	4877.9	5306.0	5151.8	5375.1	6663.4	7707.6	7643.2
18. Newsprint	891.8	839.3	805.4	849.9	776.7	977.7	700.6
19. Pearls, precious & Semi-precious stones	23849.3	22598.2	20069.9	23808.6	34278.9	27075.7	22458.8
20. Iron & Steel	12658.6	16301.3	14977.5	11683.0	14617.6	17656.7	15369.5
21. Non-ferrous metals	8856.8	10746.1	9726.1	9868.8	12811.7	14733.0	13138.7
22. Machine tools	3057.5	3137.2	2757.5	3034.6	3519.6	4642.5	4193.1
23. Machinery, electrical & non-electrical	27091.4	27979.1	29436.1	28445.8	34258.8	39758.7	39568.2
24. Transport equipment	19323.9	18345.4	18227.8	22687.7	22732.5	24775.8	24568.9
25. Project goods	4535.8	3631.4	2761.1	2074.4	2077.6	2375.6	2025.5
26. Professional instrument, Optical goods, etc.	3597.5	3714.5	3621.7	3857.2	4754.6	5187.4	5020.1
27. Electronic goods	32378.4	36857.1	40021.9	41930.4	51540.9	55471.0	52526.7
28. Medcnl. & Pharmaceutical products	5233.1	5432.8	5440.0	4995.0	5480.7	6359.5	6460.5
29. Gold	27477.3	34407.2	31770.7	27518.0	33657.2	32910.1	28229.7
30. Silver	4458.3	4523.5	3742.7	1839.2	3213.8	3748.2	2727.8
31. Other Commodities	24048.1	23297.0	24340.8	25299.2	23345.4	21397.4	21190.4
Total Imports	450213.7	448033.4	381007.8	384357.0	465581.0	514078.4	473995.2

Sources: - Directorate General of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics & Ministry of Commerce and Industry.

The composition of the import of pulse in the year 1990-91 was \$268.2 million, it decreases \$81.9million in 1999-2000, again it increases in the year 2004-05 it was \$395.6million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$1335.0 million, in 2012-13 it was \$2341.2 million, in the year 2018-19 it was \$1140.8 million, in 2019-20 it was \$1440.1 million.

The composition of the import on the Crude rubber, including synthetic & reclaimed in the year 1990-91 was \$126.1 million, it increases \$143.3 million in 1999-2000, in the year 2004-05 it was \$409.2 million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$785.7 million, in 2012-13 it was \$2234.3 million, in the year 2018-19 it was \$3221.9 million, in 2019-20 it was \$2906.3 million.

The composition of the import Paper in the year 1990-91 was \$254.2 million, it increases \$447.2 million in 1999-2000, in the year 2004-05 it was \$727.7million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$1424.8 million, in 2012-13 it was \$2379.1 million, it decreases, in the year 2018-19 it was \$977.7 million, in 2019-20 it was \$700.6 million.

The composition of the import on the pulp & waste paper in the year 1990-91 was \$255.2 million, it increases \$281.7million in 2000-01, in the year 2004-05 it was \$489.5 million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$778 million, in 2012-13 it was \$1284.3 million, in the year 2018-19 it was \$1311.7 million, in 2019-20 it was \$1143.0 million.

The composition of the import on the Metal ferrous ores & other minerals in the year 1990-91 was \$851.7 million, it increases \$874.5 million in 1999-2000, in the year 2004-05 it was \$2468.5 million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$7911.7 million, in 2012-13 it was \$14982.2 million, it decreases in the year 2018-19 it was \$ 7583.3 million, in 2019-20 it was \$5088.9 million.

The composition of the import on the Iron & steel in the year 1990-91 was \$1177.6 million, it decreases \$951.7million in 1999-2000, again it increases in the year 2004-05 it was \$2669.7million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$8688.6 million, in 2012-13 it was \$10944.6 million, in the year 2018-19 it was \$17656.7 million, in 2019-20 it was \$15369.5 million.

The composition of the import on the machine tools in the year 1990-91 was \$263.2 million, it increases \$261.4 million in 1999-2000, in the year 2004-05 it was \$620.4 million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$2208 million, in 2012-13 it was \$2761.5 million, in the year 2018-19 it was \$4642.5 million, in 2019-20 it was \$4193.1 million.

The composition of the import on the electronic good in the year 1993-94 was \$912.4 million, it increases \$2796.6 million in 1999-2000, in the year 2004-05 it was \$9993.2 million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$20209.9 million, in 2012-13 it was \$31457.4 million, in the year 2018-19 it was \$55471.0 million, in 2019-20 it was \$52526.7 million.

The composition of the import on the transport equipment in the year 1990-91 was \$930.5 million, it increases \$136.6 million in 1999-2000, in the year 2004-05 it was \$4327.4 million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$20111.6 million, in 2012-13 it was \$13713.3 million, in the year 2018-19 it was \$24775.8 million, in 2019-20 it was \$24568.9 million.

The composition of the import on the project good in the year 1990-91 was \$1424.7 million, it increases \$986 million in 1999-2000, in the year 2004-05 it was \$596.2 million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$1293.6 million, in 2012-13 it was \$6557.6 million, in the year 2018-19 it was \$2375.6 million, in 2019-20 it was \$2025.5 million.

The composition of the import on the Pearls, precious and semi-precious stones in the year 1990-91 was \$2083.1 million, it increases \$5436 million in 1999-2000, in the year 2004-05 it was \$9422.7 million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$ 7971.6 million, in 2012-13 it was \$22619.2 million, in the year 2018-19 it was \$27075.5 million, in 2019-20 it was \$22458.8 million.

The composition of the import on the Organic & Inorganic Chemicals in the year 1990-91 was \$1275.6 million, it increases \$2866.3 million in 1999-2000, in the year 2004-05 it was \$5699.9 million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$9896.6 million, in 2012-13 it was \$19256.7 million, in the year 2018-19 it was \$23827.7 million, in 2019-20 it was \$20617.2 million.

The composition of the import on the Textile yarn Fabric, made-up articles in the year 1990-91 was \$246.7 million, it increases \$538.4 million in 1999-2000, in the year 2004-05 it was \$1571.2 million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$2474.1 million, in 2012-13 it was \$3989.2 million, in the year 2018-19 it was \$1900.0 million, in 2019-20 it was \$1923.2 million.

` Due to increases the demand of Gems & jewelry increases the import on the Gold in the year 1999-2000 was \$4706.1 million, , in the year 2004-05 it was \$11150 million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$16723.6 million, in 2009-10 it was \$28640 million ,in 2012-13 it was \$53694.1 million, in the year 2018-19 it was \$32910.1 million, in 2019-20 it was \$28229.7 million.

The composition of the import on the Silver in the year 1990-91 was \$554.3 million, in the year 2004-05 it was \$612.3 million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$1143.3 million, in 2009-10 it was \$961.7 million , in 2012-13 it was \$1980 million, in the year 2018-19 it was \$3748.2 million, in 2019-20 it was \$2727.8 million.

The composition of the import on the Plastic materials in the year 1990-91 was \$610 million, it increases \$719.5 million in 1999-2000, in the year 2004-05 it was \$1456.9 million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$3685.2 million, in 2012-13 it was \$8623.9 million, in the year 2018-19 it was \$15682.0 million, in 2019-20 it was \$14633.5 million.

The composition of the import on the Coal, coke and briquettes, etc in the year 1990-91 was \$440.0 million, it increases \$1008.1 million in 1999-2000, in the year 2004-05 it was \$3198.4 million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$6423.7 million, in 2012-13 it was \$15438.1 million, in the year 2018-19 it was \$26177.8 million, in 2019-20 it was \$22455.1 million.

The composition of the import on the in the Medicine & pharmaceutical product year 1990-91 was \$261.1 million, it increases \$373 million in 1999-2000, in the year 2004-05 it was \$705.4 million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$1671.7 million, in 2012-13 it was \$3118 million, in the year 2018-19 it was \$6359.5 million, in 2019-20 it was \$6460.5 million.

The composition of the import on the Chemical materials & product in the year 1990-91 was \$159.4 million, it increases \$360.8 million in 1999-2000, in the year 2004-05 it was \$819.4 million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$1625.3 million, in 2012-13 it was \$3631 million, in the year 2018-19 it was \$7707.6 million, in 2019-20 it was \$7643.2 million.

The composition of the import on the other commodity in 1990-91 was \$1534.9 million, it increases \$3765.9 million in 1999-2000, in 2004-05 it was \$7553.9 million, in 2007-08 it was \$11596.7 million, in 2012-13 it was \$29698.9 million, in 2018-19 it was \$21397.4 million, in 2019-20 it was \$21190.4 million. So, the total import in the year 1990-91 was \$24072.5 million, it increases \$49670.7 million in the year 1999-2000, in the year 2004-05 it was \$111517.0 million, in the year 2007-08 it was \$251439 million, in the year 2010-11 it was \$369769 million, in the year 2012-13 it was \$491487.0 million, in 2015-16 it was \$381007.8 million, in 2018-19 it was \$514078.4 million, in 2019-20 it was \$473995.2 million.

It based on following fig:-

The above classification of imported goods was prominent from 1991-2013. The above graph shows a steep rise in both bulk and non-bulk imports during the period 2004-05 to 2008-09 and from the period 2009-10 to 2011-12.

The above chart shows the trend and distribution of the 30 major commodities and other commodities taken as a whole from the year 2013-14 to 2019-20 in terms of US Dollars.

India export the Coffee to the major country Belgium, Germany, Italy ,Russia ,Spain, USA etc. in the year 1998-99 total export of Coffee was \$410.7million, which \$358.8 million in 2005-06 where as total export of coffee Belgium \$19.9 million ,Germany was \$34.5 million , Italy was \$82.7 million, Russia was \$67.4 million & USA was \$5.6 million , in 2015-16 total export of coffee was \$783.9 million, it decreases \$738.9 million in 2019-20 , total export of Belgium was \$4609 million , Germany was \$78.4 million, Italy was \$127.9 million ,Russia was \$60.7 million & USA was \$31.6 million.

India export the Rice to the major country to Bangladesh, France, Saudi Arabia, South Africa, U.A.E & U.K. . in 1998-99 total export of Rice was \$1429.9 million, it increases \$1405.2 million in 2005-06,in this year total export of Rice to Bangladesh was \$124.8 million, Saudi Arabia was \$423.3 million ,U.A.E was \$90.3 million, Total export of Rice in 2020-21 was \$639 6.6 million dollar whereas, the total export of the Bangladesh watch \$14.9 million and the France was \$5.5 million dollar and South Africa was \$70.9 million and U.A.E was \$34 0.1 million and UK watch \$11 0.3 million and USA was \$212.6 million .

India export the Spices to the major country was Bangladesh, Germany, Japan Saudi Arab, Sri Lanka, UAE, UK and USA. The total export of the spices in the year 1998-99 was it \$3880 million, Bangladesh \$4.3 million and Germany was \$17.5 million in Saudi Arabia \$6.2 million dollar in Japan \$19.4 million dollar and Sri Lanka was \$5.5 Million Dollar, USA was \$12 3.2 million dollar and UK , was \$25.4 million dollar. It increases the 44519.1 Million Dollar in 2004-05 , \$21.7 million in the exported to the Japan in 21.7 million , Bangladesh and 16.9 million to Germany was 17.1 million , it was \$12.2 million Saudi Arab and \$20.7 million in UAE and \$25.7 million was UK and it was \$86.2 million in USA . in 2018-19 it was \$3322.4 million it increases \$3622.6 million in 2019-20, whereas the total export of Bangladesh was \$183.4 million ,Saudi Arabia was \$48.0 million , Sri Lanka was \$107.3 million , U.A.E was \$116.3 million & USA was \$510.8 million .

Export of selected commodity to principle country:-

India mainly export the Tee, coffee, Rice, Tobacco, Spices, Cashew nut, oil meals, marine product, iron ore, lather product, Gems & jewelers , chemical product, Engineering goods, cotton & handloom product, readymade garment, jute & jute manufacture product & carpets to the principle country . it based on the below table

India export the Tee to the major country Germany, Iran, Iraq, Kazakhstan, Poland, Russia, U.K & U.S.A. in 1998-99 total export of Tee in Germany was \$26.4 million, Russia was \$197.9 million, Iraq was \$23.4 million, U.S.A was \$19.7 million. So, total export Tee in the year 1998-99 was \$538.4 million. In 2004-05 the total export of Tee was decreases it was \$409.6 million, the total export Germany was \$2605 million, Russia was \$52.1 million, U.S.A was \$28.1 million, Iraq was \$33.1 million & Japan was \$15.6 million. In 2011-12 total export of Tee was \$851.1 million, total export of Germany was \$41.9 million, Russia was \$120.8 million , U.S.A was 68.8 million ,over the period of time India increases the export of Tee to Iran , in 2011-12 it was \$48.0 million. In 2015-16 total export of Tee was \$720 million, in this year total export of tee in Germany was \$40 million, Iran was \$105.1 million , in 2018-19 total export Tee was \$830.9 million , where as total export of Iran was \$153.7 million, Russia was \$106.4 million & USA was \$59.8 million, in 2019-20 total export of Tee was \$826.5 million , where as total export of Germany was \$37.6 million, Iran was \$198.1 million & U.S.A was \$63.0 million.

India export the Coffee to the major country Belgium, Germany, Italy ,Russia ,Spain, USA etc. in the year 1998-99 total export of Coffee was \$410.7million, which \$358.8 million in 2005-06 where as total export of coffee Belgium \$19.9 million ,Germany was \$34.5 million , Italy was \$82.7 million, Russia was \$67.4 million & USA was \$5.6 million , in 2015-16 total export of coffee was \$783.9 million, it decreases \$738.9 million in 2019-20 , total export of Belgium was \$4609 million , Germany was \$78.4 million, Italy was \$127.9 million ,Russia was \$60.7 million & USA was \$31.6 million.

India export the Rice to the major country to Bangladesh, France, Saudi Arabia, South Africa, U.A.E & U.K. . in 1998-99 total export of Rice was \$1429.9 million, it increases \$1405.2 million in 2005-06,in this year total export of Rice to Bangladesh was \$124.8 million, Saudi Arabia was \$423.3 million ,U.A.E was \$90.3 million, Total export of Rice in 2020-21 was \$639 6.6 million dollar whereas, the total export of the Bangladesh watch \$14.9 million and the France was \$5.5 million dollar and South Africa was \$70.9 million and U.A.E was \$34 0.1 million and UK watch \$11 0.3 million and USA was \$212.6 million .

India export the Spices to the major country was Bangladesh, Germany, Japan Saudi Arab, Sri Lanka, UAE, UK and USA. The total export of the spices in the year 1998-99 was it \$3880 million, Bangladesh \$4.3 million and Germany was \$17.5 million in Saudi Arabia \$6.2 million dollar in Japan \$19.4 million dollar and Sri Lanka was \$5.5 Million Dollar, USA was \$12 3.2 million dollar and UK , was \$25.4 million dollar. It increases the 44519.1 Million Dollar in 2004-05 , \$21.7 million in the exported to the Japan in 21.7 million , Bangladesh and 16.9 million to Germany was 17.1 million , it was \$12.2 million Saudi Arab and \$20.7 million in UAE and \$25.7 million was UK and it was \$86.2 million in USA . in 2018-19 it was \$3322.4 million it increases \$3622.6 million in 2019-20, whereas the total export of Bangladesh was \$183.4 million ,Saudi Arabia was \$48.0 million , Sri Lanka was \$107.3 million , U.A.E was \$116.3 million & USA was \$510.8 million .

TABLE 133 : EXPORTS OF SELECT COMMODITIES TO PRINCIPAL COUNTRIES - US \$

	US \$ MILLION										
Commodity / Country	1998-99	1999-00	2000-01	2001-02	2002-03	2003-04	2004-05	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Tea											
Germany	26.4	24.4	20.3	18.1	19.7	27.3	26.5	25.5	22.3	27.1	29.9
Iran	13	4.1	11.6	8.3	2.4	1.9	25.2	18.3	22.2	42.7	45.2
Iraq	23.4	13.1	20.4	23.6	48.2	13.4	33.1	11.1	10.7	0.5	8.2
Japan	14.1	12.6	11.2	9.4	9.6	15.2	15.6	15.7	13.7	15	16.4
Kazakhstan	17.8	12	19.9	23.7	14.4	31.7	28.7	22.3	9.1	13.5	28.4
Poland	18.2	17.5	11.1	29.6	6.7	6.1	7	5.5	6.1	8.3	8.8
Russia	197.9	161.9	104.8	84.5	59.3	56.6	52.1	53.7	61.3	71.2	78.5
U.A.E.	47.1	40.4	59.1	49.9	51.1	57	60.5	54.7	39.2	72.8	73.5
U.K.	52.6	41.5	45.9	34.2	40.1	39.4	44.2	50.2	55.1	56.9	69.6
U.S.A	19.7	20.9	23.4	22	24.7	28.1	28.1	33.4	36.2	38.1	48.8
Others	108.2	63.4	63.7	57.3	65	79.7	88.6	100.5	158.9	159.2	177.3
Total	538.4	411.9	391.5	360.5	341.4	356.3	409.6	390.9	435.3	505.3	584.6
Coffee											
Belgium	21.6	16.4	12.8	11.4	15.1	16.4	9.1	19.9	22.9	26.4	24.1
Germany	61.5	52.8	31	26.5	24.9	25.4	21.9	34.5	42.3	36.2	40.2
Italy	64.5	44.9	27.8	30.6	35.4	43	50.8	82.7	99.6	115.4	121.6
Latvia	3.3	6.4	8.4	1.2	0.9	1.4	3.2	4.5	6	6.3	3.9
Netherlands	13.8	8	6.3	4.3	3.5	4.1	6.6	4.9	6.7	6.5	5.9
Russia	59.2	56.7	63.1	66.8	46.2	46	40.5	67.4	50.9	39	44.4
Spain	18.8	19	9.4	8.6	8.1	10.8	9.9	14.7	16	17.2	17.9
Switzerland	4.4	4.8	8.8	4.4	3.7	3.2	4.5	5.6	6.4	7.6	8.3
U.K.	3.6	4.5	5.9	3.4	1.5	1.9	2.2	2.8	2.7	2.7	3.8
U.S.A	33	21.3	17.1	10.6	4.7	3.8	7.3	5.6	8.4	10.3	9.1
Others	127	96.3	68.8	61.8	61.2	80.4	82	116.2	173.1	197.4	211.3
Total	410.7	331.1	259.4	229.6	205.4	236.3	237.9	358.8	435.1	465	490.5
Rice											
Bangladesh	535	84.5	65.1	17	116.7	196.8	186.2	124.8	108.1	657.8	214.9
France	6.7	7.9	12.7	5.4	7.4	7.5	8.7	6.3	3.1	5.1	0.8
Kuwait	23.8	32.6	52.3	43.7	37.6	33.2	59.2	60	74.1	117.5	159.8
Saudi Arabia	362	293	286.6	261.1	226.9	269	421.3	423.3	316.9	608.9	675.2
Singapore	6.3	7	7.2	10.7	18.9	8.5	8.5	14.7	12.5	17	11.8
South Africa	128.5	37.1	14.7	51.1	146.5	47.5	114.8	72.2	100.9	89.1	9.1
U.A.E.	36.9	34.5	24.8	17.6	29.1	51.5	82	90.3	119.9	377.1	631.2
U.K.	40	40.1	67	41.2	43.1	48.6	63.3	51.6	50.6	80.4	94.7
U.S.A	5.1	16.8	29.6	21.7	31	23	22.4	30.8	33.1	53.4	59.7
Yemen	10.1	13.1	7.3	10.3	9.9	15.1	34.2	31.8	37.9	57.7	38.2
Others	338.6	154.8	74.5	185.8	537.7	206.5	505.8	499.3	698	855.6	532
Total	1492.9	721.4	641.8	665.6	1204.9	907	1506.5	1405.2	1554.9	2919.6	2427.4
Tobacco											
Belgium	21.2	22.2	13.6	24	23.6	20.8	26.1	36.7	45.5	61.2	153.4
Germany	6.6	17.9	20.8	14.1	15.3	25.6	15.2	16	21	25.7	33.6
Netherlands	3.3	7.5	10.2	4.7	8.4	13.6	11.6	11.3	11.8	19	26.4
Russia	25.5	47.3	27.8	22	24.1	20.9	31.8	39.3	28.9	29	40.5
Saudi Arabia	9	8.2	8.7	5.7	7.9	8.2	11.1	11.1	10.7	12.6	19.7
Singapore	4	7	7.6	8.1	8.8	9.2	9.4	9.3	15.4	9.3	18.6
U.A.E.	14.4	9	15.3	12.6	21.4	23.3	16.1	22.3	36.8	55.5	49.9
U.K.	19.7	28.1	14.4	6.7	11.3	12.2	18	13	16.3	16	17.3
U.S.A	8.4	14.1	12.9	16.3	18	12.3	15.2	11.8	17.3	18.3	33
Yemen Republic	2.2	4.6	7.7	6.3	5.3	3.6	7.7	8.8	13.2	8.4	13.5
Others	66.8	67.1	50.9	49	67.2	88.9	117	121.1	155.5	224.8	346.6
Total	181.1	232.8	189.8	169.4	211.4	238.6	279.2	300.6	372.4	479.8	752.5
Spices											
Bangladesh	4.3	10.9	15.5	10.5	10.3	13.6	16.9	10.6	38.4	49.4	27
Germany	17.5	16.7	12.2	11.3	16.5	13.6	17.1	22.7	30.8	42.1	53.9
Japan	19.4	19.1	22.9	23.1	20.9	17.4	21.7	27.3	30.4	40	50.2
Saudi Arabia	6.2	8.2	12.6	9.2	10.2	11.5	12.2	13.4	14.5	23.1	33.2
Singapore	17.4	11.4	13.5	8.4	9.5	8	12.6	13.6	19.8	41.2	47.9
Spain	3.8	8.4	10.9	8	7.1	5.1	9	7.2	6.7	13.3	12.7
Sri Lanka	5.5	11.3	13	14.2	17.2	19.5	16.6	19.7	31.8	40.2	43.9
U.A.E.	18.2	17	20.8	14.6	14.1	20.2	20.7	24.6	34.3	52.8	81.6
U.K.	25.4	25.2	24.6	24.3	24.5	22.4	25.7	31.6	41.6	56.6	69
U.S.A	123.2	134.2	75.4	72.4	78.5	71.8	86.2	103.4	130.7	217.8	289.7
Others	147	145.5	132.7	117.8	133.1	132.9	180.6	203.9	319	495.2	669
Total	388	407.9	354.1	313.9	342.1	336	419.1	477.9	697.9	1071.7	1378.1
Cashew including Cashew Nut Shell											
Liquid											
Canada	2.4	9.2	7.1	7.4	6	4.7	6	7.4	6	2.9	4.1
France	10.8	10.8	12.1	12.3	11.6	8.8	13.1	17.3	16.7	16.1	20.7
Israel	6.3	7.1	6.4	5.1	4.3	2.4	4.5	4.1	4.9	4	5
Italy	4.6	5.7	5.7	4.6	4.5	3.5	5	5.6	5.8	3.1	5.9
Japan	25.7	29.8	26.7	16.6	20	19.3	21.9	24.9	20.1	24.2	31.1
Netherlands	72	108.8	83.2	53.6	51.2	44.6	71.2	92.8	83.6	60.6	77.2
Saudi Arabia	5.9	6.7	8.3	6	8.9	6.7	12.2	13.7	14.8	17	18.9

Commodity / Country	1998-99	1999-00	2000-01	2001-02	2002-03	2003-04	2004-05	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09
U.A.E.	15.3	19.5	18.3	13	18.5	20	30	42.7	45.9	68	82.9
U.K.	28.4	44.8	32.6	26.4	22.8	20.2	31.6	32.8	21.6	19	19.1
U.S.A	171.3	271.7	202.3	186.6	224.4	180.4	261	222.4	215.5	198.3	209.5
Others	45.1	53.7	46.7	43.5	53.6	60.5	97.4	122	119.1	141.9	162.8
Total	387.8	567.9	449.5	376.2	426	371	554	585.8	553.9	555.1	637.2
Oil Meals											
Bangladesh	1.8	7.1	21.7	31.6	38	68.4	65.1	28.5	81.2	104.7	104.3
Indonesia	51.8	50.7	68.6	81.1	32.9	128.5	81.9	144	153.4	213.8	189.6
Japan	43.2	40	34.2	9.9	17.2	52.3	48.6	131.8	127.9	232.5	337.6
Korea, Republic of	53.5	45.6	46	47	54	51.4	75.6	137.2	161.3	220.2	170.5
Pakistan	24.5	19.8	18.3	4.4	7.4	26.2	42.9	53.6	66.3	93.7	97.1
Russia	2.8	5.4	10.3	0.1	0.1	0.3	1.7	0.9	2.1	0.5	0
Singapore	41.4	33.5	75.7	71.9	23.2	45.1	46.6	72.2	35	19.3	72.5
Sri Lanka	8.8	9.5	10.1	12.4	13.1	27.2	23.2	22.5	26.2	45.8	40.2
Thailand	30.7	28.1	34.7	73.2	3.7	59.9	48.2	65.4	80.6	152.9	160.6
Vietnam	20	29.8	40.9	33.5	54.1	61.3	109.4	209.2	288.6	595.8	481
Others	183	108.5	87.1	109.4	63.5	208.2	164.3	235.9	193.8	342.8	579.4
Total	461.5	378	447.6	474.5	307.3	728.7	707.2	1101.1	1216.4	2022	2232.8
Marine Products											
China People's Republic of	51.5	87.7	115.8	84.9	118.1	88.8	110.3	150.6	114.1	168.6	108.9
Chinese Taipei	7.4	10.8	34.8	34.8	42.1	11	9.2	10.6	15.4	15.5	21.4
Hong Kong	14.9	18.3	24	19.2	22.6	27.2	34	41.4	42.3	63.3	71.3
Italy	20.5	23.3	29.4	29.9	32.7	34.2	37.4	48.1	66.5	73	66.2
Japan	488.3	491	509.9	344.2	321.4	242.2	272.6	256.1	282.5	271.5	223.6
Spain	32.5	40	44.6	60.4	79.7	65.8	102.2	116.5	125.9	157.5	111.4
Thailand	24.5	23.5	28.5	32.9	46.3	23.5	19.3	25.7	29.5	29.1	40.8
U.A.E.	84	63.3	71.2	43.4	34.6	33.8	47.1	55.7	61.5	59	57.3
U.K.	33.5	46	60.9	54.4	68	64.4	81.4	79	91.5	83.3	65.1
U.S.A	148.5	180.6	239	271.3	389.7	410.9	336.7	351.4	284.9	220.9	209
Others	132.8	198.2	235.8	261.3	276.3	326.9	389.6	454	654.1	578.8	561.4
Total	1038.4	1182.6	1393.8	1236.8	1431.6	1328.7	1439.8	1589.2	1768.2	1720.5	1536.4
Iron Ore											
Belgium	7.9	1.5	2.8	0.7	3.2	2.5	6.3	6.4	7.4	0	0.3
Chile	0	2.3	16.9	5.9					40	0	0
China People's Republic of	87.8	81.3	129.9	206.9	408.3	823.6	2684.2	3272.8	3333.4	5403.1	4329.5
Chinese Taipei	27.9	27.3	36.6	21.2	18.6	17	19	2.6	0	0	0
Iran	15.3	25	9.9	11.6	1.9	3.6	1.6	0	0	0.2	0.2
Japan	184.9	96	118.8	109.6	308.3	179.1	250.5	369.1	329.2	252.4	255.7
Korea, Republic of	13.3	15.2	22.1	20.4	52.4	26.8	65	51.6	84.3	65.7	46.5
Pakistan	6.2	1.6	3.7	4.7	16.3	8.4	22.4	19.9	26	14.4	36
South Africa	0	0	2.8	0	0	0	0	0	1.2	0	0
Turkey	0.7	2.5	4	0	1.5	0	3.8	7.4	6.9	0	0
Others	39.9	18.6	10	45.3	57.4	64.9	224.4	71.2	73.5	76.2	55.4
Total	384	271.2	357.6	426.4	867.9	1125.8	3277.3	3801.1	3902	5812	4723.6
Leather and Manufactures											
France	77.4	82.6	88.5	88.5	86.6	107.6	135.9	140.8	171.8	196.5	219.2
Germany	369.2	293	305.5	302.8	270.6	322	343.1	357.2	404.4	491.3	505.5
Hong Kong	54	54.5	98.2	121.2	165.7	226.9	247.6	251.5	279.7	280.9	237.4
Italy	199.6	165.1	238.5	258.5	250.1	277	249.8	308.7	409.2	487.2	458.2
Netherlands	50.2	44.1	55.4	60.2	50.6	57	64.7	82	99.5	134.4	148.2
Portugal	29.8	24.4	37.2	36.7	34.5	33.3	36.3	41.2	48.6	55.5	47.9
Russia	24.4	26.7	31.5	15.8	11.1	11.3	7.9	11.4	17	15.6	12
Spain	70.1	66.5	100.2	100.8	109.9	158.3	173.3	198.6	184.8	214.3	216.9
U.K.	235.5	262.9	265.4	244.9	236.5	237.9	297.7	335.7	355.8	410.7	407.4
U.S.A	255.9	258	342.3	284.8	242.4	245.1	277.8	310.4	312.3	308.7	358.3
Others	294.7	312.5	381.7	396	390.4	486.7	587.4	660.3	733.7	907.4	945
Total	1660.7	1590.2	1944.4	1910.1	1848.3	2163	2421.6	2697.7	3016.7	3502.5	3556
Gems and Jewellery											
Belgium	827.8	855.5	908.9	861.8	1024.8	1054	1349.4	1490.8	1469.2	1963.3	1875.9
Hong Kong	1235.8	1814.8	1745	1683.6	1878.3	2334.6	2735.3	3330.1	3463	5098.3	5263.2
Israel	1236.8	342.3	273.7	257.7	412.5	477	697.7	813.7	875.6	1037.7	793
Japan	1237.8	449.4	385.7	381	417.5	355.4	499.9	485.5	430.5	450.1	371.4
Singapore	1238.8	117.9	119.6	121.5	257.5	180.2	563	1241.1	151.6	217.3	547.7
Switzerland	1239.8	131.9	143.1	120.9	115.9	149.3	170.1	143.5	117.6	211.9	207
Thailand	1240.8	171.5	190.5	237.5	232.1	202	293.3	329.5	340.1	390.5	321.5
U.A.E.	1241.8	259	440	542.1	661.9	1373.5	2537.4	2488	3299.9	4039	10756.3
U.K.	1242.8	133.5	144.5	170	203	221.1	221.8	226	278.1	285.2	563.4
U.S.A	1243.8	2923	2728.9	2628.7	3345.8	3699.5	4046.6	4371.6	4755.3	4972.3	4588.4
Others	1244.8	303.6	304.2	471.2	480.7	526.7	647.4	609.3	796.1	1013.1	2667.4
Total	1245.8	7502.3	7384	7306.3	9029.9	10573.3	13761.8	15529.1	15977	19678.7	27955.2
Chemicals & allied products											
Brazil	49.1	70.7	118.2	112.7	123.5	147.6	182.9	236.1	274.3	389.8	486.7
China People's republic of	76.2	99.3	140.2	158.3	224.9	291.1	452.5	567	636.4	790.4	513.6
Germany	189.5	184.1	215.6	209.7	290.9	374.1	381.3	456.5	551.2	697.1	706.3

Commodity / Country	1998-99	1999-00	2000-01	2001-02	2002-03	2003-04	2004-05	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09
Hong Kong	130.2	128.1	156.3	100.5	99.2	107.3	77.7	80	74.1	69.4	51.4
Italy	88.5	105.4	119.4	94.2	123.1	131	143.3	198.2	254.9	328.5	355.9
Netherlands	118.1	155.1	144.8	117.2	133.7	163	191.1	269.1	311.9	406	451.4
Russia	69.6	143.2	124.5	117.1	119.3	158	189.3	264.5	318.8	343.3	369.8
U.A.E.	114.6	156.4	165.8	174.8	153.7	217.7	199.9	277.1	328.1	379	446.9
U.K.	118.2	132.1	148	158.5	197.9	227.6	269.9	356.8	409.8	503	519.3
U.S.A	341	339.9	444.1	563.4	710.8	761.3	920.1	1193.1	1557.5	2124.3	2451.5
Others	1611.2	1894.8	2257.1	2273.4	2858.4	3626.5	4643.2	10871.1	12618.5	8858.2	10358.9
Total	2906.2	3409	4034.1	4079.9	5035.4	6205.2	7651.4	14769.5	17335.5	14888.9	16711.7
Engineering Goods											
Bangladesh	125.7	134.3	202.4	268.2	232	443.5	326.8	358.7	328.2	411	546.7
Germany	224.8	209.6	283	292.6	382.9	527	725.9	841.4	1101.2	1568.4	2299.9
Hong Kong	119.5	175.5	222.8	118.8	158.7	176.3	221.6	318.7	475.7	431.5	592.4
Italy	119.2	149.4	197.5	172.8	224.1	365.1	639.5	653.7	1280.5	1341.2	1353.1
Malaysia	73.5	155.8	242.1	275.7	140.8	234.3	293.8	371.4	396	799.2	1826.6
Singapore	168.7	223.5	313.8	354.9	374.2	431.2	771.5	1173.4	1414.7	1839.9	3122
Sri Lanka	163.6	166.7	217.6	160.2	258.9	379.6	457.4	663.1	700.6	732.9	587.6
U.A.E.	313.2	366	444.7	462.4	600.2	957.5	1137	1835.4	2098.7	2845.4	3488.7
U.K.	291.2	336	430.3	363.9	443	725.9	902.2	1077.1	1276.8	1543.5	2028
U.S.A	771	932	1221.8	1132	1526.3	1719	2786.4	3395.1	4576.9	5120.4	6178.6
Others	2093.7	2303.3	3042.5	3356.2	4691.9	6446	9086.1	11030.8	15918	20731.8	25261.9
Total	4463.9	5152.1	6818.6	6957.8	9033	12405.4	17348.3	21718.8	29567.2	37365.2	47285.6
Cotton yarn, fabrics, madeups,Handloom product etc.											
Bangladesh	123.4	157	175.7	165.8	138.3	174.5	208.2	244	226.8	373.4	323.1
Germany	124.4	128.9	142.4	117.7	136.6	144.5	144	145.9	150.3	161	173.7
Hong Kong	125.4	170	204.2	123.9	103.5	121.7	94.9	89.7	67	54.7	42.1
Italy	126.4	129.4	151.8	161.4	155	173.5	189.2	228.9	249.7	215.7	165.2
Japan	127.4	104.1	108.7	110.9	117	99.8	90.9	87.5	104.1	85.9	78.4
Korea, Republic of	128.4	189.8	130.9	131.7	178.9	214.6	174.6	217.1	210.8	172.9	137.9
Mauritius	129.4	91.2	99.5	76.5	67.3	78.6	64.8	49.8	59.6	54	32.8
U.A.E.	130.4	98.2	110.8	76.9	92.8	88.9	113.6	120.8	101.2	105.8	99.8
U.K.	131.4	194.2	195.6	171.2	155.6	162.1	154.9	147.3	154.1	151.9	134
U.S.A	132.4	447.8	531.7	491.1	623.7	552	608.9	833.3	864.4	904.5	866.1
Others	133.4	1379.1	1609.5	1521.9	1582.4	1584.6	1606.2	1780.4	2030.7	2373.5	2062.6
Total	1412.4	3089.6	3460.7	3072.9	3351	3394.8	3450.1	3944.8	4218.7	4653.3	4115.7
Readymade Garment											
Canada	177.1	203.5	234.3	218.3	256.4	240.9	250.7	274.6	273	251.7	268.1
France	178.1	341.2	349.8	338.4	395.1	435.6	472.3	638.9	670.3	705.9	791.4
Germany	179.1	319.4	355.6	362.7	466	496.8	449.2	677.8	646.4	861	1120.8
Italy	180.1	138.4	157.9	150.7	168.6	222.8	290.8	383.2	443.5	423.4	443.4
Japan	181.1	76.4	115.1	83.1	65.2	77	84.9	118.4	122.8	104.4	134.1
Netherlands	182.1	147.5	158.2	188.5	223.8	224.6	204.9	293.4	350	370.8	428.3
Russia	183.1	245.6	310.4	332.6	264.6	202.3	104.3	21.1	70	60	32.4
U.A.E.	184.1	490.2	542.9	364.4	395.2	612.6	522.7	446.3	523.7	690.5	943
U.K.	185.1	346.9	405.2	422.3	510.6	537.1	656.9	944.2	945.5	1196.1	1290.6
U.S.A	186.1	1478.6	1845.9	1459.6	1725.9	1617.4	1991.3	2852.5	2890.4	2832.6	2710.3
Others	187.1	977.4	1093.5	1086	1218.5	1564.3	1533.5	1967.3	1956.7	2190.7	2772.6
Total	188.1	4765.1	5568.9	5006.6	5689.9	6231.4	6561.4	8617.7	8892.3	9687.1	10935
Jute & Jute Manufacturers											
Australia	4.5	4.8	4	4.2	4.4	4.6	4.7	8.2	3.8	6.4	6.8
Belgium	22.4	24.7	28.8	23	19.5	24.9	23.4	16.3	18.5	18.5	12.4
Egypt, Arab Republic of	4.6	5.2	8.1	7.5	9.6	9.6	12.6	14.9	11.3	15.3	14.2
Germany	4	3.9	3.2	3.4	5.8	7.1	11.1	12	11.7	12.9	12.4
Italy	2.9	2.5	3.3	2.7	4.3	5.4	7.3	8.4	8.9	9.7	7.3
Japan	6	6.5	7	5.7	7	11.5	7.1	7.9	4.8	6.9	6.2
Saudi Arabia	5.6	5.2	6.6	5.3	7.8	7.4	14	10.9	11.3	15.6	13.6
Turkey	10.5	5.7	7.4	6.1	9.5	11.8	21.2	13.8	16.2	16.2	13.5
U.K.	14	10.4	9	11.6	11.3	16.4	15.9	15.3	15	30.9	31.2
U.S.A	26.3	25.6	29.6	24.7	44.6	47.3	61.8	77.3	60.5	70.5	48.3
Others	37.5	31.3	44.1	34.2	63.9	96.3	97.1	111.4	98.5	124.8	133.2
Total	138.2	125.7	151.2	128.3	187.6	242.4	276.3	296.3	260.4	327.7	299.1
Carpets											
Australia	9.2	11	9.9	6.8	8.9	10.4	12.1	18.1	17.3	18.7	16.3
Canada	10.6	11.8	11.4	10.9	11.3	11.5	11.1	17	19.7	17.9	14.9
France	17.2	19.2	17.1	15.4	15.8	16.2	16.4	14.6	16.6	18.1	13.8
Germany	119	155.5	116.9	86.5	79.8	95.7	112.9	156.1	139.4	142	125.4
Italy	12.9	10.5	9.4	8.6	10.4	12.4	15.6	22	27.9	29.4	24.6
Japan	15.3	17.1	19.2	16.4	14.7	12.4	10.7	14.3	14.2	11.1	8.8
Spain	7.3	9.6	9.4	7.3	9.1	12.5	12.3	21	25.9	27.2	16.8
Sweden	12.3	13.9	13.2	13.1	10	14.2	9.1	17.9	20.3	16.4	13.9
U.K.	23.3	26.2	27.7	32.4	35.1	44.7	42.9	53.3	63.2	54.4	37.4
U.S.A	241.9	289.4	270.1	227.7	263	265.9	283.1	373.4	384.2	369	275
Others	74.5	81.1	77.5	85	74.7	89.6	110.2	144.8	199.4	239	228.2
Total	543.5	645.1	581.7	510.2	532.6	585.7	636.4	852.6	928	943.3	775.1

TABLE 133 : EXPORTS OF SELECT COMMODITIES TO PRINCIPAL COUNTRIES - US \$

Commodity / Country	US \$ million										
	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20
1	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23
Tea											
Germany	22	32.5	41.9	42.3	43	35.2	40	41.4	42.9	43.8	37.6
Iran	44.8	67.3	48	74	100.3	88.2	105.1	98.4	126.4	153.7	198.1
Iraq	26	4.1	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.7	5.2	7.8	9.9
Japan	15.7	24.8	25.9	26.7	25.4	24.4	22.5	22.6	24.2	22.7	27.8
Kazakhstan	29.8	50.8	54.6	61.5	50.3	54.4	31.1	34.2	27.4	28.8	23.6
Poland	11.5	11.4	11.7	10.8	11.8	10.6	13.4	12.5	15.2	16.5	16.3
Russia	99	113.1	120.8	126.3	108.5	96.7	102.9	108.4	120.8	106.4	102
U.A.E.	72.4	77.7	92.6	95.9	79.9	44.1	50.8	56.1	66.3	56.2	43.6
U.K.	67.7	79.1	106	102.2	58.3	57.1	64.1	51.1	55.8	48.2	41.9
U.S.A	51.7	61.1	68.8	67.2	71.3	67.8	63.2	69.3	64.3	59.8	63
Others	179.8	214.3	280.7	252.5	249.8	203	226.6	236.6	288.7	286.9	262.7
Total	620.4	736.2	851.1	859.6	798.8	681.8	720	731.3	837.3	830.9	826.5
Coffee											
Belgium	18.3	47.8	60.5	64.8	52.4	41.8	43.6	55.7	55.9	48	46.9
Germany	30.2	91.1	105.7	74.6	81	79.7	70.6	80.8	93.8	70.6	78.4
Italy	88.7	160.7	195.9	206.1	184.6	161	173.8	176.5	172.6	154	127.9
Latvia	3.3	3.9	7.9	5.8	5.3	6.2	2.9	2.3	2.2	2.2	2.2
Netherlands	1.3	5.6	9	4.4	4.8	5.6	4.1	7.5	8	6.5	7.8
Russia	61.5	60.8	93.9	74.6	37.5	57.6	64.8	71	68.6	52.1	60.7
Spain	9.7	17.8	30.5	16.2	13.4	13.6	12.6	18.7	20.8	15.4	13.7
Switzerland	7	5.5	8.5	8.7	6.5	8.2	9.3	4.6	4.4	4.7	5.2
U.K.	3.4	5.4	9.4	7.3	7.3	10	7.4	8.2	9	10.4	11.2
U.S.A	10.9	18.9	23.2	30.6	29.2	25	28.7	36.8	48.9	48.5	31.6
Others	194	243.1	401.7	373	376.9	405.3	366.1	380.7	484.4	409.9	353.2
Total	428.3	660.6	946.2	866.1	798.8	814	783.9	842.8	968.6	822.3	738.9
Rice											
Bangladesh	0.1	2.6	56.8	15.4	251.2	451.1	135	31.5	838.8	222.3	14.9
France	0.3	9.1	16.3	17.4	21.6	18.6	17	19.3	20.4	7.1	5.5
Kuwait	217.6	239.6	296.9	217.4	265.7	270.8	229.9	168.4	200.2	202.6	221.1
Saudi Arabia	705.4	688.7	763.9	752	1195.4	1294.2	919.9	734.9	903	1037.2	1018
Singapore	12.2	8	44.1	74.6	74.9	98.3	66.6	54.4	50.8	48.2	55.6
South Africa	3.2	13.2	94.6	182.1	174.5	145.5	99.2	101	71.5	72.9	70.9
U.A.E.	661.2	624.4	820.4	380.1	313.6	439.9	589.3	601.4	586.9	445.3	340.1
U.K.	42.4	77.4	144.8	166.5	144.9	157.9	153.8	109.4	166.8	115.2	110.3
U.S.A	36.2	55.4	120.2	118.6	166.3	155.6	164.9	139.8	182.3	203.2	212.6
Yemen	63.7	65.2	120.7	189.1	223.3	243.7	153.8	122.3	213	255.4	220.4
Others	630	759.3	2552	4100.4	4958.6	4577.5	3317.4	3651.5	4500.3	5141.1	4127.1
Total	2372.3	2542.9	5030.7	6213.6	7790.1	7853.1	5846.6	5733.8	7733.9	7750.6	6396.6
Tobacco											
Belgium	165.5	123.2	134.7	155.8	206.9	153.6	183.6	189.8	174.4	135.5	149.1
Germany	41	52.2	30.8	28.9	36	18.4	14.9	17.6	13.6	21.4	15.1
Netherlands	50.2	42.6	38.1	30.9	36.9	33.8	41.4	28.3	19.5	23.9	13.3
Russia	48	42.4	37.1	42.7	41.9	37.4	38.7	32.5	25.5	26.7	21.7
Saudi Arabia	15.4	19.9	29.2	36.8	45.6	58.2	61.6	36.4	20.3	16.8	15.8
Singapore	13.8	18.3	15.5	20.4	20.4	29.1	27.7	17.9	20.2	16.5	16.3
U.A.E.	49.5	57	56.9	74.5	82.8	78.9	100	131.9	138	129.9	145.5
U.K.	24.5	24.5	33.1	22.2	15	11.7	5.6	9.6	9	4.4	1.5
U.S.A	30.5	23	27.7	32.5	30.6	25.2	28.1	30	23.9	30.6	29.5
Yemen Republic	14.4	16.8	13.5	13	12.4	16.5	16.2	13.1	12.2	15.6	18.2
Others	462.9	454.8	419.4	467.9	482.7	495.7	464.4	451.5	477.6	560.1	478.9
Total	915.7	874.7	836	925.6	1011.4	958.6	982	958.7	934.2	981.3	905
Spices											
Bangladesh	47.8	52.2	58.2	41.8	59	56.2	51.2	118.6	83.5	115.6	183.4
Germany	47.3	78	108.5	106.2	80.5	74.3	81.8	77.9	90.6	81.7	72.1
Japan	52	49.1	61.1	51.5	41.6	47.5	50.4	54	52.8	57	56.4
Saudi Arabia	41.6	46.3	92.9	75.9	78.4	85.9	98.5	91.2	101.4	48.9	48
Singapore	39.3	52.7	102.2	119.5	70.5	46.4	50	48.2	43.1	94.3	63.7
Spain	12.4	18.2	26.6	36	37.6	40.9	36.5	45.1	31.2	20.1	22.6
Sri Lanka	52.3	66.4	80.6	58	53.9	67.7	96.8	97.1	76.4	88.2	107.3
U.A.E.	70.5	93.1	147.7	108.5	87.8	122.3	102.3	108.7	120.3	101.6	116.3
U.K.	75.3	96.7	119.8	114.3	104.1	101.2	115.6	116.4	107.6	100.7	94.4
U.S.A	191	261.5	492.2	455.1	391.5	409.8	426.4	440	488.1	533.9	510.8
Others	668.3	951.2	1468.8	1648.7	1492.4	1378.3	1432	1654.8	1910.8	2080.5	2347.4
Total	1297.8	1765.4	2758.6	2815.5	2497.3	2430.3	2541.5	2851.9	3105.9	3322.4	3622.6
Cashew including Cashew Nut Shell Liquid											
Canada	2.8	3.6	7.5	4.9	5.6	5.5	3.2	3.2	6.6	3	1.8
France	20	19.8	22.8	20.6	21.3	21.4	23.7	17.7	23.9	14.3	9.3

Commodity / Country	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20
Israel	3.5	3	5.1	3.8	5.3	5.2	5.7	3	5.2	2.4	0.9
Italy	3.7	6.4	11.7	6	5.9	8.7	5.9	6.2	3.2	1.9	1.4
Japan	32.9	35.4	50.4	50.7	51.8	57.6	64.4	58.7	92.6	81.6	65.1
Netherlands	54.5	63.5	76.4	62.9	70.2	68.2	47.8	43.9	90.6	78	86.6
Saudi Arabia	20.1	23.6	43.2	42.5	53.6	50	59.7	70.6	85.7	69.5	56.1
U.A.E.	104.2	86.3	126.5	101.1	128.5	180	146.6	181.4	194.3	124.9	118
U.K.	23	15.7	22.9	19	19.7	20.4	13.9	15.5	19.4	12.6	6.8
U.S.A	164	202.7	313.1	229.4	250.1	230.4	176.5	163.2	140.6	48.1	34.8
Others	167.6	166.2	249	212.1	230.2	261.9	221.2	223.6	260.2	218.1	186
Total	596.3	626.2	928.6	753	842.3	909.3	768.6	786.9	922.4	654.4	566.8
Oil Meals											
Bangladesh	191.5	233.6	195.6	168.8	221.5	183.2	83.3	154.8	212	214.2	72.8
Indonesia	105.5	173.5	132.6	123.9	117.8	44.4	12.2	12.6	12.6	14.9	5.8
Japan	169.4	458	466.3	297.5	136.2	30.5	25.3	84.6	50.6	69.7	32.4
Korea, Republic of	106.5	107.9	115.7	259.5	311.8	156.9	11.2	1.4	0.3	0	0
Pakistan	87.6	51.8	199.2	193.6	10.6	0.2	0	0.5	0.6	0.4	0.2
Russia	0.5	0	0	0	4.9	4.9	1.6	3.3	3.3	3.9	0.6
Singapore	23.5	33.4	9.2	53.5	252.8	183.4	123.7	90.8	102.4	146.7	148.7
Sri Lanka	43.1	51.6	58.4	71.9	49.8	38.4	12.7	20.9	17.8	20	7.5
Thailand	147.3	102.3	203.1	292	161.5	77.4	19.9	17.9	44.9	70.6	49.2
Vietnam	408.8	471.2	342.4	299.3	145.1	76.2	69.2	66.2	116.1	140.1	63.4
Others	367.1	746.2	739.1	1147.9	1384.5	528.8	193.9	352.5	529.3	828.1	446.9
Total	1650.8	2429.5	2461.6	2907.9	2796.4	1324.2	553	805.4	1089.9	1508.6	827.5
Marine Products											
China People's Republic of	230.5	283.7	183.8	181.4	113.4	98.6	82.3	79.3	84.3	99	66
Chinese Taipei	50.9	70.1	52.8	55.6	126.8	143.6	129.2	163.2	163.6	144.2	127.9
Hong Kong	159.1	132.9	98.4	97.1	407	447.3	404.7	390.2	453.6	419.2	418
Italy	88.6	119.3	108.7	110.6	193	131.7	149.7	137.5	164.1	723.9	1345.4
Japan	245.4	335.5	434.9	357.3	166.3	205.4	184.3	239.5	249.6	170.3	149.1
Spain	144.4	171.3	178.3	171.4	61	71.2	59.3	69.3	71.4	80.9	67.9
Thailand	86.7	102	127	103.1	150.8	112.6	126.1	224.8	264.5	321.5	211.1
U.A.E.	69.3	67.1	99.7	101	131.1	172	138.9	168	195	181.5	200.4
U.K.	81.4	78.9	99.4	91.9	143.6	162.3	134.8	148.6	180.6	139.8	136.6
U.S.A	205.3	399	616.6	739.3	1267.9	1457.5	1326.9	1767.1	2418.3	2327.9	2535.5
Others	725.1	855.7	1461.1	1452.6	2255.9	2508.4	2031.3	2515.6	3142.8	2194.3	1464.2
Total	2086.7	2615.6	3460.7	3461.3	5016.6	5510.5	4767.5	5903.1	7387.7	6802.6	6722
Iron Ore											
Belgium	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chile	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.1	0
China People's Republic of	5114.3	4367.6	4194.2	1373.5	5.5	77.5	31.8	6.3	0	0	0
Chinese Taipei	0	0	0.1	0	245.1	184.5	0	23.1	189.8	86	181.4
Iran	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Japan	312.9	117	263.7	186.1	1200.5	196.8	155.3	1449.6	1091.2	952.8	2134.2
Korea, Republic of	63.1	89.1	99.7	14	0	0	0	0	0	11.2	5.6
Pakistan	0	0	2.5	0	49.8	49.9	0	4.3	90.1	104.9	101.9
South Africa	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Turkey	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.6	47.6
Others	488.6	126.6	68.9	26.7	51.5	6.6	4.4	50.2	99.9	150.7	154.3
Total	5978.9	4700.3	4629.1	1600.3	1552.4	515.3	191.5	1533.5	1471.1	1317.3	2625
Leather and Manufactures											
France	253.4	278.8	302.7	319	339.5	358.2	295.7	275.9	315.9	309.6	287.4
Germany	488.5	572.9	729	627.3	729.2	765.5	643.6	624.5	645.7	624.2	575.2
Hong Kong	251.2	324.9	358.4	440.2	473.4	422.9	316.3	265.6	247.6	190.6	108.6
Italy	396.3	452.3	524.8	436.9	511.5	499.8	403.2	368.4	382	362.3	314.4
Netherlands	136.7	154.5	197.2	189.1	207.8	210.4	169.2	155.7	179.6	178.9	162.3
Portugal	39.3	39.3	46.3	38.2	51.3	68.4	62	67.4	68.6	68.7	58.4
Russia	6.7	18.6	32.7	28.4	51	49.6	48.5	51	55.9	52.3	46.2
Spain	218.1	247.3	295.6	266	303.1	347.3	324.4	288.5	272.6	255.2	251.8
U.K.	451.8	500	538.5	592.9	641.1	726.5	693.1	585.3	589.8	573	506.8
U.S.A	294.5	345.7	437.7	523.2	648	733	801.2	834.1	815.8	853.8	829.1
Others	824.6	976.3	1330.7	1409	1616.9	1849.1	1650.6	1649	1715.5	1672.1	1505
Total	3361.1	3910.6	4793.6	4870.2	5572.8	6030.5	5407.8	5165.6	5288.9	5140.8	4645.3
Gems and Jewellery											
Belgium	1641.5	2391.7	3817.3	2439	2677	2678.1	2325	2471.6	2426.6	2473.4	2173.1
Hong Kong	6231.9	8663.7	11188.9	10460.2	11138.3	12201.7	10884.8	12834.2	13121.9	11138.8	9523.4
Israel	750.4	961.6	1456	1156.3	1314.8	1182.8	1002.6	999.1	1031	1006.4	913.8
Japan	256	280.4	372.7	346.5	345.7	281.1	246.9	308.6	276.5	432.4	401.2
Singapore	598.6	474.8	615.5	637.2	530.1	492.3	427.5	564	559.4	702.7	572.4
Switzerland	106.7	180.1	376.3	197.1	357	292.3	270.9	216.4	276.4	241	209.5
Thailand	309	383.9	603.5	631	755.5	664.2	627.6	606.9	653.9	613.6	646.5
U.A.E.	12369.1	16616.4	16364.2	18751.6	12750.8	12260.9	12915.2	13865.5	10821.3	10394.9	9413.6
U.K.	348.8	349.5	506.1	486.8	404.7	478.4	516.7	461.9	693.5	482.1	482.7
U.S.A	4718	5270.5	6772.1	6755.2	7796.4	8370.9	8631.4	9689.4	10016.1	10403.2	9215.3
Others	1666.3	4903.5	2767.9	1596.5	3318	2363.4	1435.6	1395.3	1668	2362.6	2340.1

Commodity / Country	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20
Total	28996.3	40476.1	44840.5	43457.4	41388.3	41266.1	39284.3	43412.8	41544.4	40251	35891.7
Chemicals & allied products											
Brazil	461.1	533.3	673	838.6	255.2	283.1	259.7	271.3	375.6	495.1	427.2
China People's republic of	655.1	828.5	1041.3	1043.9	620.6	611.5	564.1	528.4	607.3	697.5	673.5
Germany	608.4	743.8	928.6	980.1	25.2	34.9	25.7	49.5	55.3	22.8	23.9
Hong Kong	56.7	85.5	60	70.1	232.2	279.4	267.8	272.2	310.1	317	323.4
Italy	342.9	368.7	443.4	406.4	383.3	400.2	377.3	349	429.5	488.3	516.1
Netherlands	444.7	602.3	798.2	700	764	889.6	692.6	783.5	1942.9	2966.9	2355.5
Russia	311.5	500.3	471.7	643.3	75.8	87.2	77.7	113	148.3	140.3	163
U.A.E.	494	567.4	627.9	657.3	646.4	542.6	510.9	526.2	723.7	785.8	782.9
U.K.	568.2	663.9	806.5	835.8	290.7	299.4	265.5	250.1	279.7	308.8	279
U.S.A	2721.6	3572.3	4741.2	5516.7	1496.8	1593	1389.8	1420	1734.1	2036.7	2119.7
Others	10137.9	12134.9	15543.4	16851.4	7495.8	7452.8	7300.1	7773.2	9331.8	10963.5	11059.5
Total	16802.1	20600.9	26135.2	28543.6	12286	12473.6	11731.3	12336.1	15938.2	19222.7	18723.6
Drugs & Pharmaceuticals											
Brazil	--	--	--	--	313.3	375.9	326.2	337.4	383.7	452.1	473.1
Germany	--	--	--	--	404.5	372.9	347.7	333.3	389.3	445.8	504.2
Hong Kong	--	--	--	--	42.6	43.5	35.3	36.7	35.5	39.1	38.9
Italy	--	--	--	--	129	99.1	122.6	123.7	153.6	166.7	146.1
Netherlands	--	--	--	--	234	243.2	243.7	202.6	233.7	205.9	321
People's Republic of China	--	--	--	--	118.5	139.1	144.1	145.4	200.5	230.2	288
Russia	--	--	--	--	546.6	425.6	373.8	383.5	468.8	485.6	552.4
U.A.E.	--	--	--	--	119.6	109.3	109.5	112.9	128.3	260.2	203.1
U.K.	--	--	--	--	528	543.1	563.8	549.8	556.7	630.2	557.9
U.S.A	--	--	--	--	3958.3	4311.7	5513.9	5563.5	5118.2	5824.3	6749.4
Others	--	--	--	--	8555.1	8768	9129	8996.2	9614.1	10406.4	10868.5
Total	--	--	--	--	14949.5	15431.5	16909.5	16785	17282.4	19146.6	20702.7
Engineering Goods											
Bangladesh	577.7	595.3	787	1105.7	1335.3	1476.3	1605.9	2069	2522	2931.9	2533.1
Germany	1762.4	2320.3	2613.3	2447.9	2173.4	2251	2247.8	2331.3	3370.6	3406.5	3150.2
Hong Kong	482	535.3	545.3	358.9	155.3	170.2	159.8	124	292.1	235.2	219
Italy	1242.8	1646.7	1711.6	1514.2	1638.8	1761.7	1557.5	2158.8	2553.9	2442.9	2016.4
Malaysia	1068.5	1730.8	1116.1	1224.1	912.9	2073.7	1354.4	2421.6	2029.9	1745	2312.5
Singapore	2529.1	2323.3	5219.1	3488.3	2936	2478.4	2841.2	2831.8	2000.4	3478.1	2250.9
Sri Lanka	597.1	1389	1940.2	1741.9	2115.1	3774.1	2784	1462.1	1605.2	1775.8	1268.6
U.A.E.	2459.1	3637.5	4829.6	4613.8	5189.6	5971	4309.4	4113.8	4276.3	4370.4	4523.3
U.K.	1729.3	1991.4	2470.9	2632.6	2557.7	2718.9	2363	2616.6	2957.7	2907	2686.2
U.S.A	4221.1	6262	8516.3	7688.7	6450.1	8123.2	7194.1	7414.4	10646.4	12373.3	12411.9
Others	21602.2	35705.8	38082.8	38472.5	38438.6	42276.4	35532.3	39672.7	46451.9	47955.4	45316.3
Total	38271.3	58137.9	67832.2	65288.6	63902.7	73074.8	61949.5	67216.1	78706.3	83621.6	78688.4
Cotton yarn, fabrics, madeups ,Handloom product etc.											
Bangladesh	281.2	653.6	686.8	934.3	978.8	1044.4	1044.2	1051.9	1201.8	1324.8	1164.8
Germany	131.6	213.2	255.8	201.6	340	312.1	272.1	280	306.5	284.3	275
Hong Kong	51.7	119.2	96	157.7	162.1	98.9	67.2	86.2	52.4	39.9	19.8
Italy	134	199.4	191.2	134.8	214.7	208.8	195	207.3	229.3	198	164
Japan	46.5	92.9	103.3	79.6	129.1	125	103.4	102.6	101.3	111.6	113.5
Korea, Republic of	227.2	312.9	223.1	216	50	42.8	41.8	41.8	52.6	49.4	42.1
Mauritius	26.1	43.4	44.3	38.7	214.2	223.2	200.4	201.8	213.4	249.3	201.1
U.A.E.	89.4	111.8	139.8	148.4	228.1	258.5	247.2	207	185.5	173.9	195.1
U.K.	84.9	140.7	173	189.3	291.5	304.4	273.1	256.6	260	272	257.6
U.S.A	630.8	1003.9	1256	1391.8	2125.9	2284.8	2285.2	2326.3	2327.7	2529.8	2473.3
Others	1980.8	2894.6	3635.8	4024.4	6281.5	5871.8	5389.7	5100.7	5327.2	5982.3	5119.7
Total	3684.2	5785.6	6805.1	7516.6	11015.9	10774.6	10119.4	9862.2	10257.7	11215.1	10026
Readymade Garment											
Canada	238.9	244.1	259.4	227.5	246.6	242.3	250.5	228.8	232.1	236.9	217.8
France	712.7	700.2	811.7	664.8	768.4	892.3	830.2	776	763.4	737.4	644
Germany	1057.1	1080.2	1154.3	986.8	1189.7	1220.3	1112.8	1146.4	1178.5	1143.6	956.4
Italy	410.5	421.8	507.3	383.9	450.6	442.1	379.9	371	395.8	416.3	341.2
Japan	132	144.9	217.9	215.1	221.7	202.4	185.4	178.3	191	215.8	216.5
Netherlands	403.9	433.5	552.4	427.3	449.8	435.5	380.2	394.8	449.6	471.3	445.8
Russia	24.1	17.1	45.4	44.9	80.7	90.8	57.8	68.7	83.1	77.6	74.1
U.A.E.	969.7	1100.7	1346.4	1430.6	1737.6	2649.6	3413.9	3926.6	2810.7	1980.9	1683.1
U.K.	1280.8	1314.8	1495.4	1493.9	1659	1858.9	1802.3	1631.3	1718.3	1605.3	1530.7
U.S.A	2655	2951.5	3184.2	3091.9	3423.8	3614.5	3861.8	3748	3864.3	4165.7	4227.3
Others	2820.9	3193	4116.8	3958.9	4762.5	5184.6	4689.7	4898.3	5020	5087.5	5150.8
Total	10705.6	11601.8	13691.2	12925.6	14990.5	16833.3	16964.4	17368.2	16706.7	16138.3	15487.7
Jute & Jute Manufacturers											
Australia	6.5	11	12.6	9.4	9.6	9.5	12	12.2	12.2	14.1	8.6
Belgium	10.2	22.5	10.8	9.1	6.5	6.4	5	4.9	6	5.3	7.5
Egypt, Arab Republic of	7.2	30.4	16	11.2	6.8	5.6	4.3	5.8	5.7	1.9	0.5
Germany	10	20.8	20	14.4	17.4	15.5	13.3	14.9	15.5	14	13.6

Commodity / Country	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20
Italy	6	8.8	7	7	4.9	5.8	10.3	8.3	5.8	5.9	6.1
Japan	3.3	7.1	5.6	5.8	4.7	4.7	4.3	4.3	4.8	4.9	4.7
Saudi Arabia	10.8	28.3	20.3	19.2	17.4	14.7	12.5	10.7	12.8	7.5	9.8
Turkey	7.5	36.7	16.3	11.8	5.7	3.6	6.1	4.9	7.3	2.1	2.1
U.K.	18	28.1	27.9	23.6	25.3	23.4	27.3	23.2	22	22.7	23.8
U.S.A	47.6	68.6	64.9	64	65.3	69.5	65	61.6	70.5	70.4	74.6
Others	90.7	196.9	263.1	211.7	188.1	138.1	135.2	159.2	172.5	176.3	191.4
Total	217.8	459.2	464.5	387.2	351.6	297	295.4	309.9	335.1	324.9	342.6
Carpets											
Australia	17.3	22.2	25.1	30	33.4	35.1	46.9	50.1	56.3	58.7	56
Canada	14.5	15.7	17	19.1	22.7	20.5	20.5	23.2	20	21.8	22.1
France	13.1	12.7	15.8	15.8	19.6	16.2	22.2	23.5	23.9	26.3	24.1
Germany	145.7	137.9	118.6	112.4	110.8	110.2	144.6	170.4	140.7	102.2	86.6
Italy	20.7	20.6	20.1	14	17.3	17.1	19	25.3	25.5	30.4	23.4
Japan	9.2	8.8	10.1	13.3	12.9	12.6	13.9	14.6	15.6	16.4	14
Spain	11.5	12.1	11	7.1	10.5	9.1	13.2	14.5	15.6	16.7	16.2
Sweden	9.1	9.7	11.5	11.2	13.8	15.2	17.3	18.6	22.4	25.9	26.4
U.K.	37	35	43.5	91	78.5	70.3	84.4	79.4	78.5	78.5	70.1
U.S.A	239.5	336	331.1	411.3	516.1	589.8	699.5	707	733.2	808	774.8
Others	216.4	424.9	245.7	260.2	342.8	464.8	358.6	363.5	298	296.9	259.7
Total	734	1035.6	849.6	985.4	1178.3	1360.8	1440.1	1490.2	1429.8	1481.9	1373.3

Source:- Directorate General of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics & Ministry of Commerce and Industry.

India exports the cashew Nut to the major country like Canada, France, Japan, Saudi Arabia, Netherlands, U.A.E, U.K, USA, Italy, and Israel. Total export in the year 1998-99 was \$387.8 million, whereas the Canada was 2.4 million dollar, France was 10.8 million dollar, Israel was 6.3 million dollar, Italy was 4.6 million dollar, Japan was 25.17 million dollar, Saudi Arab was 5.9 million dollar, U. A. E was 15.3 million dollar, U.K was 28.4 million dollar and USA was 171.3 million dollar. It increases 585.5 million dollar in 2005-06, the total export of the France was 17.3 million dollar, Japan was 24.9 million dollar, Saudi Arab was 13.7 million dollar, U.A.E. was 42.7 million dollar, UK was 32.8 million dollar and USA was 222.4 million dollar. in 2018 -19 total export of a cashew nut was 654.4 million Dollar ,at the total explorers of France was 14.3 million dollar, Israel was 2.4 million dollar, Japan was 81.6 million dollar, Saudi Arab 69.5 million dollar ,UAE was 124.9 million dollar and USA was 48.1 million dollar. 2019-20 total export of the cashew nut was 566.8 million dollars , total export of the France was 9.3 million dollar ,Japan was 65.8 1 million dollar, Netherland 86.6 million dollars ,Saudi Arab was 56.1 million dollar, UAE was 11 8.0 million dollar & USA was 34.8 million dollar.

India export the Marine product in 1998-96 the total export was 138.4 million dollar, whereas the total export of the China was 50.5 million dollar, Hong Kong was 14.9 million dollar, Italy was 20.5 million dollar, Japan was 488.3 million dollar, Spain was 32.5 million dollar, UAE was 84.0 million dollar, UK was 33.5 million dollar and USA was 148.5 million dollar. In 2005-06 total export of the Marine product was 1589.2 Million Dollar, whereas the total export of the China was 150.6 million dollar, Hong Kong was for 41.4 million dollar, Italy was 48.1 million dollar, Japan was 256.1 million dollar, Spain was 116.5 million dollar, Thailand was 25.7 million dollar, UAE was 55.7 million dollar and USA was 351.4 million dollar. In 2018-19 total export was 6802.6 million dollar, whereas the total export of the China was 99.0 million dollar, Hong Kong was 419.2 million dollar, Italy was 72 3.9 million dollar, Japan was 170.3 million dollar ,Thailand was 321.5 million dollar and USA was 23 27.9 million dollar. In 2019-20 total export 6722.0 million dollar, China was 66.0 million dollar, Hong Kong was 418.0 million dollar, Italy was 134 5.4 million dollar, Thailand was 211.1 million dollar and USA what 2535.5 million dollar.

India export the iron ore in 1998-99 total export was 384.0 million dollar ,whereas the total export of the China was 87.8 million dollar, Japan was 184.9 million dollar, Pakistan was 6.2 million dollar and Turkey was 0.7 million dollar. In 2005-06 total export of the iron ore was 3801.1 million dollars, whereas the total export of the China was 3272.8 million dollar, Japan was 3609.1 million dollar, Korea was 51.6 million dollar, Pakistan was 19.9 million dollar and Turkey was 7.4 million dollar. 2018-19 total export of the iron ore was 1317.3 million dollar, whereas export of the Belgium was 5.1 million dollars, Japan was 952.8 million dollars, Korea was 11.2 million dollars, Pakistan was 104.9 million dollar and Turkey was 6.6million dollar. In 2019-20 total export of the iron ore was 2625.0 million dollar whereas the total export of the China was 181.4 million dollar, Japan was 2134.2 million dollar, Korea was 101.9 million dollar and Turkey was 47.6 million dollar.

India exported the leather & manufactures product in 1998-99 , total export was 1660.7 million dollar, whereas the total export of the France was 77.4 million dollar, Germany was 369.2 million dollar, Italy was 199.6 million dollar, Netherland was 50.2 million dollar, Russia was 24.4 million dollar, Spain was 70.1 million dollar , USA 255.9 million dollar and UK was 235.5 million dollar. In 2005-06 total export was 2697.7 million dollar, whereas the total export of the France was 140.8 million dollar, Germany 357.2 million dollar, Hong Kong was 215 1.5 million dollar, Italy was 308.7 million dollar , Spain was 198.6 million dollar ,USA was 310.4 million dollar and UK Was 335.7 million dollar . In 2018-19 total export was 5140.8 million dollar, whereas the total export of the France was 309.6 million dollar, Germany 624.2 million dollar, Italy what is 362.3 million dollar, Spain was 255.2 million dollar, UK wash 573.0 million dollar and USA was 853.8 million dollar. 2019-20 total export of was 4645.3 million dollar, whereas the total export of the France was 287.4 million dollar, Germany

was 575.2 million dollar, Hong Kong was 108.6 million dollar, Italy was 314.4 million dollar, Spain was 251.8 million dollar , UK was 506.8 million dollar and USA 829.1 million dollar.

India exported the Gems and Jewellery in 1998-99 , total exported was 1245.8 million dollar, whereas the total export of the Belgium was 827.8 million dollar, Hong Kong was 1235.8 million dollar, Israel was 1236.8 million dollar, Japan was 1237.8 million dollar, Switzerland was 1239.8 million dollar, Thailand was 1240.8 million dollar, UAE was 1241.8 million dollar, UK was 1242.8 million dollar and USA was 1243.8 million dollar. In the year 2005 -06 total export of the Gems and Jewellery was 15529.1 million dollar, whereas the total export of the Belgium was 1490.8 million dollar, Hong Kong was 3330.1 million dollar, Israel 1813.7 million dollar, Japan was 485.5 million dollar, Singapore was 12411.1 million dollar ,Thailand was 329.5 million dollar, UAE was 2488.0 million dollar, UK was 226.0 million dollar and USA was 4371.6 million dollar. In 2019-20 total export was 15529.1 million dollar, whereas the total export of the Belgium was 1490.8 million dollar, Hong Kong was 3330.1 million dollar, Japan was 485.5 million dollar, Switzerland was 143.5 million dollar, Thailand was 1329.5 million dollar, UAE was 2488.0 million dollar, UK was 226.0 million dollar and USA was 4371.6 million dollar.

India exporter total amount of the Engineering good in the year 1998-99 was 4463.9 million dollar, whereas the total export of the Bangladesh was 125.7 million dollar , Germany was 224.8 million dollar, Italy was 119.2 million dollar ,Singapore was 168.7 million dollar, Sri Lanka was 163.6 million dollar, UAE was 313.2 million dollar ,UK was 291.2 million dollar and USA was 771.0 million dollar. In the year 2005-06 total exports of the engineering good was 21718.8 million dollar, whereas the total export of the Bangladesh was 358.7 million dollar, Germany was 841.4 million dollar, Italy was 653.7 million dollar, Singapore was 1173.4 million dollar, UAE was 1835.4 million dollar, UK was 1077.1 million dollar and USA 3395.1 million dollar. In 2018-19 total export of engineering good was 83621.6 million dollar, whereas the total export of the Bangladesh 12391.9 million dollar, Germany was 3406.5 million dollar, Italy was 2442.9 million dollar, Singapore was 3478.1 million dollar, UAE was 4370.5 million dollar, UK was 2907.0 million dollar and USA was 12373.3 million dollar. In the year 2019-20 total export was 78688.4 million dollar, whereas export of the Bangladesh was 2533.1 million dollar, Germany was 3150.2 million dollar, Hong Kong was 219.0 million dollar, Italy was 2016.4 million dollar, Singapore was 2250.9 million dollar, UAE 4523.3 million dollar, UK was 2686.2 million dollar and USA was 12411.9 million dollar.

India exported the Cotton and Handloom product in the year 1998-99, in the year total export was 1412.4 million dollar, whereas the total export of the Bangladesh was 123.4 million dollar ,Hong Kong was 125.4 million dollar, Japan was 127.4 million dollar, UAE was 130.4 million dollar, UK was 131.4 million dollar and USA was 132.4 million dollar. In the year 2004-05 total export to be 3944.8 million dollar, whereas the total export of the Bangladesh was 244.0 million dollar, Hong Kong was 89.7 million dollar, Italy was 228.9 million dollar, Korea was 217.1 million dollar, UAE was 120.8 million dollar, UK was 147.3 million dollar and USA was 833.3 million dollars. 2018-19 total export watch 11215.1 million dollar, whereas the total export of the Bangladesh was 1324.8 million dollar, Germany was 284.3 million dollar, Japan was 111.6 million dollar, UAE was 1713.9 million dollars and USA was 2529.8 million dollar. In 2019-20 total export was 10026.0 million dollar, whereas the total export of the Bangladesh was 1164.8 million dollar, Germany was 275.0 million dollar, Italy was 113.5 million dollar, UAE was 195.1 million dollar, UK was 257.6 million dollar and USA was 2473.3 million dollar.

India export the Ready-made Garment in the year 1998-99 was \$188.1 million dollars, whereas the total export Canada was \$177.1 million dollar, France was \$178.1 million dollar Japan was \$181.1 million dollar & USA was \$186.1 million dollar. It increases the export \$8617.7 million in 2005-06, whereas the total export of Germany was \$677.8 million, Japan was \$118.4 million, Italy was \$383.2 million, U.A.E was \$446.3 million ,UK was \$944.2 million, USA was \$2852.5 million. In 2018-19 total export was \$16138.3 million , it decreases \$15487.7 million in 2019-20 ,in this year the total export Canada was \$217.8 million, France was \$644.0 million , Germany was \$956.4 million, Italy was \$341.2 million, Japan was \$216.5 million, Russia was \$74.1 million, UAE was \$1683.1 million, UK was \$1530.7 million , USA was \$4227.3 million.

India exported the Jute & Jute manufacturing product the major country was Australia, Belgium, Egypt, Germany, Italy, Japan, Saudi Arab, Turkey, UK and USA. Total export the jute and jute manufacturing product in the year 1998-99 was 138.2 million dollar, whereas the total export of the Australia was 4.5 million dollar, Belgium was 22.4 million dollar, Egypt was 4.6 million dollar, Saudi Arab was 5.6 million dollar, Turkey was 10.5 million dollar UK was 14.0 million dollar & USA was 26.3 million dollar. In the year 2005-06 total export watch 296.3 million dollar, whereas the total export of the Australia was 8.2 million dollar, Belgium was 16.3 million dollar, Egypt was 14.9 million dollar, Germany was 12.0 million dollar, Japan was 7.9 million dollar, Saudi Arab was 10.9 million dollar, UK was 15.3 million dollar & USA was 77.3 million dollar. In 2018-19 total export was 324.9 million dollar, whereas the total export in Australia was 14.1 million dollar, Germany was 14.0 million dollar, Japan was 4.9 million dollar, Saudi Arab was 7.5 million dollar UK was 22.7 million dollar & USA was 70.4 million dollar. In the year 2019-20 total export was 342.6 million dollar, whereas the total export of the Australia was 8.6 million dollar, Belgium was 7.5 million dollar, Germany was 13.6 million dollar, Saudi Arab was 9.8 million dollar, UK was 23.8 million dollar & USA was 74.6 million dollar.

India export the Carpets to the major country Australia ,Canada, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, Spain ,Sweden ,UK and USA. The total amount of the carpet exported 1998-99 was 543.5 million dollar, whereas the total export of the Australia was 9.2 million dollar, Canada was 10.6 million dollar, France was 17.2 million dollar, Germany was 119.0 million dollar, Japan was 15.3 million dollar, UK was 23.3 million dollar & USA was 241.9 million dollar. It increases in the year 2005-06 total export was 852.6 million dollar, whereas the total export of the Australia was 18.1 million dollar, Canada was 17.0

million dollar, Germany was 156.1 million dollar, Italy was 22.0 million dollar, Spain was 21.0 million dollar, Sweden was 17.9 million dollar, UK was 53.3 million dollar & USA was 373.4 million dollar. In the year 2018-19 total export was 1481.9 million dollar, it decreases 1373.3 million dollar in 2019-20, whereas the total export of the Australia was 56.0 million dollar, Canada was 22.1 million dollar, France was 24.1 million dollar, Germany was 86.6 million dollar, Italy was 23.4 million dollar, Japan was 14.0 million dollar, Sweden was 26.4 million dollar, UK was 70.1 million dollar & USA was 774.8 million dollar.

Direction of foreign trade in India:-

Year	Direction of Foreign trade											
	US \$ million											
	1990-91		1991-92		1992-93		1994-95		1995-96		2000-01	
Group/Country	Exports	Imports	Exports	Imports	Exports	Imports	Exports	Imports	Exports	Imports	Exports	Imports
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
I. OECD countries	10248.8	13773	10337	10522.4	11209.8	12269.3	15443.8	14731.7	17705.1	19209.2	23473.6	20157.9
A. EU	4988.5	7067.1	4826.9	5665.5	5246.8	6603	7030.7	7114.6	8708.3	10303.2	10410.8	10510.2
1. Belgium	701.9	1514.6	666.9	1388	683.4	1826.8	988.4	1206.7	1120.4	1701.9	1470.6	2870
2. France	427.1	727	425.5	614.8	471.5	594.7	582.1	615.6	747	840.7	1020	640.8
3. Germany	1420.5	1935.6	1269.9	1559.4	1427	1656.9	1747.7	2187	1977.4	3145.1	1907.6	1759.6
4. Italy	558.1	608.2	580	448.1	622.1	524.3	857.9	741	1014	1064.3	1308.8	723.6
5. Netherlands	359.1	442.1	372.6	279.3	415.2	381.7	585.5	385.9	769	570.2	880.1	437.5
6. U.K.	1185.7	1612.8	1138.1	1201.9	1213.4	1417.4	1689.7	1559.1	2010.8	1917.7	2298.7	3167.9
B. North America	2829.6	3234.7	3109.7	2274.8	3707.1	2552.6	5287.5	3171.2	5825.8	4242.6	9961.6	3412.1
1. Canada	156.4	311.7	188.6	280.1	191.1	405.2	266.8	265.5	305.4	381.2	656.5	397.1
2. U.S.A	2673.2	2923	2921.1	1994.7	3515.9	2147.4	5020.7	2905.7	5520.4	3861.4	9305.1	3015
C. Asia and Oceania	1895.2	2689.5	1878.2	2023.3	1690.8	2326.8	2427.8	3031	2651.9	3551.8	2263.6	2984.3
1. Australia	179	815.7	202.5	586	223.2	838.1	346.4	915.2	375.7	1021.9	405.9	1062.8
2. Japan	1693.7	1808.3	1651.5	1369.3	1436.5	1427.9	2026.6	2039.9	2215.6	2467.6	1794.5	1842.2
D. Other OECD countries	535.6	781.7	522.2	558.9	565.1	786.9	697.7	1414.9	519.1	1111.6	837.6	3251.3
1. Switzerland	224.1	267.6	219	151	199.1	378.2	247.4	824.3	281.6	1020.5	437.7	3160.1
II. OPEC	1020.4	3924	1561.8	3821.1	1788.4	4776.7	2428.6	6050.1	3079	7644.4	4850	2688.8
1. Indonesia	109.4	81.1	146.7	66.9	138.5	60	277.7	321.1	662.4	461.1	399.8	910.2
2. Iran	78.5	567.1	122.5	582	114.4	397.7	156.8	536.5	155	598.2	227	211.2
3. Iraq	24.2	276.2	0	2.5	5.9	0	0.2	0	0.6	0	84	6.9
4. Kuwait	41.1	202.3	52.3	304.7	108.3	954.1	133.9	1480.2	135.5	1970.1	199.1	112.7
5. Saudi Arabia	233.2	1615.8	351.3	1442.5	407.5	1496	435.7	1569.6	482.3	2024.7	822.9	621.1
6. U.A.E.	438.9	1059.1	738.5	1247.5	814.3	1111.7	1265.9	1533	1428.3	1606.6	2597.5	659
III. Eastern Europe	3243.2	1882.2	1952.7	991.6	814.6	554.4	1057.1	967.6	1340	1673.8	1317.8	850.2
1. Romania	53.2	27.7	12.5	25.2	7.8	55	16.2	48.2	29.9	148.1	12.2	21.7
2. Russia	2928.6	1420.1	1640	728.5	606.4	254.6	807.1	504.4	1045	856.3	889	517.7
IV. Developing countries	1724.8	1725.8	1726.8	1727.8	1728.8	1729.8	6969.5	6970.5	6971.5	6972.5	6981.5	6982.5
A. Asia	2610	3371.9	3016.4	2872.4	3481.5	3203.7	5707.5	5091.7	7307.8	6426	10037.9	8459.5
a) SAARC	533.4	131.4	621.5	132.1	736.4	177.2	1215	176.7	1720.6	256.5	1928.5	465.8
1. Afghanistan	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.
2. Bangladesh	305.1	17.4	324	5.7	355.3	7.7	644.7	38.2	1049.1	85.9	935	80.4
3. Bhutan	2.2	0.8	1.2	0.5	2.2	1.2	11.1	18.3	17.2	34.7	1.1	21.1
4. Maldives	5.9	0	4.9	0	7.7	0.1	15.4	0.2	15.7	0.2	24.6	0.2
5. Nepal	48.3	45.4	77.1	28.5	72.5	24.8	120.1	36.6	160	49.1	140.8	255.1
6. Pakistan	41	47.1	40.1	85.9	50.8	129.7	57.2	52.7	76.8	45.1	186.8	64
7. Sri Lanka	130.9	20.5	174.2	11.4	248	13.8	366.6	30.7	401.7	41.4	640.1	45
b) Other Asian developing countries	2076.6	3240.5	2394.9	2740.2	2745.1	3026.5	4492.5	4914.9	5587.2	6169.4	8109.4	7993.7
1. China, People's Republic of	18.2	31	48.2	20.9	141.3	126	254.2	760.8	332.7	812	831.3	1502.2
2. Hong Kong	596.5	165.6	614.3	106.2	765	170.4	1517.4	287	1821.4	388	2640.9	852.1
3. South Korea	182.7	366.1	238.7	319.3	174.9	355.1	332.4	629.5	448.3	824.8	450.8	893.8
4. Malaysia	151	554.8	202.4	394.3	189.8	405.9	286.6	490.1	393.2	902.7	608.2	1176.8
5. Singapore	379.4	795.7	388.8	694.7	588.5	632.1	770.3	899.7	901.6	1091.9	877.1	1463.9
6. Thailand	247	64.5	198.6	48.5	253.6	58.3	406.6	171.6	472.9	169.7	530.1	337.9
B. Africa	393.6	572.7	441.3	840.5	566.5	756.4	877.5	1038.6	1512.7	1131.7	1956.4	1996.1
1. Benin	13.1	1.1	10.6	2.4	8.5	3.4	7.1	5.6	11.3	15.5	45.1	52.1
2. Egypt, Arab Republic of	98.9	43.9	81	66.7	114.2	88.2	119.8	228.3	164.3	72.6	357.5	38.8
3. Kenya	36	21.8	41.7	9.2	57.7	9.8	122.7	13.8	245.1	15	140.9	19
4. South Africa	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.
5. Sudan	21.5	1.7	15.8	0.1	14.2	1.7	16.4	13.5	30.6	15.3	97.8	8
6. Tanzania	29.6	34.5	48	34.4	70	36.7	65.8	54.3	81.4	96.3	102	59.5
7. Zambia	22.3	86	27.3	49.1	27.9	69.6	27.7	54.7	35.2	59.9	22.5	11.6
C. Latin American countries	95.2	545.8	129.5	361.1	188.1	320.8	384.5	772.1	377.9	587.4	1018.2	700.6
V. Others / unspecified	534.1	2.9	426.8	1.4	488.3	0.3	431.5	2.6	472.4	3	1906.3	15683.4
Total trade	18145.2	24072.5	17865.4	19410.5	18537.2	21881.6	26330.5	28654.4	31794.9	36675.3	44560.3	50536.5

Direction of Foreign trade

US \$ milio

Year	2004-05		2005-06		2007-08		2008-09		2009-10		2010-11	
Group/Country	Exports	Imports	Exports	Imports	Exports	Imports	Exports	Imports	Exports	Imports	Exports	Imports
1	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25
I. OECD countries	36494.8	39989.9	45836.8	51796.8	62642.85	87445.39	68452.3	96387	64141.6	94143	83350.65	113157
A. EU	17539.6	18713	22385	25151.3	32861	36810.35	38965.3	42274.6	35922.2	38348.3	46026.26	44505.49
1. Belgium	2509.7	4588.9	2871.2	4725.1	4208.35	4358.03	4415.7	5665.6	3742.8	6000	5782.64	8598.87
2. France	1680.9	1894.1	2079.6	4113.3	2596.61	6253.16	2995.4	4601.8	3793.9	4179.5	5199.02	3701.85
3. Germany	2826.2	4015.3	3586.1	6023.6	5116.39	9869.68	6347.6	11941.4	5402.9	10304	6745.26	11881.68
B. North America	14632.6	7777.1	18374.6	10374.6	21977.28	22991.48	22330.5	20897.6	20600.8	19083.5	26634.2	22079.91
1. Canada	866.8	775.7	1021.6	919.9	1265.26	1972.19	1358.2	2456.2	1121.5	2098.1	1347.6	2028.71
2. U.S.A	13765.7	7001.4	17353.1	9454.7	20712.03	21019.29	20972.3	18441.5	19479.4	16985.4	25286.59	20051.2
C. Asia and Oceania	2941.4	7187.6	3444.4	9225.6	5162.33	14496.26	4618.3	19194.2	5251.4	19585.4	6991.27	20049.49
1. Australia	720.2	3824.5	821.2	4947.9	1150.04	7836.94	1429.9	10979.1	1382.5	12364.7	1712.58	10795.6
2. Japan	2127.9	3235.1	2481.3	4061.1	3853.78	6323.24	3002.1	7790.9	3613.3	6722.5	5088.21	8627.54
D. Other OECD countries	1381.3	6312.2	1632.9	7045.3	2642.23	13147.31	2538.2	14020.6	2367.2	17125.8	3698.92	26522.15
1. Switzerland	540.9	5939.9	479.5	6555.8	614.98	9828.65	766.5	11458.9	586.9	14592.6	689.48	24743.88
II. OPEC	13207.4	10022.5	15242.2	11171.1	26670.92	76075.84	38872.8	97487.9	37648.6	92360.5	53502.01	124067.8
1. Indonesia	1332.6	2617.7	1380.2	3008.1	2159.12	4823.69	2517.3	6686	3078.3	8643.8	5689.94	9906.43
2. Iran	1231.4	410.2	1188.3	702.5	1948.51	10915.34	2514.5	12137	1856.4	11516	2488.25	10913.48
3. Iraq	131.2	1.1	155.9	2.1	271.06	6829.16	430.8	7454.4	477.1	7013.1	674.91	8993.62
4. Kuwait	421.4	305.9	513.7	461.9	681.78	7689.86	788.9	9392.6	782.1	8217.8	1853.95	10310.22
5. Saudi Arabia	1412.1	1301.2	1809.8	1632.3	3706.48	19401.13	4987.7	19513.1	3910.4	17002.2	4674.09	20379.63
6. U.A.E.	7347.9	4641.1	8591.8	4354.1	15626.91	13470.5	23966.3	23030.8	23891.2	19349.2	33770.28	32729.34
III. Eastern Europe	1780.2	2514.2	1980.4	3793.9	3383.57	5263.67	2012.6	6611.9	1793.3	6157.3	2813.54	5716.58
1. Romania	106	168.4	84.4	270.1	263.27	417.59	.	.	.	.	.	.
2. Russia	631.3	1322.7	733.1	2022.2	939.74	2468.49	1078	4302.2	977.4	3567.2	1691.4	3603.1
IV. Developing countries	31597.1	28604.2	39736.4	37890.5	69572.07	80647.95	68545.9	96858.5	70099.8	93716.9	96039.78	122125.7
A. Asia	24968.4	22581.3	30981.2	30450.6	51477.19	64141.63	51252.8	78679.6	53242.4	73936.7	70069.28	100104.7
a) SAARC	4440.7	950.2	5547.6	1413.3	9617.24	2111.4	8440.5	1796.9	8356.5	1651.8	11636.46	2170.16
1. Afghanistan	.	.	142.7	58.4	248.86	109.23	396.5	128.8	464.5	124.4	421.58	145.3
2. Bangladesh	1631.1	59.4	1664.4	127	2916.79	257	2460.9	308.4	2424.2	254.1	3237.86	445.85
3. Bhutan	84.6	71	99.2	88.8	86.65	194.38	110.6	149.6	118.2	152.4	175.92	201.34
4. Maldives	47.6	0.6	67.6	2	89.55	4.15	128.3	3.9	79.8	3.6	99.98	31.92
5. Nepal	743.1	345.8	860	379.9	1506.05	627.72	1555.4	490.4	1528.4	452.4	2166.43	513.35
6. Pakistan	521.1	95	689.2	179.6	1944.17	287.8	1420.3	362.8	1572.6	275	2031.3	332.28
7. Sri Lanka	1413.2	378.4	2024.7	577.7	2825.16	631.12	2368.5	353	2168.8	389.9	3503.4	500.13
b) Other Asian developing countries	20527.7	21631.1	25433.5	29037.2	41859.95	62030.23	42812.3	76882.8	44885.9	72284.8	58432.83	97934.49
1. China, People's Republic of	5615.9	7098	6759.1	10868	10828.78	27102.38	9275.6	32092.9	11532.5	30783.8	15454.33	43474.05
2. Hong Kong	3691.8	1730.1	4471.3	2207	6305.22	2699.18	6607.6	6464.5	7862.1	4703.9	10323.91	9399.18
3. South Korea	1041.7	3508.8	1827.2	4563.9	2851.8	6037.63	3990.5	8622.6	3399.2	8547.2	3723.37	10471.85
4. Malaysia	1084.1	2299	1161.9	2415.6	2567.59	6004.9	3431	7086.2	2846.3	5162.8	3879.77	6528.58
5. Singapore	4000.6	2651.4	5425.3	3353.8	7367.54	8117.64	8209.2	7514.5	7577.1	6454.7	9817.64	7143.09
6. Thailand	901.4	865.9	1075.3	1211.6	1807.91	2301	1896.8	2685.8	1734.2	2927.4	2270.78	4271.03
B. Africa	4478.6	3930.4	5699	4742	12494	10355.78	11576.1	12480.5	10417.4	12383.1	15880.43	13208.02
1. Benin	47.1	79.8	96.6	77.5	275.31	72	203.7	106.8	220.6	125.9	263.24	153.73
2. Egypt, Arab Republic of	444.7	152.6	672.4	220.4	1396.23	1982.77	1651.3	2123.2	1399.2	1693.8	1981.11	1351.52
3. Kenya	426.6	46.7	576.5	48.5	1578.73	86.51	1335.2	81.8	1452.8	79.3	2183.27	124.25
4. South Africa	984	2197.7	1526.9	2471.8	2657.37	3613.09	1955.6	5410	2055.4	5670	3925.3	7138.56
5. Sudan	317.4	22.9	294.6	32.6	407.77	431.49	482.2	400	459.9	473.3	488.15	612.92
6. Tanzania	173.9	131.7	243.5	119.8	587.31	164.48	1028.3	199.6	921	235.8	1470.81	325.15
7. Zambia	50.4	23	66.5	40.6	132.2	74.8	106.7	215.7	88.2	101.3	118.31	31.89
C. Latin American countries	2150.1	2092.5	3056.2	2697.9	5600.89	6150.55	5717	5698.4	6440.1	7397.1	10090.07	8813.01
V. Others / unspecified	456.5	30386.7	294.6	44513.5	862.6	2221.1	7411.4	6351	5068	1995.3	15430.22	4702.03
Total trade	83535.9	111517.4	103090.5	149165.7	163132.1	251654	185295	303696.3	178751.4	288372.9	251136.2	369769.1

Direction of Foreign trade												
US \$ million												
Year	2012-13		2013-14		2014-15		2015-16		2016-17		2017-18	
Group/Country	Export	Import	Export	Import	Export	Import	Export	Import	Export	Import	Export	Import
1	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37
ECD countries	102733.9	136751.9	108774	116358	109337	120373	100838	109912	104488	109265	119622	126729
A. EU	50320.34	53067.48	51742.1	49968.8	49511.7	49241.1	44590.7	43938.4	47308.8	42389.3	53603.7	47881.3
1. Belgium	5498.07	10062.99	6377.5	10752.5	5519.5	10805.9	5027.6	8256.1	5656.9	6624.6	6206.9	5993.4
2. France	4963.58	4047.61	5108.5	3692	4956.7	4416.1	4633.4	3730.3	5250	5707.8	4900.3	6524.2
3. Germany	7239.24	14353.15	7516.1	12932.8	7537.3	12787.9	7092.9	12088.4	7181.6	11583.7	8687.8	13295.7
4. Italy	4370.3	5152.55	5272.9	4156.7	5092.3	4231.8	4217.7	4072.2	4902.2	3895	5709.9	4706.9
5. Netherlands	10498.29	2925.87	7995.8	3139	6324.7	2802.9	4725.1	1859.9	5069.7	1895.7	6261.1	2512.6
6. U.K.	8641.32	6555.69	9779.5	6045.2	9319.7	5018.3	8828.5	5192.5	8530.1	3665	9690.9	4807.2
B. North America	38155.3	26765.27	41180.4	25654.1	44644.7	25564	42354.4	26015.4	44216.4	26439	50384.8	31339.6
1. Canada	2033.38	2504.53	2037.1	3148.4	2196	3749.4	2018.4	4234	2004.1	4131.5	2506.2	4728.5
2. U.S.A	36121.92	24260.74	39143.3	22505.7	42448.7	21814.6	40336	21781.4	42212.3	22307.4	47878.7	26611.1
Year	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18						
Group/Country	Export	Import	Export	Import	Export	Import	Export	Import	Export	Import	Export	Import
C. Asia and Oceania	8924.66	25196.3	9391.3	19918.3	8489.8	20970	8233.9	19296.6	7113.2	21413.6	9099.4	25610.9
1. Australia	2348.86	11999.16	2300.3	9822.7	2782.1	10247.2	3263	8898.8	2957.8	11154.5	4012.3	13993.8
2. Japan	6273.38	12510.23	6814.3	9481	5385.6	10131.4	4662.8	9850.2	3845.7	9754.6	4734.2	10973.5
D. Other OECD countries	5333.64	31722.83	6460	20817.1	6690.9	24598.1	5658.8	20661.8	5849.5	19022.8	6534.5	21897.3
1. Switzerland	1117.85	29830.99	1797	19311.5	1068.6	22133.2	977.2	19299.5	978.1	17248.7	1083.8	18923.1
II. OPEC	62839.31	189626.7	55708.8	162716	56392.3	137155	46272.8	90165.1	45200	92541.8	44302.5	109359
1. Indonesia	5332.77	14517.99	4850.4	14748.7	4043.3	15004.6	2819.5	13131.9	3488.1	13428	3963.8	16438.8
2. Iran	3366.4	11588.29	4971.5	10307.6	4175.1	8955	2781.5	6278.8	2379.6	10506.5	2652.4	11111.5
3. Iraq	1241.59	20089.95	918.1	18521.5	829.3	14247.7	1004.4	10837.6	1111.4	11707.9	1462.2	17615.8
4. Kuwait	1061.36	16599.94	1061.2	17154.1	1198.9	13382	1247.5	4969.7	1498	4462.3	1365.7	7165.7
5. Saudi Arabia	9780.08	33350.18	12219.3	36404.6	11161.4	28107.6	6381.5	20321.3	5110.3	19972.4	5410.7	22070
6. U.A.E.	36338.29	38428.99	30521.6	29020.6	33028.1	26139.9	30316.5	19445.7	31175.5	21509.8	28145.6	21740
III. Eastern Europe	3936.3	8803.37	3510.8	7922.3	3415.4	7716	2415.7	7095.6	2820.4	9329.3	3058.7	12914.5
1. Romania	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.	.
2. Russia	2329.74	4073.66	2121.3	3894.5	2097	4249.2	1587.8	4585	1937.1	5552.3	2135.4	8573.5
IV. Developing countries	124834.6	153965.2	134723	159043	136885	174904	110039	164860	120658	165750	133732	207174
A. Asia	85752.18	118796.5	95332.3	126170	93856.8	137506	76940.1	132457	88573.7	133352	99848.5	165832
a) SAARC	14759.41	2604.45	17504.5	2473.1	20493.5	2930.9	18594.2	2975	19222.1	2813.4	22926.3	3198
1. Afghanistan	472.12	114.74	474.4	208.8	422.6	261.9	526.6	307.9	506.3	292.9	709.7	433.8
2. Bangladesh	5122.36	630.17	6167.2	484.4	6449.9	621.4	6034.9	727.1	6820.1	701.7	8460.2	685.6
3. Bhutan	200.83	151.97	355.6	152.2	333.9	149.9	469	281.3	509.3	307.8	541.7	373.3
4. Maldives	122.44	7.44	106.1	4	152.4	4.3	179.1	4.3	197.8	9.2	217	5.7
5. Nepal	3028.59	527.06	3592.4	529.9	4573.9	639.9	3902.7	470.6	5453.6	445.1	6597.1	438.4
6. Pakistan	1837.09	512.55	2274.4	426.9	1857.2	497.3	2171.2	441	1821.9	454.5	1924.3	488.6
7. Sri Lanka	3975.96	660.53	4534.5	666.9	6703.7	756.2	5310.7	742.8	3913.2	602.2	4476.3	772.6
b) Other Asian developing countries	70992.77	116192	77827.8	123697	73363.2	134575	58346	129482	69351.6	130538	76922.2	162634
1. China, People's Republic of	13505.53	54313.78	14824.8	51036.2	11935.7	60413.2	9011.4	61708	10171.9	61283	13336.8	76271.7
2. Hong Kong	12292.82	8072.63	12732.4	7322.4	13599.9	5572	12092.3	6051.7	14047.2	8204.2	14690.3	10676.1
3. South Korea	4375.01	13445.94	4208.8	12471	4603	13529.1	3523.4	13047.1	4241.4	12585.4	4461	16361.8
4. Malaysia	4437.11	10444.12	4198	9230.2	5816.5	11117.7	3706.8	9083.8	5224.9	8933.6	5700.1	9011.6
5. Singapore	13587.8	7735.91	12510.7	6762.7	9809.4	7124.5	7719.8	7308.4	9564.6	7086.6	10202.1	7467
6. Thailand	3725.77	5490.34	3703.4	5340.4	3464.8	5865.9	2987.9	5510.2	3133.4	5415.4	3653.7	7134.6
B. Africa	24395.08	18700.12	26666.6	15224.7	28380.4	19778.5	21683.5	18643	20251.9	17976.4	21472.5	22673
1. Benin	479.04	255.87	764	167.6	497.9	222.1	427.3	275.7	447.9	207.4	479.7	223
2. Egypt, Arab Republic of	2886.9	2576.04	2562.3	2389	3025.6	1741.8	2337.7	1221.2	2067.4	1163.8	2392.3	1292.9
3. Kenya	3772.44	105.57	3882.3	126.6	4117.9	117.4	3025.9	127.5	2194.3	104.4	1974.6	72.6
4. South Africa	5139.69	8015.43	5074.4	6075.4	5302	6496.5	3588.1	5948.4	3546	5833.8	3825.2	6834.7
5. Sudan	756.94	133.63	863.1	436.4	882.5	569.7	782.4	149.2	748.7	245.1	822.7	452.1
6. Tanzania	2156.53	679.16	3400.9	724.5	2484.6	1089	1654.6	924.8	1783.6	948.5	1618.8	1029.7
7. Zambia	243.02	322.09	377.3	243.1	366.6	283.4	298.1	475.4	237.2	743.9	294.3	1095
C. Latin American countries	14687.3	16468.61	12724.3	17648.1	14647.7	17619.7	11415.7	13759.9	11832.7	14421.8	12411	18668.9
V. Others / unspecified	6226.47	2340	13101.6	17891.2	15014.3	17903.1	11713.8	14235.3	12069.9	15165.7	12705.3	19763.9
Total trade	300570.6	491487.2	314416	450214	310352	448033	262291	381008	275852	384357	303376	465578

Direction of Foreign trade						
Year	US \$ million					
	2018-19		2019-20		2020-21(Apr-Nov)	
Group/Country	Export	Import	Export	Import	Export	Import
1	38	39	40	41	42	43
I. OECD countries	128175	144875.7	124014.1	133137.4	59936	50517
A. EU	57203.1	58433.8	53737.4	51208.8	21318	21131
1. Belgium	6729.9	10469.2	5809.9	8879.4	2835	3867
2. France	5232.6	6665.7	5097.6	5955.2	2599	2352
3. Germany	8902.4	15161.1	8290.7	13351.3	4875	8186
4. Italy	5593.4	5292.4	4970.8	4489.1	2608	2229
5. Netherlands	8812.8	4062.8	8365.6	3390.7	3816	1880
6. U.K.	9309.3	7561.9	8737.6	6712.6	4585	2617
B. North America	55257.7	39064.9	55935.6	39542.8	33141	18214
1. Canada	2851.4	3515.4	2851.5	3880.3	1798	1909
2. U.S.A	52406.3	35549.5	53084	35662.5	31343	16305
C. Asia and Oceania	8762	26534.7	7750.1	22738.7	5008	10603
1. Australia	3520.4	13131.2	2851.8	9782.2	2468	4459
2. Japan	4861.7	12772.7	4519.8	12434.7	2540	6144
D. Other OECD countries	6952.2	20842.3	6591	19647	469	569
1. Switzerland	1186.7	18087.6	1200	16899.7	897	5837
II. OPEC	48780.5	136548.7	48180.2	123832.4	16653	40282
1. Indonesia	5275.6	15849.7	4123.9	15061.9	2671	7268
2. Iran	3511	13525.6	3373.6	1397.3	1290	188
3. Iraq	1788.7	22372.5	1878.2	23740.2	967	7582
4. Kuwait	1333.9	7430.8	1286.6	9573.8	614	2964
5. Saudi Arabia	5561.7	28479.2	6236.9	26857.4	1425	9204
6. U.A.E	30126.7	29785.3	28853.5	30256.6	9686	13094
III. Eastern Europe	3504	9465.6	4235.8	11964	1805	3309
1. Romania	.	.	.	.	204	103
2. Russia	2389.5	5840.4	3017.6	7093	1601	3206
IV. Developing countries	146523.5	223040.7	134049.2	204830.3	313600	474710
A. Asia	108513.8	179905.5	95866.9	168030.6	44093	71980
a) SAARC	25348.8	4363	21892.1	3834.6	11659	1889
1. Afghanistan	715.4	435.4	997.6	529.8	499	282
2. Bangladesh	9210.1	1044.8	8189	1263.8	4976	578
3. Bhutan	657.3	371	715.3	405.7	387	270
4. Maldives	223	20.4	226.6	6	119	9
5. Nepal	7766.2	508.1	7146.2	711.6	3411	386
6. Pakistan	2066.6	494.9	816.6	14	170	2
7. Sri Lanka	4710.2	1488.4	3800.9	903.7	2097	362
b) Other Asian developing countries	83165	175542.5	73974.8	164196	32434	70091
1. China, People's Republic of	16752.2	70319.6	16607.2	65259.4	13645	38819
2. Hong Kong	13002	17987	10967	16935.3	6374	9488
3. South Korea	4705.1	16759	4845.1	15659.7	2891	7127
4. Malaysia	6436.3	10818.6	6364.4	9782.3	3970	4416
5. Singapore	11572.3	16281.6	8922.6	14746.8	5510	7070
6. Thailand	4441.4	7441.8	4299.3	6788.4	44	3171
B. Africa	24166.8	24449.4	24318.9	21795.6	6780	5336
1. Benin	426.9	375.8	326.6	358.9	327	286
2. Egypt, Arab Republic of	2886.4	1677.8	2504.2	2031.4	1370	1199
3. Kenya	2071.8	137.1	2108.6	89.6	1209	65
4. South Africa	4067.2	6517.3	4108.1	6969.8	2168	3275
5. Sudan	920.9	742.6	1096.9	396.8	647	102
6. Tanzania	1704	903.5	1740.1	1023.5	891	408
7. Zambia	319.1	510.5	247.6	843.3	168	1
C. Latin American countries	13842.9	18685.8	13863.4	15004.2	8896.27	11285.7
V. Others / unspecified	14162	19196.3	14111	15847.5	1019.39	82.68
Total trade	330078.1	514078.4	313138.5	473995.2	256349.7	344959.7

Source:- Directorate General of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics & Ministry of Commerce and Industry.

In the pre independence period, the direction's of Indian foreign trade was not according to comparative cost advantage in India but by the colonial relation between India & Britain. In other words, it was Britain that decided from which countries India could Import its requirement & which countries it could export its product. Naturally, a major part of India's trade was either directly with Britten or its colonies. This pattern continued for some years after the independence, after the independence the new economic reforms comes in 1991, India developed the political & diplomatic contacts with the other country. Thus, new vistas for developing trade relation to the other countries opened up. The situation changed very much

since, & after the six decade of planning, the trading relation exhibit changes . The diversification in the trade relation in the trade relation has reduced the vulnerability of the economy to the outside political pressures.

Direction of Export & Import:-

For the purpose of studying direction's of trade, India's trading partner have been divided into five major groups in table OECD, OPEC, Eastern Europe, Developing Nations & Others / unspecified countries. The export & import of OECD group in 1990-91 was \$10248.8 million \$ import was \$13773.0 million, in 1994-95 OECD group total export was \$15443.8 million & import was \$14731.7 million, in 2005-06 it increases the export was \$45836.8 million & import was \$51796.8 million , in 2015-16 OECD group total export was \$100838.0 million & import was \$109912.0 million, in 2019-20 OECD group total export was \$124014.1 million & import was \$133137.4 million, in 2020-21(Apr-Nov) total export of the OECD group was \$59936.0 million & import was \$50517.0 million.

OECD country again derived European Union (EU), North America, Asian Ocean country. where the total export of the European Union (EU) in the year 1990-91 was \$4988.5 million & import was ` \$ 7067.1 million in this year the total export of Belgium was \$701.9 million & import was \$1514.6 million , total export of France was \$427.1 million & import was \$727.0 million ,total export of the Germany was \$1420.5 million & import was \$1935.6 million & the total export of the U.K was \$1185.7 million & import was \$1612.8 million ,EU country increases the export in the year 2000-01 it was \$10410.8 million & import was \$110510.2 million , in the year 2005-06 total export was \$22385.0 million& import was 25151.3 million, in 2010-11 It increases the total export was \$46026.26 million and import was \$44505.49 million in 2015-16 European Union total export was \$44590.7 million & import was \$143938.4 million, in 2017-18 total export was \$53603.7 million & import was \$47881.3 million , in 2019-20 total export was \$53737.4 million & import was \$51208.8 million , in 2020-21 total export was \$21318.0 million import was \$21131.0 million. Whereas the total export to the Germany in the year 2020-21 was \$4875.0 million & import was \$8186 million, total export of France was \$2599.0 million & import was \$2352.0 million, the share of Belgium in India export was \$2835.0 million & import was \$3867 million. The share of U.K in India's export & import was \$4585.0 million & \$2617.0 million.

The share of North America in Indian's export & import in the year 1990-91 was \$2829.6 million & 3234.7 million, in this year total export of Canada was \$156.4 million & import was \$311.7 million, in this year total export of U.S.A was \$2673.2 million & import was \$2923.0million, in 2000-01 total export of North America was \$9961.6 million & import was \$3412.1 million. In 2010-11 total export of North America was \$26634.2 million & import was \$22079.91 million, in 2019-20 total export of North America was \$55395.6 million & import was \$39542.8 million. In 2020-21 total export of North America was \$33141.0 million & import was \$18214.0 million, whereas the share of Canada Indian's export was \$1798.0 million & import was \$1909.0 million, the share of U.S.A Indian's export was \$31343.0 million & import was \$16305.0 million.

The share of Asia & Oceania countries in Indian's export & import in 1990-91 was \$1895.2 million & \$2689.5 million, in this year share of export & import Australia was \$179.0 million & \$815.7 million, in this year total export of Japan was \$1693.7 million & import was \$1808.3 million. In 2000-01 total export Asia & Oceania countries was \$2263.6 million & import was \$2984.3 million. In 2010-11 total export of Asia & Oceania countries was \$6991.27 million & import was \$20049.49 million. In 2019-20 total export of Asia & Oceania countries was \$7750.1 million& import was \$22738.7 million. In 2020-21 total export of Asia & Oceania countries was \$5008 million & import was \$10603 million, whereas the share of Australia in India's export was \$2468 million & import was \$4459 million. The share of Japan in India's export was \$2540 million & import was \$6144 million.

The share of other OECD countries in India's export & import in 1990-91 was \$535.6 million & \$781.7 million. In 2000-01 the share of other OECD countries India's export was \$ million & import was \$ million. In 2010-11 the share of other OECD countries India's export was \$8376.6 million & import was \$3251.3 million. In 2019-20 the share of other OECD countries India's export was \$6591 million & import was \$19647 million. In 2020-21 the share of other OECD countries India's export was \$649 million & import was \$569 million.

The share of OPEC country in India's export & import in 1990-91 was \$1020.4 million & \$3924 million. In this year the share of Indonesia in India's export was \$109.4 million & import was \$81.1 million, the share of Iran in India's export was \$78.5 million & import was \$567.1 million, the share of Iraq in India's export was \$24.2 million & import was \$276.2 million , the share of Kuwait in India's export was \$41.1 million & import was \$202.3 million, the share of Saudi Arabia in India's export was \$233.2 million & import was \$1615.8 million , the share of U.A.E in India's export was \$438.9 million & import was \$1059.1 million. IN 2010-11 OPEC country Indian's export was \$53502.01 million & import was \$124067.8 million. In 2019-20 OPEC country export was \$48180.2 million & import was \$123832.4 million , in 2020-21 OPEC country total export was \$16653 million & import was \$40282 million, In this year the share of Indonesia in India's export was \$2671 million & import was \$7268 million, the share of Iran in India's export was \$1290 million & import was \$188 million, the share of Iraq in India's export was \$967 million & import was \$7582 million , the share of Kuwait in India's export was \$614 million & import was \$2946 million, the share of Saudi Arabia in India's export was \$1425 million & import was \$9204 million , the share of U.A.E in India's export was \$9686 million & import was \$13094 million.

The share of Eastern Europe in India's export & import in 1990-91 was \$3243.2 million & \$1882.2 million. In this year the share of Romania in India's export was \$53.2 million & import was \$27.7 million, the share of Russia in India's export was \$2928.6 million & import was \$1420.1 million. In 2010-11 Eastern Europe total export was \$2813.54 million & import was \$5716.58 million, in 2019-20 Eastern Europe total export was \$4235.8 million & import was \$11964 million, in 2020-21 Eastern Europe total export was \$1805 million & import was \$3309 million. . In this year the share of Romania in India's export was \$204 million & import was \$103 million, the share of Russia in India's export was \$1601 million & import was \$3206 million.

The share of Developing countries India's export & import in 1990-91 was \$1724.8 million & \$725.8 million. In 2010-11 Developing countries total export was \$96039.78 million & import was \$122125.7 million, in 2019-20 Developing countries total export was \$134049.2 million & import was \$204830.3 million & in 2020-21 Developing countries total export was \$313600 million & import was \$474710 million.

The Developing countries divided the (a) Asia, (b) Africa & (c) Latin American countries again Asia countries are divided (1.) SAARC & (2.) Other Asian developing countries.

The share of Asia countries in India's export & import in 1990-91 was \$2610 million & \$3371.9 million. In 2010-11 Asia countries total export was \$70069.28 million & import was \$100104.7 million, in 2019-20 Asia countries total export was \$95866.9 million & import was \$168030.6 million, in 2020-21 Asia countries total export was \$44093 million & import was \$71980 million.

The share of SAARC countries in India's export & import in 1990-91 was \$533.4 million & \$131.4 million. In this year the share of Bangladesh in India's total export was \$305.1 million & import was \$17.4 million, the share of Bhutan in Indian's total export was \$2.2 million & import was \$0.8 million, the share of Maldives in Indian's total export was \$5.9 million & import was \$0.0 million, the share of Nepal in Indian's total export was \$48.3 million & import was \$45.4 million, the share of Pakistan in Indian's total export was \$41 million & import was \$47.1 million, the share of Sri Lanka in Indian's total export was \$130.9 million & import was \$20.5 million. In 2010-11 SAARC countries total export was \$11636.46 million & import was \$2170.16 million, in 2019-20 total export of SAARC countries was \$21892.1 million & import was \$3834.6 million , in 2020-21 SAARC countries total export was \$11659 million & import was \$1889 million, In this year share of Afghanistan in India's total export was \$499 million & import was \$282 million, the share of Bangladesh in India's total export was \$4976 million & import was \$578 million, the share of Bhutan in Indian's total export was \$387 million & import was \$270 million, the share of Maldives in Indian's total export was \$119 million & import was \$9 million, the share of Nepal in Indian's total export was \$3411 million & import was \$386 million, the share of Pakistan in Indian's total export was \$170 million & import was \$2 million, the share of Sri Lanka in Indian's total export was \$2097 million & import was \$362 million.

The share of other Asian developing countries in India's export & import in 1990-91 was \$2076.6 million & \$3240.5 million. In 2010-11 the share of other Asian developing countries total export was \$58432.83 million & import was \$97934.49 million, in 2019-20 the share of other Asian developing countries total export was \$73974.8 million & import was \$164196 million, in 2020-21 the share of other Asian developing countries total export was \$32434 million & import was \$70091 million.

The share of African countries in India's export & import in 1990-91 was \$393.6 million & \$572.7 million. In this year the share of Benin in Indian's export was \$13.1 million & import was \$1.1 million, the share of Egypt in Indian's export was \$98.9 million & import was \$43.9 million, the share of Kenya in Indian's export was \$36 million & import was \$21.8 million, the share of Tanzania in Indian's export was \$29.6 million & import was \$34.5 million, the share of Sudan in Indian's export was \$24.5 million & import was \$1.7 million, the share of Zambia in Indian's export was \$22.3 million & import was \$86 million,. In 2010-11 African countries total export was \$15880.43 million & import was \$13208.02 million, in 2019-20 African countries total export was \$24318.9 million & import was \$21795.6 million, in 2020-21 the share of African countries total export was \$6780 million & import was \$5336 million, In this year the share of Benin in Indian's export was \$327 million & import was \$286 million, the share of Egypt in Indian's export was \$1370 million & import was \$1199 million, the share of Kenya in Indian's export was \$1209 million & import was \$65 million, the share of South Africa in Indian's export was \$2168 million & import was \$3275 million, the share of Sudan in Indian's export was \$647 million & import was \$102 million, the share of Zambia in Indian's export was \$168 million & import was \$1.0 million, the share of Tanzania in Indian's export was \$891 million & import was \$408 million.

The share of Latin American countries in India's export & import in 1990-91 was \$95.2 million & \$545.8 million. In 2010-11 Latin American countries total export was \$10090.07 million & import was \$8813.01 million, in 2019-20 the share of Latin American countries total export was \$13863.4 million & import was \$15004.2 million, in 2020-21 the share of Latin American countries total export was \$8896.27 million & import was \$11285.7 million.

The share of other unspecified countries in India's export & import in 1990-91 was \$534.1 million & \$2.9 million. In 2010-11 Unspecified countries total export was \$15430.22 million & import was \$4702.03 million, in 2019-20 Unspecified

countries total export was \$14111 million & import was \$15847.5 million, in 2020-21 Unspecified countries total export was \$1019.39 million & import was \$82.68 million.

In 199-91 total export was \$18145.2 million & import was \$24072.5 million, in 2010-11 total export was \$251136.2 million & import was \$369769.1 million, in 2019-20 total export was \$313138.5 million & import was \$473995.2 million, in 2020-21 total export was \$256349.7 million & import was \$344959.7 million.

Balance of Payment in India:-

The balance of payment is the statement is essentially a double entry system of record of the transactions between the entities, government anatomies, or individuals of one country to another for a given period of time. All the transaction details are mentioned in the statement, giving the authority a clear vision of the flow of funds.

After all, if the items are included in the statement, then the inflow and the outflow of the fund should match. For a country, the balance of payment specifies whether the country has an excess or shortage of funds. It gives an indication of whether the country's export is more than its import or vice versa.

Types of Balance of Payment Accounts:-

The balance of payment is divided into three types:

1. Current account: This account scans all the incoming and outgoing of goods and services between countries. All the payments made for raw materials and constructed goods are covered under this account. Few other deliveries that are included in this category are from tourism, engineering, stocks, business services, transportation, and royalties from licenses and copyrights. All these combine together to make a BOP of a country.

2. Capital account: Capital transactions like purchase and sale of assets (non-financial) like lands and properties are monitored under this account. This account also records the flow of taxes, acquisition, and sale of fixed assets by immigrants moving into the different country. The shortage or excess in the current account is governed by the finance from the capital account and vice versa.

3. Finance account: The funds that flow to and from the other countries through investments like real estate, foreign direct investments, business enterprises, etc., are recorded in this account. This account calculates the foreign proprietor of domestic assets and domestic proprietor of foreign assets, and analyses if it is acquiring or selling more assets like stocks, gold, equity, etc.

Importance of Balance of Payment

A balance of payment is an essential document or transaction in the finance department as it gives the status of a country and its economy. The importance of the balance of payment can be calculated from the following points:

- It examines the transaction of all the exports and imports of goods and services for a given period.
- It helps the government to analyse the potential of a particular industry export growth and formulate policy to support that growth.
- It gives the government a broad perspective on a different range of import and export tariffs. The government then takes measures to increase and decrease the tax to discourage import and encourage export, respectively, and be self-sufficient.
- The balance of payment also indicates the government to detect the state of the economy, and plan expansion. Monetary and fiscal policies are established on the basis of balance of payment status of the country

The economic reform of 1991 brought the global transition in India. The transition towards a newer India, and a change in perspective of government towards the role of private players and markets in the economy. The Balance of Payment crisis followed by pledging of Gold reserves, taking loan from IMF and other structural adjustment programmed (sponsored by IMF and World Bank) were the initial steps towards the economic reforms that were launched. The BOP crisis was the result of decades of imprudent economic policies that India followed. The institutional arrangements of the economy, pre 1991, were adequate then but were eventually deteriorating the fiscal situation of the country. The role of fiscal policy in India's history is significant. In 1991, India ran into an unsustainable deficit in balance of payments. The country ran into large deficits for long time and as a result faced the balance of payment crisis.

To combat the crisis, the government took various fiscal, monetary, trade, finance and industrial measures. Since mid-1991, the Indian economy took a departure from the past policies prevailed post-independence. Liberalisation, Privatisation and Globalizations are the words that strike the most listening to the reforms that took place post crisis. India's economy paved itself into a new regime through new economic policy (NEP). It is necessary to know about the economic compulsion that leads to such crisis which leads to these reforms.

The fiscal deficit during 1990-91 was around 8.4 percent of GDP. The fiscal imbalances were marginally corrected by the budget 1991-92, which envisaged 2% reduction in the fiscal deficit. Year 1991 is marked as a landmark in India's history. The country faced its biggest economic crisis and used it as an opportunity to bring about significant changes in its economic policies. India saw a rapid transformation in its economy and a different perspective of India knows as New India came into existence since then. Indian BOP's present in the below table:-

Balance of Payment in India												
US \$ million												
Item/Year	2000-01			2001-02			2003-04			2004-05		
	Credit	Debit	Net									
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	11	12	13	14	15	16
A. Current account												
1. Merchandise	45452	57912	-	44703	56277	-	66285	80003	-	85206	118908	-
			12460			11574			13718			33702
2. Invisibles (a+b+c)	32267	22473	9794	36737	21763	14974	53508	25707	27801	69533	38301	31232
a) Services	16268	14576	1692	17140	13816	3324	26868	16724	10144	43249	27823	15426
i) Travel	3497	2804	693	3137	3014	123	5037	3602	1435	6666	5249	1417
ii) Transportation	2046	3558	-1512	2161	3467	-1306	3207	2328	879	4683	4539	144
iii) Insurance	270	223	47	288	280	8	419	363	56	870	722	148
iv) G.n.i.e.	651	319	332	518	283	235	240	212	28	401	411	-10
v) Miscellaneous	9804	7672	2132	11036	6772	4264	17965	10219	7746	30629	16902	13727
Software services	6341	591	5750	7556	672	6884	12800	476	12324	17700	800	16900
Business services	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5167	7318	-2151
Financial services	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	512	832	-320
Communication services	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1384	738	646
b) Transfers	13317	211	13106	16218	362	15856	22736	574	22162	21691	906	20785
i) Official	252	0	252	458	0	458	554	0	554	616	356	260
ii) Private	13065	211	12854	15760	362	15398	22182	574	21608	21075	550	20525
c) Income	2682	7686	-5004	3379	7585	-4206	3904	8409	-4505	4593	9572	-4979
i) Investment income	2554	7218	-4664	3254	7098	-3844	3774	7531	-3757	4124	8219	-4095
ii) Compensation of employees	128	468	-340	125	487	-362	130	878	-748	469	1353	-884
Total Current account (1+2)	77719	80385	-2666	81440	78040	3400	119793	105710	14083	154739	157209	-2470
B. Capital account												
1. Foreign investment (a+b)	17720	11858	5862	15488	8802	6686	32682	18938	13744	46934	33934	13000
a) Foreign direct investment (i+ii)	4101	829	3272	6229	1495	4734	4464	2076	2388	6087	2374	3713
i) In India	4031	0	4031	6130	5	6125	4322	0	4322	6052	65	5987
Equity	2399	0	2399	4096	5	4091	2229	0	2229	3779	65	3714
Reinvested earnings	1352	0	1352	1644	0	1644	1460	0	1460	1904	0	1904
Other Capital	280	0	280	390	0	390	633	0	633	369	0	369
ii) Abroad	70	829	-759	99	1490	-1391	142	2076	-1934	35	2309	-2274
Equity	70	414	-344	99	669	-570	142	1264	-1122	35	1672	-1637
Reinvested earnings	0	340	-340	0	700	-700	0	552	-552	0	248	-248
Other capital	0	75	-75	0	121	-121	0	260	-260	0	389	-389
b) Portfolio investment	13619	11029	2590	9259	7307	1952	28218	16862	11356	40847	31560	9287
i) In India	13619	10859	2760	9259	7238	2021	28218	16862	11356	40847	31536	9311
of which FII's	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	0	0
GDRs/ADRs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	0	0
ii) Abroad	0	170	-170	0	69	-69	0	0	0	0	24	-24
2. Loans (a+b+c)	23806	18542	5264	11601	12862	-1261	19667	24031	-4364	30287	19378	10909
a) External assistance	2941	2531	410	3352	2235	1117	3350	6208	-2858	3809	1886	1923
i) By India	0	17	-17	0	87	-87	24	128	-104	24	128	-104
ii) To India	2941	2514	427	3352	2148	1204	3326	6080	-2754	3785	1758	2027
b) Commercial borrowings	9621	5318	4303	2687	4272	-1585	5228	8153	-2925	9084	3890	5194
i) By India	0	5	-5	3	0	3	3	0	3	0	232	-232
ii) To India	9621	5313	4308	2684	4272	-1588	5225	8153	-2928	9084	3658	5426
c) Short term to India	11244	10693	551	5562	6355	-793	11089	9670	1419	17394	13602	3792
i) Suppliers' Credit >180 days & Buyers' Credit	-	-	-	0	0	0	-	-	-	0	0	0
ii) Suppliers' credit up to 180 days	-	-	-	0	0	0	-	-	-	0	0	0
3. Banking capital (a+b)	9744	11705	-1961	13870	11006	2864	19222	13189	6033	14581	10707	3874
a) Commercial Banks	9423	11305	-1882	13385	10725	2660	18887	12386	6501	14304	10325	3979
i) Assets	206	4380	-4174	1267	1711	-444	950	161	789	505	552	-47
ii) Liabilities	9217	6925	2292	12118	9014	3104	17937	12225	5712	13799	9773	4026
of which Non-Resident Deposits	8988	6672	2316	11435	8681	2754	14281	10639	3642	8071	9035	-964
b) Others	321	400	-79	485	281	204	335	803	-468	277	382	-105
4. Rupee debt service	0	617	-617	0	519	-519	0	376	-376	0	417	-417
5. Other capital	2856	2564	292	2298	1517	781	4314	2615	1699	6737	6081	656
Total capital account (1 to 5)	54126	45286	8840	43257	34706	8551	75885	59149	16736	98539	70517	28022
C. Errors & omissions	382	688	-306	405	599	-194	885	283	602	881	274	607
D. Overall balance (A+B+C)	132227	126359	5868	125102	113345	11757	196563	165142	31421	254159	228000	26159
E. Monetary movements (i+ii)	1448	7316	-5868	0	11757	-	0	31421	-	634	26793	-
i) I.M.F.	0	26	-26	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ii) Foreign exchange reserves (Increase- / Decrease+)	1448	7290	-5842	0	11757	-	0	31421	-	634	26793	-
						11757			31421			26159

Balance of Payment in India

Item/Year	US \$ million											
	2005-06			2007-08			2008-09			2010-11		
	Credit	Debit	Net									
1	17	18	19	23	24	25	26	27	28	32	33	34
A. Current account												
1. Merchandise	105152	157056	-51904	166163	257630	-91468	189001	308521	-	256159	383481	-
									119521			127322
2. Invisibles (a+b+c)	89687	47685	42002	148875	73145	75730	167818	76215	91603	190488	111218	79269
a) Services	57659	34489	23170	90342	51490	38853	105964	52046	53916	124636	80555	44081
i) Travel	7853	6638	1215	11349	9258	2091	10894	9427	1469	15793	11026	4768
ii) Transportation	6325	8337	-2012	10014	11514	-1501	11310	12819	-1510	14246	13880	366
iii) Insurance	1062	1116	-54	1639	1044	595	1422	1130	292	1945	1400	545
iv) G.n.i.e.	314	529	-215	330	376	-45	389	793	-404	535	820	-285
v) Miscellaneous	42105	17869	24236	67010	29298	37712	81948	27878	54069	92117	53430	38687
Software services	23600	1338	22262	40300	3358	36942	46300	2564	43736	53100	2194	50905
Business services	9307	7748	1559	16772	16553	220	18603	15317	3286	24050	27694	-3644
Financial services	1209	965	244	3217	3133	85	4428	2959	1469	6508	7483	-975
Communication services	1575	289	1286	2408	859	1549	2298	1088	1211	1562	1152	410
b) Transfers	25620	933	24687	44261	2315	41945	47547	2749	44798	56265	3125	53140
i) Official	669	475	194	753	514	239	645	413	231	647	631	16
ii) Private	24951	458	24493	43509	1801	41707	46903	2337	44566	55618	2494	53125
c) Income	6408	12263	-5855	14272	19340	-5068	14309	21418	-7110	9587	27538	-17952
i) Investment income	6229	11491	-5262	13811	18245	-4433	13483	20109	-6626	8471	25546	-17075
ii) Compensation of employees	179	772	-593	460	1096	-635	826	1309	-484	1116	1992	-876
Total Current account (1+2)	194839	204741	-9902	315037	330773	-15738	356820	384736	-27917	446647	494700	-48053
B. Capital account												
1. Foreign investment (a+b)	77298	61770	15528	271121	227795	43326	171660	163318	8342	292561	250435	42127
a) Foreign direct investment (i+ii)	9178	6144	3034	37322	21429	15893	43006	20634	22372	38609	26775	11834
i) In India	8962	61	8901	34844	116	34729	41902	165	41737	36047	7018	29029
Equity	5976	61	5915	26866	108	26756	32094	165	31929	22250	6514	15737
Reinvested earnings	2760	0	2760	7680	0	7680	9032	0	9032	13102	0	13102
Other Capital	226	0	226	300	8	292	776	0	776	695	504	191
ii) Abroad	216	6083	-5867	2477	21312	-18835	1103	20468	-19365	2562	19757	-17195
Equity	216	3982	-3766	2477	16898	-14421	1103	13283	-12180	2562	10610	-8048
Reinvested earnings	0	1092	-1092	0	1084	-1084	0	1084	-1084	0	1569	-1569
Other capital	0	1009	-1009	0	3330	-3330	0	6101	-6101	0	7578	-7578
b) Portfolio investment	68120	55626	12494	233800	206367	27433	128654	142685	-14031	253952	223660	30293
i) In India	68120	55626	12494	233564	206294	27271	128511	142366	-13855	253175	221704	31471
of which FII's	0	0	0	226621	206294	20327	127349	142366	-15017	251125	221704	29422
GDRs/ADRs	0	0	0	6645	0	6645	1162	0	1162	2049	0	2049
ii) Abroad	0	0	0	236	74	163	142	319	-177	777	1956	-1179
2. Loans (a+b+c)	39479	31570	7909	82192	41539	40653	62217	53902	8315	108781	79646	29135
a) External assistance	3631	1929	1702	4240	2127	2114	5231	2792	2439	7882	2941	4941
i) By India	24	88	-64	24	28	-4	72	416	-344	76	102	-26
ii) To India	3607	1841	1766	4217	2099	2118	5160	2375	2785	7806	2840	4967
b) Commercial borrowings	14343	11835	2508	30293	7684	22610	15222	7362	7860	24123	11963	12160
i) By India	0	251	-251	1592	1624	-32	1996	782	1214	1840	1513	328
ii) To India	14343	11584	2759	28701	6060	22641	13226	6578	6648	22283	10451	11832
c) Short term to India	21505	17806	3699	47658	31728	15930	41764	43750	-1986	76776	64742	12034
i) Suppliers' Credit >180 days & Buyers' Credit	19372	17647	1725	42641	31728	10913	38814	38352	462	72086	64742	7344
ii) Suppliers' credit up to 180 days	2133	159	1974	5017	0	5017	2950	5398	-2448	4690	0	4690
3. Banking capital (a+b)	21658	20285	1373	55814	44054	11759	65207	68453	-3246	92323	87361	4962
a) Commercial Banks	20586	20144	442	55736	43623	12111	65093	67868	-2775	90621	86189	4433
i) Assets	772	3947	-3175	19562	12668	6895	25823	28726	-2903	35369	38666	-3297
ii) Liabilities	19814	16197	3617	36172	30956	5217	39271	39142	129	55252	47523	7730
of which Non-Resident Deposits	17835	15046	2789	29401	29222	179	37148	32857	4291	49252	46014	3238
b) Others	1072	141	931	79	432	-354	113	585	-472	1702	1172	529
4. Rupee debt service	0	572	-572	0	121	-121	0	101	-101	0	68	-68
5. Other capital	5941	4709	1232	29230	18261	10969	16684	22602	-5918	9995	22411	-12416
Total capital account (1 to 5)	144376	118906	25470	438357	331772	106585	315771	308375	7396	503660	439921	63740
C. Errors & omissions	626	1142	-516	1317	0	1317	1456	1016	440	0	2636	-2636
D. Overall balance (A+B+C)	339841	324789	15052	754709	662546	92164	674045	694125	-20080	949212	936162	13050
E. Monetary movements (i+ii)	4672	19724	-15052	0	92164	-92164	20080	0	20080	0	13050	-13050
i) I.M.F.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ii) Foreign exchange reserves (Increase- / Decrease+)	4672	19724	-15052	0	92164	-92164	20080	0	20080	0	13050	-13050

Balance of Payment in India												
											US \$ million	
	2011-12			2014-15			2015-16			2016-17		
Item/Year	Credit	Debit	Net	Credit	Debit	Net	Credit	Debit	Net	Credit	Debit	Net
1	35	36	37	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52
A. Current account												
1. Merchandise	309774	499533	-189759	316544.8	461484.5	-144940	266365.3	396444.1	-130079	280138	392580.5	-112442
2. Invisibles (a+b+c)	219229	107625	111604	241645.2	123564.1	118081.1	235044.4	127116.3	107928.1	240978.1	143831.2	97146.87
a) Services	142325	78227	64098	158107.5	81578.31	76529.18	154311.1	84634.67	69676.48	163123.5	95668.25	67455.23
i) Travel	18462	13762	4699	20334.28	15306.26	5028.027	21268.04	14791.83	6476.208	23243.68	16426.77	6816.916
ii) Transportation	18241	16382	1859	17485.23	16176.73	1308.499	14003.96	15080.36	-1076.4	15851.38	14131.92	1719.456
iii) Insurance	2632	1497	1134	2202.291	1118.513	1083.777	2002.474	1150.865	851.6089	2205.927	1495.519	710.4085
iv) G.n.i.e.	478	780	-302	543.1857	960.7495	-417.564	578.653	869.2595	-290.606	588.0576	599.5566	-11.499
v) Miscellaneous	102513	45806	56707	117542.5	48016.05	69526.44	116458	52742.35	63715.68	121234.4	63014.49	58219.95
Software services	62212	1256	60957	73108.15	2707.81	70400.34	74153.11	2699.17	71453.94	73650.6	3586.908	70063.69
Business services	25910	26788	-878	28421.86	27644.1	777.7665	28994.02	31095.03	-2101.01	32945.99	32253.6	692.3913
Financial services	5967	7984	-2018	5660.866	3579.648	2081.218	4944.25	3134.956	1809.294	5098.792	5852.487	-753.694
Communication services	1600	1557	43	1997.172	1022.609	974.5627	2171.124	1001.376	1169.748	2374.92	910.3814	1464.538
b) Transfers	66761	3267	63494	70140.6	4448.636	65691.96	66030.24	3403.313	62626.92	61563.8	5580.706	55983.09
i) Official	632	607	25	321.6487	893.2865	-571.638	438.1337	950.353	-512.219	267.8107	857.3153	-589.505
ii) Private	66129	2660	63469	69818.95	3555.35	66263.6	65592.1	2452.96	63139.14	61295.99	4723.391	56572.6
c) Income	10144	26131	-15988	13397.13	37537.17	-24140	14703.02	39078.3	-24375.3	16290.8	42582.25	-26291.4
i) Investment income	7676	24141	-16465	9839.032	34800.56	-24961.5	11102.9	36840.24	-25737.3	12353.45	40049.98	-27696.5
ii) Compensation of employees	2468	1991	477	3558.099	2736.609	821.4895	3600.117	2238.06	1362.057	3937.344	2532.268	1405.076
Total Current account (1+2)	529003	607158	-78155	558190	585048.6	-26858.6	501409.7	523560.3	-22150.6	521116.1	536411.7	-15295.6
B. Capital account												
1. Foreign investment (a+b)	234618	195387	39231	308556.5	235100.3	73456.14	276433	244541.8	31891.2	310522.4	267298.6	43223.75
a) Foreign direct investment (i+ii)	49007	26947	22061	51795.72	20544.34	31251.38	59878.21	23857.22	36020.99	70784.26	35172.08	35612.18
i) In India	46552	13599	32952	45147.02	9864.364	35282.65	55558.57	10652.02	44906.54	60220.01	18005.11	42214.89
Equity	35852	13019	22833	31910.08	9612.359	22297.72	41111.66	10524.34	30587.32	44700.99	17317.89	27383.1
Reinvested earnings	8205	0	8205	9987.933	-	9987.933	10412.91	0	10412.91	12343.17	-	12343.17
Other Capital	2494	580	1914	3249	252.0049	2996.995	4034	127.6829	3906.317	3175.84	687.219	2488.621
ii) Abroad	2456	13348	-10892	6648.703	10679.97	-4031.27	4319.642	13205.19	-8885.55	10564.26	17166.97	-6602.71
Equity	2456	6330	-3874	6648.703	3867.183	2781.52	4319.642	6485.983	-2166.34	10564.26	9792.03	772.2264
Reinvested earnings	0	1208	-1208	0	3337.09	-3337.09	0	3337.09	-3337.09	0	2925.43	-2925.43
Other capital	0	5809	-5809	0	3475.7	-3475.7	0	3382.12	-3382.12	0	4449.51	-4449.51
b) Portfolio investment	185610	168440	17170	256760.8	214556	42204.76	216554.7	220684.5	-4129.79	239738.1	232126.5	7611.565
i) In India	184747	167338	17409	256047.5	213854.2	42193.35	215706.9	219349.5	-3642.62	237513.9	229748.3	7765.61
of which FII	184150	167338	16812	254776.8	213854.2	40922.63	215333.5	219349.5	-4015.97	237513.9	229748.3	7765.61
GDRs/ADRs	597	0	597	1270.72	0	1270.72	373.355	0	373.355	0	0	0
ii) Abroad	863	1102	-239	713.2518	701.8416	11.41017	847.8899	1335.065	-487.175	2224.217	2378.261	-154.045
2. Loans (a+b+c)	140990	121683	19307	123354.9	120170.4	3184.498	120322.9	124957.3	-4634.44	120532.1	118153.2	2378.888
a) External assistance	5646	3350	2296	5779.667	4054.281	1725.386	6123.298	4618.592	1504.705	6494.789	4481.576	2013.214
i) By India	70	226	-157	60.23436	387.5377	-327.303	58.41826	519.4737	-461.055	57.86313	230.7994	-172.936
ii) To India	5576	3124	2452	5719.432	3666.743	2052.689	6064.88	4099.119	1965.761	6436.926	4250.776	2186.15
b) Commercial borrowings	32590	22247	10344	27846.52	26276.3	1570.219	24156.7	28685.97	-4529.27	22584.46	28686.04	-6101.58
i) By India	3669	2465	1204	1610.52	272.6607	1337.859	3296.699	1970.423	1326.276	4532.302	3043.805	1488.497
ii) To India	28922	19782	9140	26236	26003.64	232.36	20860	26715.55	-5855.55	18052.16	25642.24	-7590.08
c) Short term to India	102754	96087	6668	89728.73	89839.84	-111.107	90042.86	91652.73	-1609.87	91452.88	84985.62	6467.257
i) Suppliers' Credit >180 days & Buyers' Credit	99247	95412	3836	87643.14	89229.84	-1586.69	87536.88	89734.52	-2197.64	89744.88	84796.92	4947.957
ii) Suppliers' credit up to 180 days	3507	675	2832	2085.586	610	1475.586	2505.981	1918.21	587.7712	1708	188.7	1519.3
3. Banking capital (a+b)	89904	73678	16226	90093.64	78476.12	11617.52	88883.94	78254.36	10629.59	83669.26	100284.9	-16615.7
a) Commercial Banks	89478	73429	16049	88360.84	78476.12	9884.714	88848.05	77975.11	10872.94	83380.97	100282.5	-16901.6
i) Assets	13635	14228	-592	17031.4	18545.99	-1514.59	19067.51	22776.27	-3708.76	29654.3	28883.69	770.6129
ii) Liabilities	75842	59201	16641	71329.44	59930.13	11399.3	69780.54	55198.84	14581.7	53726.67	71398.84	-17672.2
of which Non-Resident Deposits	64287	52370	11918	63262.02	49205.48	14056.55	59987.84	43936.32	16051.52	47639.45	60006.22	-12366.8
b) Others	426	249	177	1732.805	0.000431	1732.805	35.89875	279.2482	-243.349	288.2876	2.40579	285.8818
4. Rupee debt service	0	79	-79	0	80.78	-80.78	0	73.15073	-73.1507	0	99.34	-99.34
5. Other capital	13296	20224	-6929	28914.41	27805.68	1108.731	24418.59	21103.42	3315.17	35937.14	28342.74	7594.407
Total capital account (1 to 5)	478808	411052	67755	550919.5	461633.3	89286.11	510058.3	468930	41128.37	550660.9	514178.9	36482.03
C. Errors & omissions	0	2432	-2432	1088.835	2109.963	-1021.13	420.3225	1493.421	-1073.1	1220.654	856.7569	363.8967
D. Overall balance (A+B+C)	1007811	1020643	-12831	1110198	1048792	61406.35	1011888	993983.7	17904.68	1072998	1051447	21550.34
E. Monetary movements (i+ii)	12831	0	12831	0	61406.35	-61406.4	856.182	18760.86	-17904.7	1241.865	22792.2	-21550.3
i) I.M.F.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ii) Foreign exchange reserves (Increase- / Decrease+)	12831	0	12831	0	61406.35	-61406.4	856.182	18760.86	-17904.7	1241.865	22792.2	-21550.3

Balance of Payment in India												
US \$ million												
	2017-18			2018-19			2019-20			2020-21 Apr-Sep(P)		
Item/Year	Credit	Debit	Net	Credit	Debit	Net	Credit	Debit	Net	Credit	Debit	Net
1	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64
A. Current account												
1. Merchandise	308970	469006	-	337237	517519	-	320431	477937	-	127942.6	153494.7	-25552.2
			160036			180283			157506			
2. Invisibles (a+b+c)	283406	172087	111319	306483	183457	123026	321712	188862	132850	145477.9	85207.87	60270.05
a) Services	195089	117527	77562	208000	126060	81941	213191	128269	84922	96710.96	55037.25	41673.71
i) Travel	28355	19516	8839	28441	21704	6737	29998	22011	7987	3868.162	5493.975	-1625.81
ii) Transportation	17441	17608	-166	19464	20529	-1065	20988	24285	-3297	10277.29	8975.296	1301.997
iii) Insurance	2506	1700	806	2661	1790	871	2431	1738	692	1154.668	915.4751	239.1932
iv) G.n.i.e.	664	794	-130	610	1114	-504	659	1107	-448	292.4059	520.0782	-227.672
v) Miscellaneous	146122	77909	68213	156824	80922	75902	159115	79128	79987	81118.43	39132.42	41986
Software services	77326	5139	72186	83466	5812	77654	93102	8459	84643	47690.41	4617.801	43072.61
Business services	37346	36630	715	39112	40413	-1301	45716	46881	-1165	22906.53	23893.18	-986.647
Financial services	5164	5537	-373	4858	3486	1372	4734	2919	1814	2012.68	2168.545	-155.864
Communication services	2098	954	1144	2561	1130	1431	2723	1296	1426	1367.521	659.0381	708.4831
b) Transfers	69455	7017	62438	76643	6697	69946	83356	8147	75208	38644.28	3260.579	35383.7
i) Official	326	837	-511	247	902	-655	161	1170	-1009	63.21345	515.8367	-452.623
ii) Private	69129	6180	62949	76396	5795	70601	83195	6977	76217	38581.07	2744.743	35836.32
c) Income	18862	47542	-28681	21839	50700	-28861	25166	52446	-27281	10122.68	26910.04	-16787.4
i) Investment income	14404	45243	-30839	17101	48321	-31219	19542	49752	-30210	7313.764	25540.56	-18226.8
ii) Compensation of employees	4457	2299	2158	4738	2380	2358	5623	2694	2929	2808.915	1369.474	1439.44
Total Current account (1+2)	592376	641093	-48717	643719	700976	-57256	642143	666799	-24656	273420.5	238702.6	34717.89
B. Capital account												
1. Foreign investment (a+b)	359546	307145	52401	321776	291682	30094	368534	324118	44417	171803.2	140381.3	31421.91
a) Foreign direct investment (i+ii)	64461	34175	30286	64846	34134	30712	77794	34780	43013	42495.51	18712.92	23782.59
i) In India	60974	21544	39431	62001	18699	43302	74390	18384	56006	41377.35	12184.91	29192.44
Equity	45521	21325	24196	45055	18452	26604	51734	18212	33522	31067.28	12169.54	18897.74
Reinvested earnings	12542	-	12542	13672	-	13672	14175	-	14175	7813.206	0	7813.206
Other Capital	2911	219	2692	3274	247	3027	8482	173	8309	2496.86	15.3681	2481.492
ii) Abroad	3487	12632	-9144	2845	15435	-12590	3403	16396	-12993	1118.16	6528.013	-5409.85
Equity	3487	5254	-1767	2845	7201	-4356	3403	7572	-4168	1118.16	2607.48	-1489.32
Reinvested earnings	0	2853	-2853	0	3032	-3032	0	3151	-3151	0	1615.623	-1615.62
Other capital	0	4525	-4525	0	5202	-5202	0	5674	-5674	0	2304.91	-2304.91
b) Portfolio investment	295084	272969	22115	256930	257548	-618	290741	289337	1403	129307.7	121668.4	7639.32
i) In India	293529	271364	22165	253714	254118	-405	284128	283576	552	128288.9	119455.6	8833.264
of which FII	293529	271364	22165	251894	254118	-2225	284128	283576	552	128288.9	119455.6	8833.264
GDRs/ADRs	0	0	0	1820	0	1820	0	0	0	0	0	0
ii) Abroad	1556	1605	-50	3216	3429	-213	6612	5761	851	1018.828	2212.772	-1193.94
2. Loans (a+b+c)	147111	130451	16660	94099	78249	15850	94239	68553	25686	38883.3	40598.17	-1714.87
a) External assistance	7718	4774	2944	8606	5192	3413	9330	5579	3751	8935.364	2975.265	5960.099
i) By India	55	124	-69	47	120	-73	8	113	-105	3.061865	55.39845	-52.3366
ii) To India	7663	4650	3013	8559	5073	3487	9323	5466	3856	8932.302	2919.867	6012.436
b) Commercial borrowings	38879	39062	-183	42162	31746	10416	46149	23188	22960	12268.92	17930.9	-5661.97
i) By India	14292	13676	616	13862	13215	647	6843	5563	1280	1210.785	2007.898	-797.114
ii) To India	24587	25386	-799	28300	18531	9769	39305	17625	21680	11058.14	15923	-4864.86
c) Short term to India	100514	86614	13900	43332	41311	2021	38759	39785	-1026	17679.01	19692	-2013
i) Suppliers' Credit >180 days & Buyers' Credit	96756	86614	10142	27490	41311	-13821	37359	38233	-873	17679.01	18181.82	-502.808
ii) Suppliers' credit up to 180 days	3758	0	3758	15842	0	15842	1400	1552	-152	0	1510.188	-1510.19
3. Banking capital (a+b)	95673	79483	16190	92798	85365	7433	84716	90031	-5315	36539.92	45485.54	-8945.62
a) Commercial Banks	95255	79064	16191	91791	84664	7127	84603	89255	-4653	36526.63	44718.15	-8191.52
i) Assets	25532	25834	-302	22936	29633	-6697	26819	31225	-4406	14160.52	21129.73	-6969.21
ii) Liabilities	69723	53230	16493	68855	55031	13824	57784	58030	-246	22366.1	23588.41	-1222.31
of which Non-Resident Deposits	59544	49868	9676	59251	48864	10387	55490	46863	8627	20964.1	16029.76	4934.338
b) Others	417	419	-1	1007	702	306	113	776	-663	13.29404	767.3902	-754.096
4. Rupee debt service	0	75	-75	0	31	-31	0	69	-69	0	57.19964	-57.1996
5. Other capital	41282	35069	6213	33809	32751	1057	62549	44087	18462	33243.89	37475.27	-4231.38
Total capital account (1 to 5)	643612	552222	91390	542482	488080	54403	610038	526858	83180	280470.3	263997.5	16472.84
C. Errors & omissions	1900	998	902	582	1068	-486	1856	882	974	637.314	413.3857	223.9284
D. Overall balance (A+B+C)	1237887	1194313	43574	1186784	1190123	-3339	1254037	1194539	59498	554528.1	503113.4	51414.66
E. Monetary movements (i+ii)	0	43574	-43574	17502	14162	3339	0	59498	-59498	0	51414.66	-51414.7
i) I.M.F.	0	0	0	0	0	0	-	-	-	0	0	0
ii) Foreign exchange reserves (Increase- / Decrease+)	0	43574	-43574	17502	14162	3339	0	59498	-59498	0	51414.66	-51414.7

Source:- Reserve Bank of India(RBI)

In 200-01 total current account credit was \$77719 million, debit was \$80385 million & net was \$-2666 million, whereas total credit of merchandise was \$45452 million , debit was \$57912 million & net was \$-12460 million, in this year total credit of invisible item was \$32267 million , debit was \$22473 million & net was \$9794 million, whereas services credit was \$16268 million , debit was \$14576 million & net was \$1692 million, Transfers credit was \$13317 million , debit was \$211 million & net was \$13106 million, income credit was \$2682 million , debit was \$7686 million & net was \$-5004 million. In 2004-05 total current account credit was \$154739 million, debit was \$157209 million & net was \$-2470 million, whereas total credit of merchandise was \$85206 million , debit was \$118908 million & net was \$-33702 million, in this year total credit of invisible item was \$69533 million , debit was \$38301 million & net was \$31232 million, whereas services credit was \$43249 million , debit was \$27823 million & net was \$15426 million, Transfers credit was \$21691 million , debit was \$906 million & net was \$20785 million, income credit was \$4593 million , debit was \$9572 million & net was \$-4979 million. In 2010-11 total current account credit was \$446647 million, debit was \$494700 million & net was \$-48053 million, whereas total credit of merchandise was \$256159 million , debit was \$383481 million & net was \$-127322 million, in this year total credit of invisible item was \$190488 million , debit was \$111218 million & net was \$79269 million, whereas services credit was \$124636 million , debit was \$80555 million & net was \$44081 million, Transfers credit was \$56265 million , debit was \$3125 million & net was \$53140 million, income credit was \$9587 million , debit was \$27538 million & net was \$-17952 million. In 2016-17 total current account credit was \$521116.1 million, debit was \$536411.7 million & net was \$-15295.6 million, whereas total credit of merchandise was \$280138 million , debit was \$392580.5 million & net was \$-112442 million, in this year total credit of invisible item was \$240978.1 million , debit was \$143831.2 million & net was \$97146.87 million, whereas services credit was \$163123.5 million , debit was \$95668.25 million & net was \$67455.23 million, Transfers credit was \$61563.8 million , debit was \$5580.70 million & net was \$55983.09 million, income credit was \$16290.8 million , debit was \$42582.25 million & net was \$-26291.4 million. In 2019-20 total current account credit was \$642143 million, debit was \$666799 million & net was \$-24656 million, whereas total credit of merchandise was \$320431 million , debit was \$477937 million & net was \$-157506 million, in this year total credit of invisible item was \$321712 million , debit was \$188862 million & net was \$132850 million, whereas services credit was \$213191 million , debit was \$128269 million & net was \$84922 million, Transfers credit was \$83356 million , debit was \$8147 million & net was \$75208 million, income credit was \$25166 million , debit was \$52446 million & net was \$-27281 million. In 2020-21(Apr-Sep) total current account credit was \$273420.5 million, debit was \$238702.6 million & net was \$34717.89 million, whereas total credit of merchandise was \$127942.6 million , debit was \$153494.7 million & net was \$-25552.2 million, in this year total credit of invisible item was \$145477.9 million , debit was \$85207.87 million & net was \$60270.05 million, whereas services credit was \$96710.96 million , debit was \$55037.25 million & net was \$41673.71 million, Transfers credit was \$38644.28 million , debit was \$3260.57 million & net was \$35383.7 million, income credit was \$10122.68 million , debit was \$26910.04 million & net was \$-16787.4 million.

In 2000-01 total capital account credit was \$54126 million, debit was \$45286 million & net was \$8840 million, whereas the total credit of Foreign investment was \$1720 million, debit was \$11858 million & net was \$5862 million, foreign direct investment the total credit was \$4101 million, debit was \$829 million & net was \$3272 million , in India total credit of Foreign direct investment was \$4031 million, debit was \$0.0 million & net was \$4031 million, in Abroad total credit of Foreign direct investment was \$70 million, debit was \$829 million & net was \$-759 million, Portfolio investment total credit of investment was \$13619 million, debit was \$11029 million & net was \$2590 million , in India total credit of Foreign Portfolio investment was \$13619 million, debit was \$10859 million & net was \$2760 million, in Abroad total credit of Foreign Portfolio investment was \$0.0 million, debit was \$170 million & net was \$-170 million , total amount of loans credit was \$23806 million , debit was \$18542 million & net was \$5264 million, whereas total amount of External assistance credit was \$2941 million , debit was \$2531 million & net was \$410 million, total amount of commercial borrowing credit was \$9621 million , debit was \$5318 million & net was \$4303 million, total amount of Short term credit to India total credit was \$11244 million , debit was \$10693 million & net was \$551 million. The total amount of banking capital credit was \$9744 million, debit was \$11705 million & net was \$-1961 million, whereas total amount of commercial bank credit was \$9423 million, debit was \$11305 million & net was \$-1882 million & other banking capital credit was \$321 million, debit was \$400 million & net was \$-79 million. The rupee debt services total amount credit was \$0.0 million, debit was \$617 million & net was \$-617 million. Other capital credit was \$2856 million, debit was \$2564 million & net was \$292 million. In 2011-12 total capital account credit was \$478808 million, debit was \$411052 million & net was \$67755 million, whereas the total credit of Foreign investment was \$234618 million, debit was \$195387 million & net was \$39231 million, foreign direct investment the total credit was \$49007 million, debit was \$26947 million & net was \$22061 million , in India total credit of Foreign direct investment was \$46552 million, debit was \$13599 million & net was \$32952 million, in Abroad total credit of Foreign direct investment was \$2456 million, debit was \$13348 million & net was \$-10892 million, Portfolio investment total credit of investment was \$185610 million, debit was \$168440 million & net was \$17170 million , in India total credit of Foreign Portfolio investment was \$184747 million, debit was \$167338 million & net was \$17409 million, in Abroad total credit of Foreign Portfolio investment was \$863 million, debit was \$1102 million & net was \$-239 million , total amount of loans credit was \$140990 million , debit was \$121683 million & net was \$19307 million, whereas total amount of External assistance credit was \$5646 million , debit was \$3350 million & net was \$2296 million, total amount of commercial borrowing credit was \$32590 million , debit was \$22247 million & net was \$10344 million, total amount of Short term credit to India total credit was \$102754 million , debit was \$96087 million & net was \$6668 million. The total amount of banking capital credit was \$89904 million, debit was \$73678 million & net was \$16226 million, whereas total amount of

commercial bank credit was \$89478 million, debit was \$73429 million & net was \$16049 million & other banking capital credit was \$426 million ,debit was \$249 million & net was \$177 million. The rupee debt services total amount credit was \$0.0 million, debit was \$79 million & net was \$-79 million. Other capital credit was \$13296 million, debit was \$20224 million & net was \$6929 million. In 2019-20 total capital account credit was \$610038 million, debit was \$526858 million & net was \$83180 million, whereas the total credit of Foreign investment was \$368534 million, debit was \$324118 million & net was \$44417 million, foreign direct investment the total credit was \$77794 million, debit was \$34780 million & net was \$43013 million , in India total credit of Foreign direct investment was \$74390 million, debit was \$18384 million & net was \$56006 million, in Abroad total credit of Foreign direct investment was \$3403 million, debit was \$16396 million & net was \$-12993 million, Portfolio investment total credit of investment was \$290741 million, debit was \$289337 million & net was \$1403 million , in India total credit of Foreign Portfolio investment was \$284128 million, debit was \$283576 million & net was \$552 million, in Abroad total credit of Foreign Portfolio investment was \$6612 million, debit was \$5716 million & net was \$851 million , total amount of loans credit was \$94239 million , debit was \$68553 million & net was \$25686 million, whereas total amount of External assistance credit was \$9330 million , debit was \$5579 million & net was \$3751 million, total amount of commercial borrowing credit was \$46149 million , debit was \$23188 million & net was \$22960 million, total amount of Short term credit to India total credit was \$38759 million , debit was \$39785 million & net was \$-1026 million. The total amount of banking capital credit was \$84716 million , debit was \$90031 million & net was \$-5315 million, whereas total amount of commercial bank credit was \$84603 million, debit was \$89255 million & net was \$-4653 million & other banking capital credit was \$113 million ,debit was \$776 million & net was \$-663 million. The rupee debt services total amount credit was \$0.0 million , debit was \$96 million & net was \$-69 million. Other capital credit was \$62549 million, debit was \$44087 million & net was \$18462 million. In 2020-21 (Apr-Nov) total capital account credit was \$280470.3 million, debit was \$263997.5 million & net was \$16472.84 million, whereas the total credit of Foreign investment was \$171803.2 million, debit was \$140381.3 million & net was \$31421.91 million, foreign direct investment the total credit was \$42495.51 million, debit was \$18712.92 million & net was \$23782.59 million , in India total credit of Foreign direct investment was \$41373.35 million, debit was \$12184.91 million & net was \$29192.44 million, in Abroad total credit of Foreign direct investment was \$1118.16 million, debit was \$6528.01 million & net was \$-5409.85 million, Portfolio investment total credit of investment was \$129307.7 million, debit was \$121668.4 million & net was \$7639.32 million , in India total credit of Foreign Portfolio investment was \$128288.9 million, debit was \$119455.6 million & net was \$8833.26 million, in Abroad total credit of Foreign Portfolio investment was \$1018.82 million, debit was \$2212.77 million & net was \$-1193.94 million , total amount of loans credit was \$38883.3 million , debit was \$40598.17 million & net was \$-1714.87 million, whereas total amount of External assistance credit was \$8935.36 million , debit was \$2975.26 million & net was \$5960.09 million, total amount of commercial borrowing credit was \$12268.92 million , debit was \$17930.9 million & net was \$-5661.97 million, total amount of Short term credit to India total credit was \$17679.01 million , debit was \$19692 million & net was \$-2013 million. The total amount of banking capital credit was \$36539.92 million, debit was \$45485.54 million & net was \$-8945.62 million, whereas total amount of commercial bank credit was \$36526.63 million, debit was \$44718.15 million & net was \$-8191.52 million & other banking capital credit was \$13.29404 million, debit was \$767.3902 million & net was \$-754.096 million. The rupee debt services total amount credit was \$0.0 million, debit was \$57.199 million & net was \$-57.199 million. Other capital credit was \$33243.89 million, debit was \$37475.27 million & net was \$-4231.38 million.

Over all balance of payment in 200-01, total credit was \$339841 million, debit was \$324789 million & net was \$15052 million. In 2011-12 total credit was \$1007811 million, debit was \$1020643 million & net was \$-12831 million, in 2019-20 total credit was \$1254037 million, debit was \$1194539 million & net was \$59498 million in 2020-21 (Apr-Nov) total credit was \$554528.1 million, debit was \$503113.4 million & net was \$51414.66 million.

Monetary movement in 2000-01, total credit was \$1448 million, debit was \$7316 million & net was \$-5868 million, whereas monetary movement IMF total credit was \$0.0 million, debit was \$26 million & net was \$-26 million & the monetary movement of Foreign exchange reserve total credit was \$1448 million, debit was \$7290 million & net was \$-5842 million. In 2011-12 Monetary movement total credit was \$12831 million, debit was \$0.0 million & net was \$12831 million, whereas monetary movement IMF total credit was \$0.0 million, debit was \$0.0 million & net was \$0.0 million & the monetary movement of Foreign exchange reserve total credit was \$12831 million, debit was \$0.0 million & net was \$12831 million. In 2019-20 Monetary movement total credit was \$0.0 million, debit was \$59498 million & net was \$-59498 million, whereas the monetary movement of Foreign exchange reserve total credit was \$0.0 million, debit was \$59498 million & net was \$-59498 million. In 2020-21 (Apr-Nov) Monetary movement total credit was \$0.0 million, debit was \$51414.66 million & net was \$-51414.67 million, whereas the monetary movement of Foreign exchange reserve total credit was \$0.0 million, debit was \$51414.66 million & net was \$-51414.67 million.

Global Export & Import rank

India rank 32 in 1999-2000 in the list of top 30 merchandise exporters & 26 rank in the list of top 30 merchandise importers. In 2003-04 India rank 30 in the list of top 30 merchandise exporters & 24 in the list of top 30 merchandise importers. In 2008-09 India rank 26 in the list of top 30 merchandise exporters & 17 in the list of top 30 merchandise importers.

Global rank in India		
Year	Rank in Export	Rank in Import
1999-2000	32	26
2000-01	31	26
2001-02	30	27
2002-03	30	24
2003-04	30	24
2004-05	30	23
2005-06	29	17
2006-07	28	17
2007-08	26	18
2008-09	26	17
2009-10	21	14
2010-11	20	13
2011-12	19	12
2012-13	19	10
2013-14	19	12
2014-15	19	12
2015-16	19	Nil
2016-17	20	14
2017-18	20	11
2018-19	19	10
2019-20	18	10
2020-21(Apr-Nov)	19	10

Source:- WTO library

In 2017-18 India rank 20 in the list of top 30 merchandise exporters & 11 in the list of top 30 merchandise importers. In 2019-20 India rank 18 in the list of top 30 merchandise exporters & 10 in the list of top 30 merchandise importers. In 2020-21 India rank 19 in the list of top 30 merchandise exporters & 10 in the list of top 30 merchandise importers. Due to the pandemic it effect the global rank in India export.

Foreign Trade Policy in India:-

The Department of Commerce has the mandate to make India a major player in global trade and assume a role of leadership in international trade organizations commensurate with India's growing importance. The Department devises commodity and country-specific strategy in the medium term and strategic plan/vision and India's Foreign Trade Policy in the long run.

India's Foreign Trade Policy (FTP) provides the basic framework of policy and strategy for promoting exports and trade. It is periodically reviewed to adapt to the changing domestic and international scenario.

The meeting of the committee of the **Ministry of Commerce & Industry** was held on 12th January, 2021 on the subject of 'New Foreign Trade Policy' for the tenure of 2021 – 2026. On April 1, India was to unveil the Foreign Trade Policy 2021-2026. The existing policy was extended by a year due to Covid-19, which was to end on March 31. And the government decided to further extend it for 6 more months. The current policy will now be valid up to September 30. The foreign

trade policy (FTP) outlines government strategies and steps to promote domestic production and exports with the objective of driving economic growth.

It remains to see how the new policy gets affected after India battles the second wave of the pandemic. The new policy is eagerly awaited as the economy continues to reel from the effects of the pandemic and disruptions to international trade caused by lockdowns and restrictions worldwide. The UN World Economic Situation and Prospects 2021 report says India's economy shrank 9.6% in 2020 against a global average of 4.3%. It projects a 7.3% growth for India in 2021. Hopes for a turnaround rest largely on exports picking up. Exporters expect the new policy to include initiatives aimed at improving India's standing in global merchandise and services exports and to correct the deficiencies of Foreign Trade Policy 2015-2020.

The main mission of the new foreign trade policy is to make India a leader in the International Trade in the next 5 years, i.e. 2021 – 26.

Impact of Covid-19 on foreign trade:-

The outbreak of Covid-19 caused a massive economic recession, with six out of the seven largest economies showing a massive GDP loss in the third quarter of 2020. Since March 2020, lockdowns became a global necessity, and the Indian subcontinent was no exception, announcing its first nation-wide lockdown by the end of March India Govt. implement the lockdown due to increases the infection. Other Govt. in world also implement the lockdown due to the globally lockdown Reduced mobility and the unavailability of resources, due to restricted borders caused significant challenges to traditional retailers. The automotive industry, in particular, emerged as one of the worst impacted industries. Simultaneously, petroleum consumption decreased. Other industries such as healthcare or fast-moving consumer goods, were less effected due to their indispensability and local shopper clientele.

The Covid-19 pandemic laid additional stress on the country's already struggling economy. With a GDP growth of just three percent in the fourth quarter of the financial year 2020, a drop of more than 20 percent in the next quarter came as a huge blow. The markets reacted differently to the crisis, which was reflected in their growth rate. The automotive market was hit the hardest by the lockdown, as it showed the maximum negative growth. While most industries were shaken to their core, financial, real estate, and professional services were estimated to incur huge losses. In May 2020, the unemployment levels reached a new high with more than 27 percent of the country's labor force unemployed.

India was greatly affected by the Covid-19 pandemic in various sectors. Intending to get hold of the situation, India announced its first nation-wide lockdown in March 2020, which led to the economic slowdown. Consequently, international trade took a huge hit as well. In April 2021, imported commodities, specifically silver, pulses and newsprint, faced more than 27 percent decline compared to previous year. By contrast, gold, precious, semi-precious stones and pearls, had a positive change rate.

Petroleum products were the most affected commodities in terms of exports from India, with a decline of about 32 percent in January 2021, compared to the same month in the previous year. Other cereals and oil meals witnessed a highly positive change rate

Conclusion:-

Over the study period it has been observed that total exports of India has increased after the adoption of New Economic policy in India. Although India is facing continuous deficit in its balance of payment but the overall prosperity is unbounded. In spite of fluctuations in GDP growth rate, the volume of trade is increasing day by day. The composition of India's exports has grown up significantly. The export of petroleum has shown a considerable increasing trend. Major portion of Indian exports is in manufactured goods. The composition of India's imports has also grown up significantly. It has also shown a positive and increasing trend during the period under study. The share of imports of petroleum and crude products and other non-bulk items have increased significantly while the imports of food grains and export related items have declined. The study also indicates that post liberalization era has certainly helped India in achieving high growth in the economy as there has been a rapid growth of imports of capital goods and technical raw materials to meet the requirement of industrialization and growing imports of petroleum products for meeting industrial and consumption requirement. It is also found that though import has a negative influence on economic growth, the volume of trade reflected by economic openness have a positive impact on the economic growth of India and its magnitude is increasing continuously.

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Thank You